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Protection of Consumer Rights in India and Bangladesh: A Comparative Study

DISSERTATION

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CERTIFICATE

It gives me pleasure to certify that **Md. Taybur Rahman** bearing LLM ID No: MU20LLM006, has completed his dissertation captioned "***Protection of Consumer Rights in India and Bangladesh: A Comparative Study***" under my guidance and supervision. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the work has not formed the basis for the award previously of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title, and the work is suitable for submission in the fulfillment of the requirement of the award of the Degree of Master of Laws.

I wish him success in every walk of life.

DR. SHIVAKANT PRAJAPATI

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DECLARATION

I, **Md. Taybur Rahman**, LLM ID No: **MU20LLM006**, Present resident of Mats Boys Hostel, Mats University, Raipur (CG) and Permanent address is Khulna, Bangladesh, hereby state that the research work on “**Protection of Consumer Rights in India and Bangladesh: A comparative study**” carried out by me for the Fulfillment of Award of the Degree of **Master of Laws** from Mats Law School, Mats University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India during the years 2020-2022 is a record of my own work and that the **Dissertation** has not formed the basis for the award previously of any degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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Md. Taybur Rahman

Date: 25 May, 2022

Place: Raipur (CG), India

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Md. Taybur Rahman

Date: 25 May, 2022

Place: Raipur (CG), India

ABSTRACT

Protection of consumer rights is considered an essential part of human rights. India and Bangladesh have had a vast number of consumers. Consumer means the person who uses or consumes any product or goods in exchange for the price. It has become the daily routine of the traders to fool the consumers by charging high prices by the shopkeepers, supplying low-quality products, and misleading them. Consumers may not be satisfied after purchasing goods due to some unscrupulous traders. Both countries have consumer protection Acts to protect against such unscrupulous traders. Namely, The Indian Consumer Protection Act, 1986 replaced 2019, and The Bangladesh Consumer Protection Act, 2009. Various government departments are working to protect the rights of consumers through this Acts, but they do not get the expected results because they do not take care of them seriously, and their work is completed at a slow pace. Moreover, some non-governmental organizations are working on consumer rights, but their activities do not reach them as there are many consumers. Therefore, more non-governmental organizations need to come forward. Several consumers live in villages, so many of them do not know about the protection of consumer rights due to a lack of education. Government and Non-government organizations need to come forward to increase consumer awareness. Several consumers in India and Bangladesh still do not know the exact details of their rights and responsibility.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IOCU-The International Organization Consumers Unions

BC -Before Christ

AD-Anno Domini

US-United State of America

UK-United Kingdom

FAO-The Food and Agriculture Organization

UN-United Nations

ILO-International Labour Organisation

WHO-World Health Organisation

UNIDA-The United Nations International Development Agency

UNCTD-The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development

CI-Consumers International

CPA -The Consumer Protection Act, 2019

CRPA-The Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009

CCPA-Central Consumer Protection Authority

BIS-The Bureau of Indian Standard

DG-Director General

NCDRC-National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission

CCPC-Central Consumer Protection Council

CRO-Consumer Rights Organisation

CGSI-Consumer Guidance Society of India

CAI-Consumer Association of India

CAB-Consumer Association of Bangladesh

TABLE OF CASES

- 1) Neena Aneja and Ors. v Jai Prakash Associates Ltd, MANU/SC/0190/2021
- 2) Srinath v. Union of India, (AIR 1996 Mad 427)
- 3) Development Authority v. M.K.Gupta, (1994) ISCC 243)
- 4) Lucknow Development Authority vs. M.K.Gupta [III (1993) CPJ 7]
- 5) S.B.Singh Gurjan v. Telecommunication Department Jodhpur,(2005) II CPJ 6 NC
- 6) Tirumurugan Co-operative Agrl. Credit Society vs. M.Lalitha (Attached hereinbelow) through legal representatives & Ors, (2004 CTJ 1 SC)
- 7) Common Cause vs. Union of India I (1993) CPJ 1 (SC)
- 8) Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh vs states and others, Writ Petition 2010
- 9) Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr, Civil Appeal No(S). 21552 Of 2017 (India)
- 10) Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited, Civil IVIL Appeal No 1879 Of 2003 (India)
- 11) Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors, Civil Appeal No.4119 Of 1999 (India)

TABLE OF STATUTES

- 1) The Consumer Protection Act, 2019 (India)
- 2) The Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020 (India)
- 3) The Constitution of India
- 4) Trade Marks Acts, 1999 (India)
- 5) Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (India)
- 6) The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016
- 7) The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940(Amendment 2008) (India)
- 8) The Sale of Goods Act, 1930 (India)
- 9) The Agricultural Produce Act, 1937(India)
- 10) The Indian Penal Code, 1860
- 11) The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh,1972
- 12) The Consumer Rights Protection Act (CRPA), 2009 (Bangladesh)
- 13) Digital Commerce Operational Guideline 2021(Bangladesh)
- 14) Sale of Goods Act 1930 (Bangladesh)
- 15) The Bangladesh Penal Code 1860
- 16) The Dangerous Drug Act 1940 (Bangladesh)
- 17) The Special Powers Act 1974(Bangladesh)
- 18) Control of Essential Commodities Act, 1956 (Bangladesh)
- 19) Trademark Act 2009 (Bangladesh)
- 20) The Mobile Court Act, 2009 (Bangladesh)

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Chapter: One

Introduction

1.1: Introduction:

Bangladesh is a small country with a large number of people, and also India has a vast population. The two countries have huge numbers of consumers. A consumer buys a product or service for himself or his family. A consumer does not accept a product or service for resale. Consumer rights are neglected in both countries. Consumer rights are violated in India and Bangladesh due to some unscrupulous businessmen. Therefore, it is essential to make consumers aware of their fundamental rights to protect them from unfair and aggressive business practices.

Consumer rights are an essential aspect that every business should consider. Because it is possible to develop the business by protecting the rights of the consumers, the economy can move towards an expanded state through social development. Most companies provide low-quality products to consumers and do not provide detailed information about the products. And, most manufacturers create unhealthy environments in their products and provide fraudulent advertisements by giving incomplete information about the products to attract consumers.

They market duplicate products that are in high demand among consumers, and these products are difficult to distinguish encouraging consumers to diversify by substituting low-quality products to buy those products. Consumers purchase such products and then express dissatisfaction. In some cases, intermediaries create artificial food crises for higher profits. Consumers need to be educated to protect themselves from such traders.

To win consumers' trust, the government has to take all necessary measures and protect it by law. The governments of India and Bangladesh have enacted laws to establish the rights of consumers. Namely, The Indian Consumer Protection Act, 1986 replaced 2019, and The Bangladesh Consumer Protection Act, 2009.

Moreover, various non-governmental organizations are working for consumers. If consumers are protected, there will be social progress, and at the same time, the country will move towards prosperity. In addition, the government needs to take effective action to increase consumer awareness, and the private sector needs to come forward to establish consumer rights.

More needs to be researched with consumer rights. So that consumers can know the correct information and the government can learn about the consumer and take necessary action.

1.2: Background:

There are United Nations Guidelines for consumer protection (UNGCP), which were first adopted by the United Nation General Assembly (UNGA) on April 16,1985. The UNGCP are considered “a valuable set of principles for setting out the main characteristics of effective consumer protection legislation, enforcement institutions and redress systems and for assisting interested member states in formulating and enforcing domestic and regional laws, rules and regulations that are suitable to their own economic and social and environmental circumstance, as well as promoting international enforcement cooperation among member states and encouraging the sharing of experiences in consumer protection. The UNGCP has been expended/ updated twice since then, with new resolution adopted in 1999 and 2015respectively. Thereafter, countries have initiated steps to set-up legal mechanisms for grievance redressal as well as making consumers aware of their rights, responsibilities and duties. Consumer protection focuses on making them aware of products or services, their characteristics and the other aspects including place to buy, price, and the need etc¹.

In India, the consumer movement as a social force' arose from the need to protect and promote consumers' interests against unethical and unfair trade practices. Food shortages, hoarding, black marketing, and adulteration of food and edible oil gave birth to an organized consumer movement in the 1960s. Until the 1970s, consumer organizations were mainly concerned with writing articles and organizing exhibitions. They formed consumer groups to investigate ration shop fraud and overcrowding in road passenger transportation. It took many years for organizations in India and around the world to raise public awareness. Because of all of these efforts, the movement was able to put pressure on business firms as well as the government to correct business practices that were unfair and against the interests of consumers as a whole. The Consumer Protection Act 1986, enacted by the Indian government in 1986, was a significant

¹ Dr. Chatar Singh Negi and Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Consumer protection in India: Empowering consumer, 10, International Journal of Development Research. 02, 33873-33877 (2020)

step. The Indian Consumer Protection Act, 1986 became obsolete in protecting the rights of consumers. In particular, the law does not apply to online shopping, unsafe deals and misleading advertising. This is why it was felt to replace it with the Consumer Protection Act, 2019.

Many people of the Bangladesh don't know about their rights and responsibility as a consumer and have no concept or education about it. For this reason, everyday they are being hunted by corruption and dishonesty. Bangladesh is a small country with largest consumer comparing its small area. Many sectors have been developed in Bangladesh after independence but consumer protection have not been improved properly. Though there is lot of organizations working for human rights but only Consumer Associations of Bangladesh (CAB) are working for consumer protection. In Bangladesh, consumers are treated negligently and their rights are violated in every sector². Development in many sectors took place in Bangladesh after independence. For a long time after independence, there was no law for protection of consumer rights in Bangladesh, but in 2009 the law was enacted to protect consumer rights.

1.3: Statement of Problem:

Every consumer buys different products and services from the market to fulfill their needs. But sometimes, consumers cannot be satisfied with products and services because of product quality, harmful products, poor service, over-pricing by the shopkeeper, and misleading advertisements. These problems are more common in Bangladesh and India because of unskilled salespeople, lack of awareness, and some unscrupulous people who are greedy for profit.

Moreover, greedy merchants market counterfeit goods to consumers to make more profit. Consumers do not easily understand whether these products are genuine or fake. Many manufacturers make products in an unhealthy environment and market these harmful products, and consumers are encouraged to sell these products with diversified advertisements. It is impossible to select quality products and choose the right one due to consumer awareness.

² Md. Emran Hossain, Consumer Protection in the Context of Existing Laws in Bangladesh,5, JETIR,671,676-681 (2018)

Consumers later express dissatisfaction because many manufacturers do not provide accurate information about their products.

India and Bangladesh have no political commitment or program to protect consumers. In some cases, political parties may seek help from merchants and manufacturers, who create artificial crises in the market and stockpile goods for unlimited profits from the general person. The government machinery is fragile in terms of implementation as the government machinery does not work correctly. So the non-government organization should come forward to help the consumers.

Therefore, everyone should be aware of their rights as consumers. Consumers need to learn how to protect themselves and be reasonable buyers when shopping online or offline.

1.4: Reason for Choosing Topic:

The vast majority of people in India and Bangladesh live in villages. They are unaware of consumer rights protection and the law. Furthermore, many people in urban areas do not know about consumer rights and laws. A consumer purchases goods for his or her own use or for the needs of his or her family. If there is any dissatisfaction with the product, the consumer cannot return the product due to some restrictions. At this opportunity, some unscrupulous traders provide unsafe products, adulterated products, or substandard products to the market for more profit. Raising awareness to protect the rights of consumers and inform them about the laws of India and Bangladesh. Actually, this is the main reason though there are some other reasons to choose the topics which are also very important, that are-

- Consumers do not want to learn about consumer rights independently, and the government can't inform individual consumers about consumer rights.
- Consumers do not try to know about the protection of rights on their own due to a lack of education.
- Political parties do not take any action to make consumers aware.
- Promoting and not given advertising about consumer rights.

- Consumers do not have the right idea about complaints and remedies.

1.5: Limitations of Research:

Researchers have encountered many limitations, the most notable of which are:

First limitation was time limit; there was a specific time to complete this research. Due to the particular time, it was impossible to gather much information. The second limitation was the gathering of information; India and Bangladesh were locked down for a long time due to coronavirus infections worldwide. All the institutions were closed on the orders of the government. Due to this, the Researcher could not collect any information from the University library and public library. Another limitation is that it was not available to gather information on this research topic.

1.6: Review of Literature:

The goal of this study is to identify the major flaws in the protection of consumer rights. I will attempt to research existing literature to comprehend the fundamental features of Consumer Protection in India and Bangladesh and their legal resources.

Books:

- 1) Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law (Asia Law House 2021), India
- 1) Ahamuduzzaman and Syeda Shamsia Husain, Consumer Protection Law, Law Book Company, Dhaka, 2011

These books clarify the concept of consumer, consumer protection, consumer protection law development, product safety, history of consumer's rights protection.

Statutes:

- 1) The Consumer Protection Act, 2019 (India)
- 2) The Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020 (India)
- 3) The Constitution of India
- 4) Trade Marks Acts, 1999 (India)
- 5) Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (India)

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- 6) The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016
 - 7) The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940(Amendment 2008) (India)
 - 8) The Sale of Goods Act, 1930 (India)
 - 9) The Agricultural Produce Act, 1937(India)
 - 10) The Indian Penal Code, 1860
 - 11) The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh,1972
 - 12) The Consumer Rights Protection Act (CRPA), 2009 (Bangladesh)
 - 13) Digital Commerce Operational Guideline 2021(Bangladesh)
 - 14) Sale of Goods Act 1930 (Bangladesh)
 - 15) The Bangladesh Penal Code 1860
 - 16) The Dangerous Drug Act 1940 (Bangladesh)
 - 17) The Special Powers Act 1974(Bangladesh)
 - 18) Control of Essential Commodities Act, 1956 (Bangladesh)
 - 19) Trademark Act 2009 (Bangladesh)
 - 20) The Mobile Court Act, 2009 (Bangladesh)

These statutes clarify the concept of Consumer rights protection, Consumer remedies, Offense, and penalty, how to establish a Consumer department in India and Bangladesh, and what can do for consumers.

Articles/Journals:

- 1) 1 Dr. Chatar Singh Negi and Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Consumer protection in India: Empowering consumer, 10, International Journal of Development Research. 02, 33873-33877 (2020)
- 2) Md. Emran Hossain, Consumer Protection in the Context of Existing Laws in Bangladesh,5, JETIR,671,676-681 (2018)
- 3) Law Student, Consumer Rights in Bangladesh: A Critical Study, Bangladesh Journal of Legal Studies, (January 23, 2022, 12:19 AM), <https://bdjls.org/consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-a-critical-study#one>

- 4) Dr. A. Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, 132, Journal of Texas Consumer Law, 132-136, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/JCCL_India.pdf
- 5) R.P. Kangle, *The Kautiliya Arthasastra. Part III A Study 116 (2000)*
- 6) Diya Berger, "A Tale of Two Movements: Consumer Protection in the U.S. from 1969 to 2010" 02 May 2013. CUREJ: College Undergraduate Research Electronic Journal, University of Pennsylvania, <https://repository.upenn.edu/curej/168>.
- 7) Peck, Linda, "Consuming Splendor: Society and Culture in Seventeenth-Century England", Cambridge Press, 2005
- 8) Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Consumer Organizations and the Right to Adequate Food, FAO, April 12, 2022, <https://www.fao.org/3/cb3685en/cb3685en.pdf>
- 9) WIPO, The Role of Industrial Property in the Protection of Consumers, WIPO Publication, April 13, 2022, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/wipo_pub_648.pdf
- 10) Dr. Manoj Kumar Padhy, Consumer Protection Jurisprudence: A Constitutional Perspective, Rostrum's Law review (13 May, 2022 1.26 Pm), <https://journal.rostrumlegal.com/consumer-protection-jurisprudence-a-constitutional-perspective/>
- 11) Sheetal Sahoo & Aman Chatterjee, Consumer Protection - Problems and Prospects (13 May 2022 1.43 Pm, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1452526
- 12) Zahangir Alam Khan, Consumer Justice in Bangladesh: A Critical Study of Laws & Rules, 64 (17 January 2016)
- 13) Gazi Delwar Hosen and Syed Robayet Ferdous, The Role of Mobile Courts in the Enforcement of Laws in Bangladesh, Volume I (2010) The Northern University Journal of Law 82, 82 (2010)
- 14) Mr. Mohd Rafiq Dar, Role of judiciary in protection of consumers with special reference to telecom industry in India. Aligarh Muslim University (India), 2012, <file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/judiciary.pdf>

These articles contain several concepts of protecting consumer rights and consumer's awareness, consumer's education, and how government departments work with consumers.

Case Law:

- 1) Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr, Civil Appeal No(S). 21552 Of 2017 (India)
- 2) Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited, Civil IVIL Appeal No 1879 Of 2003 (India)
- 3) Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors, Civil Appeal No.4119 Of 1999 (India)

These Case laws clarify several concepts of consumer justice and the judiciary's role in consumer Rights, and how to provide consumer remedies.

News Papers:

- 1) Law desk, An overview of the Digital Commerce Operation Guidelines 2021, The daily star, 10 may, 2022, 8.14 pm, <https://www.thedailystar.net/law-our-rights/news/overview-the-digital-commerce-operation-guidelines-2021-2128871>
- 2) PTI, CCPA imposes Rs 10 lakh penalty on Sure Vision for misleading ads, The Economic Times (28 May 2022)
- 3) PTI, Centre warns cab aggregators of strict action for unfair trade practices, The Economic Times (10 May 2022)
- 4) PM,<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/technology/centre-warns-cab-aggregators-of-strict-action-for-unfair-trade-practices/articleshow/91465856.cms>
- 5) Ipsita Bhattacharya, Haircut gone wrong! ITC Maurya in Delhi ordered to pay Rs 2 crore compensation to woman for bad haircut, Zee News (24 September 2021 10.11 AM),<https://zeenews.india.com/india/haircut-gone-wrong-itc-maurya-in-delhi-ordered-to-pay-rs-2-crore-compensation-to-woman-for-bad-haircut-2396624.html>
- 6) Moinul Haque, Consumer rights hardly respected, Newage (15 March 2022 00:00), <https://www.newagebd.net/article/165440/consumer-rights-hardly-respected>
- 7) Prothom Alo district reporter,The trader was fined Tk 50,000 for selling soybean oil at a higher price, Prothom Alo (23 May 2022 19:01), <https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/district/%E0%A6%AC%E0%A7%87>

- 8) Prothom Alo district reporter, Raid on flour shop in Savar, fine of Rs 1.5 lakh, Prothom Alo (17 May 2022 17:04),<https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/district/%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%AD%E0%A6%BE%E0>
- 9) HG Legal Resources, <https://www.hg.org/legal-articles/protecting-consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-39014>, (29 May 2022 1.28 AM)
- 10) The Daily Star, Filing complaint by consumers, (14 March 2017 12:00 AM), <https://www.thedailystar.net/law-our-rights/filing-complaint-consumers-1375501>,
- 11) Staff Reporter, Welcome court directives on consumer rights, Newage, Jun 19,2019 00:05, <https://www.newagebd.net/article/75795/article/index.php>
- 12) Moniruzzaman Uzzal, Food adulteration reaches new height, Dhakatribune, April 29th, 2014 09:01 pm,<https://archive.dhakatribune.com/uncategorized/2014/04/29/food-adulteration-reaches-new-height>

This news provides the concept of the current condition of consumers and what to do for consumers.

1.7: Objective of Research:

I have observed the objects for my research as under the following:

1. To clarify the concept of consumer rights
2. To explore the current legal framework for the protection of consumers' rights.
3. To explore the protection of consumers' rights in the current situation.
4. To examine consumer awareness and the practical approach.
5. To make some recommendations for protecting the rights of consumers.

1.8: Research Hypothesis:

This research is a comparative study on the protection of consumers' rights in India and Bangladesh. So some of the hypotheses of this research are given:

- A comparison of the legal frameworks in place to protect consumer rights in India and Bangladesh.
- To compare consumer awareness and practical approaches in India and Bangladesh.
- The role of the judiciary in protecting consumer rights in India and Bangladesh

1.9: Research Methodology:

This study will follow the doctrinal research analyses in India and Bangladesh. This study will examine and evaluate the present conditions of the laws and practices in this respect. Discussion on the conceptual issues will be based on the secondary literature and books, journals, electronic materials, and statutory and case laws.

1.10: Sources and Materials:

The study will be based on secondary data. The secondary data will be collected from the literature on the topic, journal, news article, books, reports on both government authorities and non-government organizations, and also data will be collected from the internet. The collected data will be classified and analyzed according to the different objectives and variables of the study.

1.11: Importance of Research:

The consumer is the market's king because the company profits from them. They play a vital role in the economy of a country. To increase profits in the present competitive economy in India and Bangladesh, traders can use unfair, unsafe products, adulterated products, substandard products, black market, and misleading advertisements.

This is to inform the consumers about their rights and give them ideas about the law not to fall prey to any fraud. Protecting consumers will play a role in a country's economic growth and to increase consumers' awareness and create interest in knowing accurate information about the product. So that consumers can stay away from unsafe products, contaminated products, low-quality products, and misleading advertisements. Consumers can lead to social development and

protect the family. Consumers will be able to know about their rights, laws, and comparisons of consumer protection' rights in India and Bangladesh as a result of this research.

1.12: Chapter Outline:

Chapter: 1: Introduction

Chapter: 2: The concept and history of consumer rights

Chapter: 3: Comparative legal framework

Chapter: 4: Consumer awareness and practical approach to protect consumer rights

Chapter: 5: Present status of Consumer Rights Protection

Chapter: 6: The judiciary's perspective on the protection of consumer rights

Chapter: 7: Conclusion and Suggestions

1.13: Conclusion:

Protecting consumer rights is a significant issue. Despite being an important issue, it is not discussed much anywhere. Moreover, important newspapers do not publish such articles on this issue due to political pressure and avoid unpleasant incidents. Raising consumer awareness and encouraging social values so that consumers can stay away from adulterated, substandard product suppliers so that consumers are unaware of their rights.

Many people live in rural areas; there are many dishonest business people. Therefore, people in rural areas need awareness to protect themselves from illegal traders. Non-governmental organizations are not coming forward and are not seen to protect the rights of consumers effectively. They need to come forward so that the non-government organization can play a leading role in protecting the rights of consumers. Law enforcement agencies need to be strict to protect consumers from unscrupulous traders.

A consumer acts as the driving force of a country's economic growth. The onus is on the government to protect the rights of consumers. Similarly, a consumer needs to be aware of his or her rights. So that a consumer can buy a safe and quality product at the time of purchase and take legal action if something is illegal.

Chapter: Two

The Concept and History of Consumer Rights

2.1: Introduction:

At present, the protection of consumer rights has become a significant issue. Consumer rights have existed since ancient Indian times, but there was no law-making and law-enforcement system. Then the king or the head of the dynasty would punish the dishonest traders. Later, Later, during the Mughal rule, written orders were issued for the protection of consumers and market surveillance to enforce the orders and punish the wrong traders. In the Indian subcontinent, the British government enacted written laws to protect consumers and executed them. According to the law, rogue traders are punished. To this end, the Government of India enacted a comprehensive law in 1985 to protect consumers. However, with the increase in e-commerce, misleading advertisements, and fraud of traders, the Act was amended in 2019. Similarly, in 2009 the government of Bangladesh made a law for the protection of consumers, but this law could not play a role in implementation and enforcement. At present, to protect the rights of consumers, increase consumers' awareness and make more effective laws against rogue traders, misleading advertisements, black market, middlemen and provide punishment.

2.2: Concept of consumer rights:

Consumer movements spread worldwide to protect consumers from exploitation by unscrupulous manufacturers, traders, and service providers. Almost all countries have enacted laws to protect consumers and the welfare of society. In India and Bangladesh, the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 and the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009, were enacted to provide better protection to the interests of consumers. Provision was made for the establishment of a consumer protection authority for the settlement of consumer disputes. Consumer markets for goods and services have changed dramatically since the India Consumer Protection Act 1986. The modern market is full of products and services. The rise of the global supply chain, the growth of international trade, and the rapid development of e-commerce have led to new delivery systems for products and services and unique options and opportunities for consumers. Equally, it puts the consumer at risk for new types of unfair trade and unethical business practices. Misleading advertising, telemarketing, multi-level marketing, direct sales, and e-commerce pose challenges to consumer

protection and require appropriate and rapid executive intervention to prevent consumer harm. Therefore, The Indian Consumer Protection Act, 1986 was replaced in 2019. In 1985, the United Nations issued guidelines for the protection of consumers, which many countries followed. This led to the formation of the National Consumer Protection Agency, led by Consumer International, which is made up of many consumer organizations from 115 countries.

2.3: Meaning of Consumer and Consumerism:

A consumer is a person who acquires goods and services for his or her own personal needs. Consumer is an individual who buys products or services for personal use and not for manufacture or resale. A consumer is someone who can make the decision whether or not to purchase an item at the store, and someone who can be influenced by marketing and advertisements. A consumer is one that buys goods for consumption and not for resale and commercial purpose. The consumer is an individual who pays some amount of money or the thing required to consumer goods and services. As such, consumers play a vital role in the economic system of a nation. Without consumer demand, producers would lack one of the key motivations to produce to sell to consumers. The consumer also forms part of the chain of distribution.³

Consumerism believes that expanding the use of market-acquired products and services is always a desirable goal and that one's well-being and happiness are inextricably linked with one's ability to purchase consumer goods and commodities. In terms of economics, it is mainly associated with the Keynesian notion that consumer spending is the primary driver of the economy, and encouraging people to spend is a direct government goal. From this perspective, spending is a beneficial factor that promotes economic growth. Consumption, in general usage, refers to the tendency of people living in a capitalist system to lead an overly materialistic lifestyle that reflects reflection, waste, or exhibit excessive enjoyment. In this sense, consumerism is widely recognized as a loss of traditional values and livelihoods, consumer exploitation, environmental damage, and detrimental psychological reactions by big businesses.

³ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 1 (Asia Law House 2021)

2.4: Types of Consumer: A service or product manufacturing company needs to recognize different consumers when they target their products for profit. Some types of consumers are:

Commercial Consumers: Businesses of all types are a significant consumer group, and they also have the advantage of being able to buy a large number of goods because they can afford to. Many commercial and business consumers buy wholesale and then negotiate prices with their suppliers, which most other consumers cannot do. A marketing or advertising firm cannot overlook this distinct group when it comes to commercial, retail, wholesale, and industrial consumers. Commercial consumers can include non-profit organizations and governmental entities in addition to traditional corporations. They frequently buy in large quantities or bulk, and depending on the product they require; they may have special requirements associated with their purchases, such as the need for a person to work with purchase orders. These customers directly impact what retail and end-user customers can afford to pay for goods and services, so they are not a consumer group to be overlooked.

Discretionary Spending Consumers: These customers have a lot of extra money to spend, and they frequently have unusual purchasing habits. Teenagers, for example, spend a lot of money on things like clothes and electronics, even during a recession. For this reason, for the most part, teenagers have no bills to pay, so every penny they earn is theirs to keep and spend. Even though their purchasing habits fluctuate on their parents' income, this is a consistent and dependable consumer group that all marketing companies should strive to reach regularly.

Extroverted Consumers: Extroverted customers are high-energy, very social in all aspects of their lives, and excited about everything life offers. Extroverted consumers favor companies that focus on distinctiveness and emotional energy because they have a greater need to communicate with others than the average person. They are more inclined than other customers to be brand loyal, and once you have them as a customer, they are likely to stay that way for the rest of their lives.

Inferior Goods Consumers: The word "inferior" does not necessarily mean that the items purchased are poor quality but rather that consumers with lower incomes tend to buy goods at lower prices. One prominent example is that they frequently prefer store brands over items

bearing a well-known brand name. Consumers of inferior goods look at the price first rather than the brand. When their income falls, they tend to spend more money on inferior goods, but they continue to buy them. As a result, a marketing or promotion firm should consider the consumers of inferior goods to be an influential group to market.

Loyal Consumers: They are typically a small but significant consumer group that will continue to do business with a person because they are highly loyal to either person's product or store. One of the most significant benefits of having loyal customers is that they love to tell their family and friends about the benefits of shopping with a shop, and as a result, a shop can gain a lot more customers in the end.

2.5: Characteristics of a Consumer:

The consumer is the last means of using the product. He buys the product himself or for family use. Consumers want their essential products to be available 24 hours a day and seven days a week. Many shop owners are now trying to sell products for a more extended period to meet the needs of consumers. Retailers cannot sell products after a particular time of the day. But consumers may need the product at any time. Consumers all the time want to get the product of their choice quickly. Moreover, they are interested in bargaining to determine the product's price. A class of consumers likes to buy products at a fixed price. At the same time, the consumer can make any decision while purchasing the product; no one can force it. They go from one store to another, buying whatever they like or deciding which brand of goods to buy. To buy a good product, they read and watch different content to know about its quality. Nowadays, consumers browse the e-commerce website before purchasing a product; they can learn about the price and quality of their product. They can quickly check and choose which product to buy by visiting there and ordering at any time. Consumers are wanted to buy the necessary products at all times easily, cheaply, and with good quality rich products.

2.6: Importance of Consumer Protection:

Impart market information: Most consumers do not know about the product they are buying and do not have any information about the goods. According to the rules, when marketing goods,

the product package should have all the information about the product. But unscrupulous traders do not disclose any information about the product. For this reason, consumers do not know about the product. At the same time, consumers suffer a lot of loss because they do not know about the product.

Physical Safety: Adulterated products are risky for health. Some unscrupulous traders are constantly marketing adulterated products, and uneducated and poor people buy those products for little money. By doing so, people and their families are at health risk. Consumers need protection from health risks.

Misconduct: Different companies are constantly being established, at the same time creating competition with other companies. In this unequal competition, the consumer cannot buy the product by determining the quality and verifying the excellent goods. Because of unequal contest, traders supply adulterated products at low prices dishonestly. As a result, consumers' health risks are increasing day by day. Illegal business practices can often lead to severe product shortages in the market, forcing consumers to buy essential products at higher prices. Artificial product shortages deprive consumers of their rights.

Misleading advertisement: Some companies, shops, and unscrupulous merchants use deceptive advertising to entice consumers to buy products. As a result the consumer expresses dissatisfaction after purchasing the goods.

2.7: Parties of Consumer protection:

Consumers:

So consumers, as far as possible, should take care of their interests and protect themselves from market irregularities. This requires knowing about their rights and trying to enforce them. Traders should not rely on good or bad. Consumers have the right to education and the freedom to listen. They should attend training programs for consumers organized by local consumer associations or their associations and invite consumer activists to talk to them about consumer rights and the remedies available under the law to protect them.

Businessman:

We expect producers, distributors, dealers, wholesalers, and retailers to pay due respect to consumer rights in their interest. They should ensure the supply of quality products and services at fair prices. To prevent unfair practices, traders 'associations, chambers of commerce and industry, and manufacturers' associations should consider consumer complaints against their members and take appropriate action against those responsible.

Government:

Consumer protection is a responsibility in the general interest of society. In the light of the views of the consumer association, it is necessary to implement various laws and amend the existing laws to protect the interests of the consumers. Representations of consumer groups should be linked to policy-making bodies established by the government. The government has taken some measures from time to time.

2.8: The general right of Consumers:

Generally, the consumers have some rights. Such as:

Right to safety:

The right to safety defines the protection of consumers against the marketing of goods and services that may be harmful to life and property. To ensure any person's safety when buying a product, they have the right to ask about its quality, including product guarantees and quality marks and certificates. It is a prominent consumer right whose goal is to bring quality and transparency to the market. The Consumer Rights Protection Authority is encouraging the purchase of quality-marked products.

Right to Information:

The right to information means that the consumer has the right to be informed about the quality, quantity, capacity, purity, quality, model, and price of the product or service to protect himself

against restricted and unfair trade practices. Consumers need to be informed about goods and services to make good decisions. Among the various consumer rights, it helps consumers act responsibly, thus protecting them from falling for any high-pressure sales strategies.

Right to Choose:

Right to choose means the consumer should have chances of choosing his required goods from a variety of goods and services at competitive and reasonable rates.⁴ No seller can ever force their consumer to buy a particular product or service. It is best executed among the core consumer rights in markets with higher competition available in different price ranges or where bargaining power is increased. This is referred to as the right to be assured and gives the consumers a choice to purchase any product or service according to their preferences and interests.

Right to Seek Redressal:

According to IOCU, The right to redress means the right to a fair settlement of just claims. This right has been generally accepted since the early 1970s. It involves the right to receive compensation for misrepresentation or shoddy goods or services, and where needed, free legal aid or an accepted form of redress for small claims should be available.⁵ Every consumer has the right to present their genuine grievances and grievances against illegal exploitation. We have the right to seek redress for our grievances and resolve our questions. Daily, many cases are being heard at the local level and disposed of accordingly.

Right to Consumer Education:

It means the right to acquire knowledge and skills to be a lifelong conscious consumer. The ignorance of consumers, especially rural consumers, is mainly responsible for their exploitation. They should know their rights and enforce them. Only then can absolute consumer protection be achieved successfully.

⁴ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 26 (Asia Law House 2021)

⁵ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 27 (Asia Law House 2021)

Right to be heard:

If a seller violates consumer rights, consumers can reach out to forums to express their concerns. Every consumer is given the right to be heard in consumer courts and other bodies to protect consumer rights. This particular right emphasizes the empowerment of the people so that they can freely express their views against any propaganda in the market.

Right to healthy environment:

The right to a healthy environment means the right to a physical environment that will improve the quality of life. This right includes protection against environmental issues over which the individual consumer has no control. It recognizes the need to protect and enhance the environment for present and future generations.

2.9: Responsibilities of a Consumer:

Responsibility to be aware:

It is the responsibility of consumers to be aware of their safety and quality before acquiring products and services. The primary responsibility of each customer is to obtain and retain the proof of purchase and other documents related to the purchase of sustainable products. For example, getting a cash memo for product purchases is vital because proof of purchase will help us prove that we are claiming product repairs or replacements if we have to complain about product defects.

Responsibility to think independently:

Consumers should be worried about what they want and should be able to make independent decisions. A consumer generally prefers to rely as little as possible on the seller for information and decisions. As consumers, we have a responsibility to protect ourselves from being fooled by responsible behavior. A well-known consumer can always take care of his interests more than anyone else.

Responsibility to speak up:

Don't be afraid to tell buyers about their problems and tell sellers precisely what they want. When we believe that a corporation, organization, or vendor has harmed us, one of our

fundamental legal rights is to speak up and defend ourselves. It is ethical to protect other customers from being wronged by the same company.

Responsibility to complain:

The consumer's responsibility is to make a sincere and fair complaint about their dissatisfaction with the product or service. Consumers are also urged to remember that they should not cause excessive demands when filing a complaint and requesting compensation for loss or damage. Consumers are often forced to exercise their right to seek redress in court. There have been cases where consumers have demanded large sums of money without apparent reason. This is considered a reckless act that should be avoided.

Responsibility to be an ethical consumer:

Consumers should be sincere and not engage in any deceptive practices. Some customers, especially during the warranty period, misuse the device in the misconception that it will be replaced during the warranty period. This isn't a honest state of affairs for them. They should always use the product correctly.

2.10: History of consumer rights protection:

Consumer protection has deep roots in the rich soil of the Indian subcontinent, dating to 3200 BC. At that time, the rulers felt that their issues were important. Many trade restrictions were established to protect the economic life of the people.

2.10.1: Ancient India:

Ancient India itself witnessed the dominance of the Vedas as a religious text from God. In ancient Indian society, the majority followed the Vedas strictly. These old codes contain provisions that seek to protect consumer interests to protect consumers. The Punishment was granted when committed for going against consumer-related conditions.

2.10.1.1: Smritis:

Many writers and commentators of the ancient period documented the living conditions of the people 'smritis'(traitions). Among them, the Manu Smriti (800 BC to 600 BC); the Yajnavalkya Smriti (300 BC to 100BC). The Narada Smriti (100 AD to 200 AD), the Bruhaspati Smriti (200

AD to 400 AD) and the Katyayana Smriti (300 AD to 600 AD) are considered as authoritative texts. Consumer protection was also a major concern in these Smritis.⁶

2.10.1.2: Manu Smriti:

Manu, the ancient legislator, wrote about the practice of ethical trade. He laid down a code of conduct for traders and provided specific punishments for those who committed crimes against buyers. Manu Smriti was about the social, political, and economic condition of the society in ancient times. It emphasizes ethical trade practices, punishing those who were unfair to consumers. Its prescribed code of conduct extends to adulteration, which is a mixture of one product with another, resulting in impurity. The king determined that all products had a market price or selling price. All weights and measurements were inspected every six months, and the results of these inspections were recorded. These efficient ways of protecting the consumer are noticeable in the early stages of the settlement.

2.10.1.3: Kautilya's Arthashastra:

Written subsequent to Manu Smriti, Kautilya's Arthashastra is considered to be a treatise and a prominent source, describing various theories of statecraft and the rights and duties of subjects in ancient society. Though its primary concern is with matters of practical administration, consumer protection occupies a prominent place in Arthashastra. It describes the role of the State in regulating trade and its duty to prevent crimes against consumers. Between 400 and 300 B.C.⁷ Kautilya's Arthashastra clearly defined laws regulating weights and measures. A penalty was proposed for traders who indulged in adulteration of goods namely grains, medicine, perfumes, salt and sugar. Arthashastra describes the role of the State in regulating trade and its duty to prevent crimes against consumers.⁸ Kautilya strongly condemned the black market and unfair trade practices. Punishment was prescribed for various types of deception, which were severe. These fines can be as serious as cutting off a fraudster's hand. The rights of traders were also protected

⁶ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 4 (Asia Law House 2021)

⁷ Dr. A. Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, 132 Journal of Texas Consumer Law, 132-136, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/JCCL_India.pdf

⁸ R.P. Kangle, The Kautiliya Arthashastra. Part III A Study 116 (2000)

by economics. The Arthashastra was created during the reign of Chandragupta. This period witnessed healthy trade practices where traders had to have a license to sell, which was allowed. The king pays the sellers a margin of profit when determining the selling price. The state was responsible for protecting consumers against unfair prices and fraudulent transactions. Such acts as smuggling and adulteration, especially of food, were punishable. This protection of consumers was ensured through an easy accessible justice system through various courts. It was the king's responsibility to administer justice.

2.10.1.4: Medieval Period:

The change in the period of India from ancient times to the medieval has led to a focus on Islam as a religion and the law of Islam. The Holy Quran, the main text of Muslims, also emphasizes the protection of consumers. There are verses in the Qur'an which indicate that the use of unjust weights and measures is unacceptable. During the Sultanate period, local prices were used to determine the price of goods.

During the rule of Alauddin Khilji, strict controls were established in the market place. Alauddin fixed the maximum price of a number of essential goods such as wheat, barley, rice, pulses, cloth, sugar, sugarcane, fruit, animal fat, besides slaves, horses and livestock. He ordered the merchants not to sell for more prices than the fixed price. He ordered the merchants to enrol their names in a register. Storing paddy, cereals was prohibited. Black marketing was also taken as a serious issue. For the violation of the orders, harsh punishments were imposed on the defaulters such as imposition of fines, imprisonment, expulsion from the capital, cutting flesh from the face etc. To implement and supervise the market reforms, the officers like 'Diwani-Riyasat', 'Sahana-i-mandi' were appointed. The merchants were severely punished for defective weights and measures. Sometimes the less weightage was compensated from the body of the merchant. The Sultan himself used to get reports from the market number of times on a day. To test practically, he used to personally send the slave boys to the market to get eatables.⁹

2.10.2: Modern Period: In the modern period, the British system replaced the age old traditional legal system of India. However, one of the outstanding achievements of British rule in India was

⁹ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 6 (Asia Law House 2021)

“the formation of a unified nationwide modern legal system. During the British period, the Indian legal system was totally revolutionized and the English legal system was introduced to administer justice.¹⁰ The previous customary law system established by the Indian kings was replaced by new modern law. The British introduced English common law in India and other legal provisions for the public and, consequently, for consumers. During British rule, some laws proved to be very effective in protecting the interests of consumers. The rules were now uniform throughout the country and were not arbitrary with the views of the various kings of ancient and medieval times.

2.10.3: After-Independence of India Period:

When India gained independence, it adopted the Anglo-Saxon system of administration of justice. Therefore, the previous law established by the British worked in independent India. In addition to the existing laws, the country was on the path to further legislation by enacting and adopting the Indian Constitution in 1950. Due to the democratic nature of the constitution, the main focus of the laws was the benefit of the common people, and also the consumers. The movement was started in India as a 'social force' to protect and promote the interests of consumers. But the Consumer Protection Act of 1986 gave it a legal authority with six declarations of consumer rights. Separate government departments of consumer affairs were set up and three levels of consumer courts were set up at the national, state and district levels.

2.10.4: After-Independence of Bangladesh Period:

Since Bangladesh gained independence in 1971, the role of government in protecting consumers has been minimal. Consumers Association of Bangladesh (CAB) has been the only non-profit organization working on consumer rights since 1978. After a long struggle, the government of Bangladesh enacted the Consumer Rights Protection Act in 2009.

2.10.5: Consumer Protection Movement in the United States of America:

Protection of the consumer in the USA dates back to the codes of antiquity. On the North American continent, provisions protecting consumers were incorporated into the earliest colonial

¹⁰ Dr. A. Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, Journal of Texas Consumer Law, 132-136, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/JCCL_India.pdf

codes. A century and a half later, the architects of the new nation gave the federal government the power to promote consumer protection by granting Congress the constitutional authority to regulate commerce among the several States and to Coin Money regulate the thereof, and fix the standard of weights and measures.¹¹ Periods of consumerism in the United States have ebbed and flowed during the last century, catalyzed by fundamental changes in the marketplace and technological advancements that have created uncertainty and fear among the general public.¹⁶ Broadly speaking, there have been the three Eras of consumerism as defined by Robert N. Mayer and Stephen Brobeck: in the early 1900s with the Progressives push for humanitarianism and efficiency, in the 1930s with the Great Depression and FDR's New Deal, and in the 1960s with Lyndon Johnson's Great Society programs.¹² The United States of America stands first in preparing the required legislation for the protection of consumers. It first started enacting the legislation for the protection of consumers, In 1890, America enacted the Sherman Act, which is the first anti-trust legislation to prohibit price fixation and to limit supply. This Act declares its object, every contract, combination in the form of trust or otherwise or conspiracy in restraint of trade or commerce to be illegal. During 1906, following journalistic exposes of the sale of unsanitary meats and the peddling of worthless patent medicines, Congress passed the Meat Inspection Act. That same year, it expanded the powers of the interstate commerce commission to include railroad rate setting. And in 1914, the Federal Government enacted two Acts, The Federal Trade Commission Act and the Clayton Act.¹³ The Second Era of consumerism began in the 1930s, during the Great Depression. The 1920s had been marked by rising income and relatively stable prices, allowing the consumer to experience rising real income and an increasingly improved lifestyle. The shock of the Depression heightened the previous problem of choice that consumers experienced during the Industrial Revolution. Individuals now found themselves unemployed, with a reduced income, while shoddy merchandise flooded the market.

¹¹ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 13 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹² Diya Berger, "A Tale of Two Movements: Consumer Protection in the U.S. from 1969 to 2010" 02 May 2013. CUREJ: College Undergraduate Research Electronic Journal, University of Pennsylvania, <https://repository.upenn.edu/curej/168>.

¹³ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 15 (Asia Law House 2021)

Worsened economic circumstances and increased uncertainty surrounding the quality of the product combined to create further support for quality testing among consumers.¹⁴

However, the modern consumer protection movement began in the 1960s with reference to a Consumer Bill of Rights by President Kennedy, the growth of the so-called “Great Society” program of the Johnson Administration, and the efforts of Ralph Nader and other consumer advocates to highlight the existence of unsafe products and the need for greater government regulation.¹⁵ As the modern consumer movement matured during the late 1970s, and into the 1980s and 1990s, it found itself both enjoying the successes of trying to improve product safety and consumer awareness but also battling strong political and business attempts to curb or eliminate the movement’s power. The consumer movement’s successes included such important safety measures as the standard use of seat belt and air bags in cars and trucks sold in the USA consumers could also learn about the nutritional level of the packaged foods they bought, once the federal government , under prodding of the consumer movement, forced foodmakers to include such labeling on products.¹⁶

The result is that American consumers are protected from unsafe products, fraud, deceptive advertising, and unfair business practices through a mixture of national, state, and local governmental laws and the existence of many private rights of actions. These public and private rights both protect consumers and, at a formal level, equip them with the knowledge they need to protect themselves. Although U.S. mechanisms for consumer protection often exist separately from each other, what the overall scheme lacks in centralization, it gains in depth and variety of protection. Its strength is the array of governmental actors, formal legal rights, and remedies protecting consumers. Its weakness lies in the unequal reality of who has access to the government and the courts.¹⁷

¹⁴ Diya Berger, "A Tale of Two Movements: Consumer Protection in the U.S. from 1969 to 2010" 02 May 2013. CUREJ: College Undergraduate Research Electronic Journal, University of Pennsylvania, <https://repository.upenn.edu/curej/168>.

¹⁵ H2O, https://h2o.law.harvard.edu/text_blocks/183, April 10, 2022

¹⁶ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 114 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁷ H2O, https://h2o.law.harvard.edu/text_blocks/183, April 10, 2022

2.10.6: Consumer Protection Movement in the United Kingdom:

In the UK the concept of consumer protection to the thinking person, throughout the eighteenth century at least, meant protection from excessive prices levied on primary commodities and protection from the short measures. Protection from common nuisances involving misuse of houses, streets and bridges is a separate area of activity. Bread, beer, Meat and fuel were singled out from earliest times as being commodities, which the crown, through the agency of the justice or other local courts, should regulate both as to quality and quantity. The Justice of peace or the Mayors of the boroughs were empowered to fix the weight and price of bread and bakers had to make their loaves with their size and quality. The price was to be fixed with reference to the current market prices of grain, meal or flour. Setting the 'assize of bread' remained the function of the Mayors or Justices, together with the enforcement of criminal penalties for contravention, until the abolition of the assize in 1836 on the adoption of Adam Smith's principle the competition was the best regulator of these matters. In 1776, in his 'Wealth of Nations'. Adam Smith stated, the interest of the producer ought to be attended to only so far it may be necessary for promoting that of the consumer. The capitalist economy is considered to be based on the concept of consumer sovereignty.¹⁸ The consumer society emerged in the late seventeenth century and intensified throughout the eighteenth century, mainly due to trade deals with their extensive colonies across 4 continents. Change was propelled by the growing middle-class who embraced new ideas about luxury consumption and the growing importance of fashion as an arbiter for purchasing rather than necessity. This revolution encompassed the growth in construction of vast country estates specifically designed to cater for comfort and the increased availability of luxury goods aimed at a growing market. This included sugar, tobacco, tea and coffee; these were increasingly grown on vast slave plantations in Caribbean colonies as demand steadily rose. In particular, sugar consumption in Britain during the course of the 18th century increased by a factor of 20.¹⁹ Moreover, the expansion of trade and markets also contributed to the burgeoning consumer revolution, by increasing the variety of goods that could be made available to affluent society. This pattern was particularly visible in London where the gentry and prosperous merchants took up residence and created a culture of luxury and consumption

¹⁸ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 17 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁹ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_revolution, April 11, 2022

that was slowly extended across the socio-economic divide. Marketplaces expanded as shopping centres, such as the New Exchange, opened in 1609 by Robert Cecil in the Strand. Shops started to become important as places for Londoners to meet and socialise and became popular destinations alongside the theatre. Restoration London also saw the growth of luxury buildings as advertisements for social position with speculative architects like Nicholas Barbon and Lionel Cranfield. There was growth in industries like glass making and silk manufacturing, and much pamphleteering of the time was devoted to justifying private vice for luxury goods for the greater public good. This then scandalous line of thought caused great controversy with the publication of Bernard Mandeville's influential work *The Fable of the Bees* in 1714, in which he argued that a country's prosperity ultimately lay in the self-interest of the consumer.²⁰ These trends were vastly accelerated in the 18th century, as rising prosperity and social mobility increased the number of people with disposable income for consumption. Important shifts included the marketing of goods for individuals as opposed to items for the household, and the new status of goods as status symbols, related to changes in fashion and desired for aesthetic appeal, as opposed to just their utility. The pottery inventor and entrepreneur, Josiah Wedgwood, noticed the way aristocratic fashions, themselves subject to periodic changes in direction, slowly filtered down through society. He pioneered the use of marketing techniques to influence and manipulate the direction of the prevailing tastes and preferences to cause his goods to be accepted among the aristocracy; it was only a matter of time before his goods were being rapidly bought up by the middle classes as well. His example was followed by other producers of a wide range of products and the spread and importance of consumption fashions became steadily more important.²¹

Though freedom was given to the producers in the Great Britain, consumer protection has been recognized. Consumer organizations may operate via protest, campaigning or lobbying. They may engage in single issue advocacy, which campaigned against keg beer and for cask ale or they may set themselves up as more general consumer watchdogs, such as the consumers Association of the UK. In the United Kingdom, the Enterprise Act 2002 allows consumer bodies that have been approved by the Secretary of State for trade and Industry to be designated as

²⁰ Peck, Linda, "Consuming Splendor: Society and Culture in Seventeenth-Century England", Cambridge Press, 2005

²¹ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_revolution, April 11,2022

super-complainans' to the office of fair Trading.²² Though the United Kingdom started legislation later than the US, it also enacted several necessary consumer law from 1950s. Such laws deal with credit repair, debt repair, product safety, service contracts, bill collector regulation, pricing, utility turnoffs, consolidation, personal loans that may lead to bankruptcy and much more.²³

2.10.7: Consumer Protection Movement in International Organisation:

The United Nations:

The United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection are a valuable set of principles that set out the main characteristics of effective consumer protection legislation, enforcement institutions and redress systems. Furthermore, the Guidelines assist interested Member States in formulating and enforcing domestic and regional laws, rules and regulations that are suitable to their economic, social and environmental circumstances; they also help promote international enforcement cooperation among Member States and encourage the sharing of experiences in consumer protection. The Guidelines were first adopted by the General Assembly in resolution 39/248 of 16 April 1985, later expanded by the Economic and Social Council in resolution 1999/7 of 26 July 1999, and revised and adopted by the General Assembly in resolution 70/186 of 22 December 2015.²⁴ First, the United Nations formulated guidelines to unite consumers' rights worldwide. The member states are interested in abiding by this guideline. After receiving this guideline, the member states express their interest in making laws like their own and then make laws to protect consumer rights.

The Food and Agriculture Organisation:

In 2004, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) adopted the Voluntary Guidelines to support the Progressive Realization of the Right to Food in the context of national food security (Right to Food Guidelines). Key elements of these guidelines are sustainability, food safety and consumer protection which support the actualisation of the right to adequate food in the context of national food security. These elements are also fundamental to

²² Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 18 (Asia Law House 2021)

²³ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 19 (Asia Law House 2021)

²⁴ The United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection, 1985

the discussion around the transformation of food systems. The role of consumer organizations is to increase knowledge and to raise awareness regarding issues such as food safety; adequate, healthy diets; access to nutritious and culturally appropriate foods; access to markets and reasonable pricing; transparent marketing and labelling practices; fair trade; and non-discriminatory labour and production practices.²⁵

The Food and Agriculture Organization carries out special programs for food control and gives instructions to follow consumer protection programs. The Food Science Control, Consumer Protection Group of the (Food and Agriculture Organization) has played an important role in promoting improved food processing to increase food production and increase quality, improve the preservation of food resources and meet the standards of improved food storage marketing, and distribution systems.

The International Labour Organisation:

The ILO promotes the interests of workers and their families in their capacity as consumers with a view to providing them with basic goods at reasonable prices in sufficient quantity and in satisfactory quality. Other programmes also deal with welfare facilities at the work place, strengthening of consumer cooperatives and providing education to workers.²⁶

The World Industrial Property Organisation: The role of industrial property in the protection of consumers, Among the various branches of industrial property, the laws on trademarks, service marks, trade names, geographical indications and on the protection against unfair competition are among the most effective and direct tools for the protection of consumers.²⁷ The World Industrial Property Organisation is trying to play a better role in protecting consumers, so that consumers around the world can be protected from unscrupulous traders.

The World Health Organisation:

²⁵ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Consumer Organizations and the Right to Adequate Food, FAO, April 12, 2022, <https://www.fao.org/3/cb3685en/cb3685en.pdf>

²⁶ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 21 (Asia Law House 2021)

²⁷ WIPO, The Role of Industrial Property in the Protection of Consumers, WIPO Publication, April 13, 2022, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/wipo_pub_648.pdf

The World Health Organisation's expert committee in 1977 determined a list of drugs that are essential for ensuring basic human health needs. This list was intended to assist the government in selecting and procuring drugs at reasonable prices. The WHO concept of an essential list considers the necessary changes needed to meet local conditions and needs. Necessary medicines are readily available to the consumers, and at reasonable prices taken from Consumers, they play a role in taking action. At the same time, WHO is working with different countries to prevent adulterated drugs in the market.

The United Nations International Development Agency:

The United Nations International Development Agency provides the necessary institutional tools for goods and product quality development, organizational tools for the organization, and implementation of national quality certification marketing schemes and ensures some relevant quality standards. Certification, quality control and ongoing technical cooperation projects, and planned activities in quality certification are all part of UNIDA's integrated program.

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development:

The United Nations Conference on trade and developments business practices has focused on issues that are relevant to consumer protection. Some of these issues deal with pricing, including resale price maintenance, refusal to sell, enterprise pricing policy on an individual basis, acquisitions, consolidation and takeover, agreement between quality enterprises, and supply of spare parts and replacement, specially for after-sales service. UNCTD also plays an important role in trademarks closely related to consumer protection.

The International Organisation of Consumer's Unions:

Consumers International (CI), formerly (1960–95) International Organisation of Consumers Unions (IOCU), international consortium of consumer-advocacy groups that promotes the rights and interests of consumers. CI was founded as the International Organisation of Consumers Unions (IOCU) in 1960 and by the early 21st century had grown to include more than 200 member organizations in more than 100 countries. It is headquartered in London and has offices

in Kuala Lumpur, Malay., and in Santiago.²⁸ Consumers International seeks to achieve changes in government policy and corporate behavior, whilst raising awareness of consumer rights and responsibilities. Its campaigns often fall under the themes of consumer justice and protection, food policy, digital consumer rights, and sustainability. Consumers International has campaigned on issues like junk food marketing and unethical drug promotion, corporate social responsibility, and unethical or unsustainable behavior by corporations and governments.²⁹

2.11: Conclusions:

Consumers play the most serious role in economic development. They only buy goods for themselves and their family. He does not accept the product for resale. A product reaches the consumers in different steps, starting from production. The last step of this cycle is the consumer. That's why consumer rights are so important so that consumers can purchase the right product. In general, consumers have several rights. Exercising those rights can protect the consumer from unscrupulous traders. Moreover, consumers have a lot of responsibilities as consumers. Consumers would be more secure if they performed these duties correctly. Similarly, it is impossible to enforce the law in many cases due to a lack of awareness. Unconscious consumers cannot perform these duties properly. Many laws have been enacted from ancient times to the present time to protect consumers. The United Nations has developed guidelines for implementing consumer rights worldwide so that member states can make their laws. Many local and foreign non-profit organizations are working for consumers' awareness and rights. As a result of the long-running movement of these organizations, effective laws have been enacted to protect consumer rights. We should all be more vocal in protecting consumer rights.

²⁸ Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Consumers-International>, April 13, 2022

²⁹ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumers_International, April 13,2022

Chapter: Three

Comparative Legal Framework

3.1: Introduction:

Consumer rights refer to a body of law governing what producers of goods must do to protect their customers from harm. These statutes arose from a succession of judicial challenges, and the outcomes of those cases have shaped them. Many states have enacted "consumer rights" laws. However, this is not yet the norm, and even these codifications may not include all of the elements widely considered "consumer rights". The right to safety is one of the most commonly recognized fundamental consumer rights. To put it another way, consumers should be able to trust that the things they buy are reasonably safe when used as advised. Defective car safety equipment, excessively flammable home products, and dangerous toys are a few examples of unreasonably safe products. They have influenced the body of law that established this right. This "right" against harmful products has been established via judgments holding the producers and marketers of these products accountable for accidents caused by their risky designs. This entails having competitive goods and services that provide price, quality, and service options. There are major statutory provisions in antitrust and unfair competition legislation in this area of consumer rights. The breakdowns of the Bell telecommunications monopoly, antitrust cases against firms like Microsoft, and so on are examples of legal activities that lead to this privilege. This implies that the government will pay attention to consumer complaints and protect their interests through well-crafted statutes and administrative rules. This is more politically manufactured right than evolved through litigation, as politicians who have ignored consumer preferences have found their support dwindling.

Finally, Due to overpopulation in India and Bangladesh, there are a large number of consumers here. Some dishonest businesses deprive consumers of their rights through deception with so many consumers. Moreover, law enforcement takes a long time due to the incompetent and insufficient number of officials. The government needs to come forward to inform the consumers about the law and increase awareness. At the same time, non-profit organizations need to come forward for the welfare of consumers and inform them about the law through various social programs so that they can know about the law and be aware of their rights.

3.2: Consumer Rights Protection-related law in India:

India first enacted an act in 1986 to protect consumer rights, and amended the Act in 2019 to make it timely. There are various laws in India to protect the rights of consumers, but these laws are not appropriate. I discussed various laws regarding Indian consumers.

3.2.1: The Consumer Protection Act, 2019:

The Act has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of e-commerce, in the age of digitization, sales, teleshopping, and many other levels of marketing.

Who is a 'Consumer' under the 2019 Act?

According to section 2(7) of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 a consumer is a person who buys goods or services for consideration and uses such products and services for personal use and resale or commercial use. In the definition of consumer, it is explicitly stated that the terms 'buy any product' and 'hire or receive any service' include all online transactions conducted either electronically or through direct sales or teleshopping or multi-level marketing.

Explanation:

- a) The expression "commercial purpose" does not include use by a person of goods bought and used by him exclusively for the purpose of earning his livelihood, by means of self-employment.³⁰
- b) The expressions "buys any goods" and "hires or avails any services" includes offline or online transactions through electronic means or by teleshopping or direct selling or multi-level marketing.³¹

'Unfair Trade Practice' under the 2019 Act:

According to section 2(47) of the Consumer protection Act,2019,"Unfair trade practice "means a trade practice that promotes the sale, use, or supply of any product or provision of any service, Adopts any unfair practices or unjust or fraudulent practices, including falsely representing, not

³⁰ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019,§ 2(7), No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

³¹ Id. at s 2(7)

issuing proper cash memos or bills, misleading facts, etc. The definition of 'unfair trade practice' has been expanded to include practices such as:

- a) Manufacturing or offering counterfeit goods for sale or adopting fraudulent practices for providing services.
- b) Permitting the publication of any advertisement, whether in any newspaper or otherwise, including by way of electronic record, for the sale or supply at a bargain price of goods or services that are not intended to be offered for sale or supply at the bargain price, or for a period that is, and in quantities that are, reasonable, having regard to the nature of the market in which the business is carried on, the nature and size of business, and the nature of the advertisement³².
- c) Permitting the sale or supply of goods intended to be used, or are of a kind likely to be used by consumers, knowing or having reason to believe that the goods do not comply with the standards prescribed by the competent authority relating to performance, composition, contents, design, constructions, finishing or packaging as are necessary to prevent or reduce the risk of injury to the person using the goods.³³
- d) Not issuing proper cash memos or bills for services provided and good sales.
- e) Disclosure of a consumer's personal information to any other person is not under the provisions of laws.

Unfair Contract:

'Unfair contact' is defined under section 2 (46). It refers to any Contact between a consumer and a manufacturer, service provider, or trader whose terms significantly change consumer rights under the Act. These terms are namely such as:

- a) The consumer requires an excessive security deposit to facilitate the fulfillment of obligations under the contract.
- b) Imposing a penalty on the consumer for breach of contract is not proportion to the loss due to such breach.

³² Id. at s 2(47)

³³ Id. at s 2(47)

- c) Refusing to accept early repayment of debts on payment of applicable penalty³⁴.
- d) Allowing any party to terminate a contract without a reasonable cause or unilaterally.
- e) Imposing on the consumer any unreasonable charge, obligation or condition which puts such consumer to disadvantage³⁵.
- f) To authorize a party to assign the contract to the detriment of the consumer and without his consent.

Consumer's Rights under the Act:

As per section 2(9) of the consumer protection Act, 2019, consumers have six primary rights, which are listed as follows:

- the right to be protected against the marketing of goods, products or services which are hazardous to life and property;
- the right to be informed about the quality, quantity, potency, purity, standard and price of goods, products or services, as the case may be, so as to protect the consumer against unfair trade practices;
- the right to be assured, wherever possible, access to a variety of goods, products or services at competitive prices;
- the right to be heard and to be assured that consumer's interests will receive due consideration at appropriate fora;
- the right to seek redressal against unfair trade practice or restrictive trade practices or unscrupulous exploitation of consumers; and
- the right to consumer awareness.³⁶

Establishment of Central Consumer Protection Authority:

Under the Act, a Central Consumer Protection Authority was established to regulate matters

³⁴ Id. at s 2(46)

³⁵ Id. at 2(46)

³⁶ Id. at 2(9)

relating to consumer rights violations, misleading advertisements, unfair trade practices, and the exercise of consumer rights. The authority will consist of a chief commissioner and other designated members and the Central Government will appoint all members of the Central Consumer Protection Authority. The Central Government may, by notification, make rules to provide for the qualifications for appointment, method of recruitment, procedure for appointment, term of office, salaries and allowances, resignation, removal and other terms and conditions of the service of the Chief Commissioner and Commissioners of the Central Authority³⁷. The Central Authority shall be established in place of the national capital at Delhi. It will have regional and other offices anywhere else the central government of India can decide.

Powers and functions of Central Consumer Protection Authority:

The central consumer protection authority will carry out the following power and functions. Including-

- a) Inquiring for violations of consumer rights, investigating, and prosecuting at the appropriate forum.
- b) Passing orders to recall products or withdrawal of hazardous services, refund the price paid, and cessation of unfair trade practices.
- c) Instructing the concerned merchant, manufacturer, supporter, advertiser, or publisher to stop false or misleading advertising.
- d) Issue consumer safety notices against unsafe products and services.
- e) File complaints before the District Commission, the State Commission or the National Commission, as the case may be, under this Act. Intervene in any proceedings before the District Commission or the State Commission or the National Commission, as the case may be, in respect of any allegation of violation of consumer rights or unfair trade practices. Review the matters relating to, and the factors inhibiting enjoyment of, consumer rights, including safeguards provided for the protection of consumers under

³⁷ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019, § 11, No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

any other law for the time being in force and recommend appropriate remedial measures for their effective implementation³⁸.

- f) Promoting awareness of consumer rights and Imposing penalties who violate consumer rights.

Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission: The Act calls for the formation of Consumer Disputes Redressal Commissions at the national, state, and district levels to hear consumer complaints. The State Commissions shall provide the Central Government with information on vacancies, disposition, the status of cases, and other topics on a quarterly basis. Consumer Disputes Redressal Commissions shall hear complaints about: overcharging or misleading charging, unfair or restrictive commercial practices, the sale of dangerous products and services that may endanger life, and the sale of faulty goods or services.

Product Liability:

Section 84 of the Act³⁹ holds a product maker accountable if the product has a manufacturing fault, is defective in design, does not adhere to manufacturing requirements, does not conform to an implied guarantee, and does not provide appropriate instructions for proper product usage. A product liability service provider in action. Under this section, to be liable, the service rendered is deficient, defective, inadequate, or incomplete, retains any information responsible for loss due to work or negligence, without adequate caution and instruction, and without disclosing the warranty or contract terms. A product seller is accountable for a product's liability if it has a significant influence on the production, testing, design, labeling, or packaging of the product. A significant alteration or modification produced the damage. The product seller provided an explicit guarantee that differed from the manufacturer's warranty. The product vendor failed to maintain, assemble, or check the goods with reasonable care.

Alternate Dispute Resolution: If the Consumer Dispute Redressal Forum thinks that consumer disputes can be settled through mediation, it can send the parties to mediation with their consent.

³⁸ Id. at s 18(2)

³⁹ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019, § 84, No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

The State Government shall establish, by notification, a consumer mediation cell to be attached to each of the District Commissions and the State Commissions of that State⁴⁰. The Central Government shall establish, by notification, a consumer mediation cell to be attached to the National Commission and each of the regional Benches⁴¹. Every consumer mediation cell shall submit a quarterly report to the District Commission, State Commission or the National Commission to which it is attached, in the manner specified by regulations⁴².

Penalties for Misleading Advertisement:

Misleading advertisement is defined under Section 2(28) of the Act and includes any advertisement, which falsely describes such product or service, gives a false guarantee to, or is likely to mislead the consumers as to the nature, substance, quantity or quality of such product or service, conveys an express or implied representation which, if made by the manufacturer or seller or service provider thereof, would constitute an unfair trade practice or deliberately conceals important information⁴³. The CCPA may impose a penalty on a manufacturer or an endorser of up to Rs 10 lakh and imprisonment for up to two years for a false or misleading advertisement⁴⁴. In case of a subsequent offence, the fine may extend to Rs 50 lakh and imprisonment of up to five years⁴⁵.

E-Filing of Complaints:

The Act provides consumers to register complaints with the jurisdictional consumer forum closest to their place of residence or employment. Previously, the consumer had to make a complaint at the point of purchase or where the merchant had its registered office location. The Act also includes provisions that allow consumers to file complaints online and to hear and/or examine parties through video-conferencing. In addition, consumers will not be required to engage a lawyer to represent their causes.

⁴⁰ Id. at s 74(1)

⁴¹ Id. at s 74(2)

⁴² Id. at s 75(5)

⁴³ Id. at s 2(28)

⁴⁴ Id. at s 21(4)

⁴⁵ Id. at s 21(3)

3.2.2: The Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020:

The Central Government had notified the Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020, with effect from July 23, 2020, under the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 ("Act"), to prevent unfair trade practices in e-commerce. However, following the publication of these guidelines, the government has received countless complaints from dissatisfied consumers, traders, and trade groups about pervasive cheating and unfair trading practices in the e-commerce ecosystem. These Rules mainly address the duties and liabilities of e-commerce entities that market and sell products and services to consumers via an online platform. The rules would apply to all electronic merchants (e-tailers) based in India or overseas who sell products and services to Indian consumers. The new rules provide the central government the authority to take action against unfair trade practices in e-commerce and direct selling. They want e-tailers to make returns simple, answer consumer complaints, and avoid discriminating against businesses on their platforms.

Scope and Applicability. – (1) Save as otherwise expressly provided by the Central Government by notification, these rules shall apply to:

- (a) all goods and services bought or sold over digital or electronic network including digital products;
- (b) all models of e-commerce, including marketplace and inventory models of e-commerce;
- (c) all e-commerce retail, including multi-channel single brand retailers and single brand retailers in single or multiple formats; and
- (d) all forms of unfair trade practices across all models of e-commerce:

Provided that these rules shall not apply to any activity of a natural person carried out in a personal capacity not being part of any professional or commercial activity undertaken on a regular or systematic basis.⁴⁶

⁴⁶ The Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020, 2, Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food and Public Distribution, Indian, 2020

3.2.3: Consumer Protection through the Constitution of India:

The rights of the consumer flow from the rights enshrined in Articles 14 and 19 and 21 of the Constitution of India. Equality before the law under Article 14 is not only a Constitutional right but it is an essential ingredient for making a state into just and effective welfare state. The right to be informed about the quantity, quality, potency, standard, purity and price of product are crucial to the exercise of other consumer rights. In India the “right to know” and the “right to receive and impart information” have been recognized as a part of the right to “freedom of speech and expression” guaranteed under Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution⁴⁷. Under Article 21 which guarantees right to life and personal liberty denial of an essential service by the state might amount to violation of this right⁴⁸. The Constitution of India in Articles 38, 39, 42, 43, 46 and 47 provides that the state shall strive to secure a social order for the promotion of welfare of the people; it shall direct its policies in such a way that operation of economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth and means of production to the common detriment, it shall make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief; it should endeavor to build an economic organization or to make suitable legislation to ensure a decent standard of life to all the workers who constitute the bulk of the consumers; it should promote educational and economic interests of schedule castes, scheduled tribes and other weaker sections and it shall also raise the level of nutrition and standard of living and to improve public health⁴⁹. Article 46 of the Indian constitution states that the state should seek to defend the economic interests of the weaker sections of its people, as well as to protect them from social injustice and all sorts of exploitation, which includes all types of market harassment and fraud. This includes the right to untainted substances that are harmful to public health and safety.

3.2.4: Trade Marks Acts, 1999:

The trademark Act has been trending recently to promote competition in the global market by conferring exclusive rights on the proprietors conveniently ignoring the rights of the consumers.

⁴⁷ Dr. Manoj Kumar Padhy, Consumer Protection Jurisprudence: A Constitutional Perspective, Rostrum's Law review(13 May, 2022 1.26 Pm), <https://journal.rostrumlegal.com/consumer-protection-jurisprudence-a-constitutional-perspective/>

⁴⁸ The Constitution of India, Article 21, 1950

⁴⁹ Sheetal Sahoo & Aman Chatterjee, Consumer Protection - Problems and Prospects (13 May 2022 1.43 Pm, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1452526

The essence of trademark law is the protection of consumers from deceit and confusion. Any deviation from this intended purpose is a manifest abuse of law. Concurrent use by two or more persons of the trademark for the same goods is quite contrary to the basic of trademark law, because the trademark is intended to denote that the goods come from one source only. There must be no compromise whatsoever from the fundamental principle of trademark law that no trademark can be registered if it is of such nature as to deceive the public or create confusion in the consumers' mind⁵⁰. Trademark rights in India are statutorily protected by the Trademark Act, 1999, as well as by the common law remedy of passing off. The Controller General of Patents, Designs, and Trademarks is in charge of enforcing such protection under the Act. The Trademark Act of 1999 addresses trademark protection, registration, and the prevention of fraudulent usage. It also addresses the rights of the trademark holder, fines for infringement, remedies for harm, and procedures of trademark transfers.

3.2.5: Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006:

An Act to consolidate the laws relating to food and to establish the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India for laying down science based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage distribution, sale and import, to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food for human consumption and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto⁵¹. Food safety is critical for both consumers and food businesses. Consumers must have trust that the food they purchase and consume will be what they anticipate, that it will not hurt them, and that they will be safeguarded against adulteration/fraud. The value of this confidence for businesses cannot be overstated. Although food safety regulation impacts everyone in the country, it is especially important for anybody involved in the production, processing, storage, transport, and sale of food, regardless of size. The Act applies to all operations in the food distribution chain, from primary production to distribution to retail and catering. The Act is modern and comprehensive, with the goal of improving consumer safety through Food Safety Management Systems and establishing standards based on science and transparency, as well as meeting the dynamic needs of Indian food commerce and industry and international trade.

⁵⁰ Clap, <https://clap.nls.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/CONSUMER-PROTECTION-VIS-A.pdf>, 13 May, 2022

⁵¹ The Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006, No 34, Acts of parliament, 2006 (India)

3.2.6: The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016:

An Act to provide for the establishment of a national standards body for the harmonious development of the activities of standardisation, conformity assessment and quality assurance of goods, articles, processes, systems and services and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto⁵². The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) is an Indian National Standard Body. BIS is regulated by India's Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food, and Public Distribution. The BIS has provided various benefits to the national economy through standardization, testing, and certification, such as providing quality and reliable goods that are safe for internal and external consumption, minimizing health hazards to consumers, promoting export and import substitutes, and so on.

Offences, Punishment and Enforcement activity:

The Act empowers BIS to pass orders granting, suspending or rejecting a license. Any violation of the provisions of the Act and the non-compliance with the standards set by BIS is punishable with either imprisonment for a period of one year or with a fine extending up to INR 50,000. BIS also carries out enforcement activity to curb the use of Standard Mark or its imitation by unscrupulous traders and manufacturers not holding a valid BIS license⁵³. The goal of these enforcement operations is to safeguard consumers from being deceived regarding the quality of items bearing the BIS Standard Mark. Enforcement raids, which include search and seizure operations, are conducted against dealers and producers based on intelligence gathered regarding misuse of the Standard Mark, and prosecution cases are brought in court when necessary.

3.2.7: The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940(Amendment 2008):

Drugs are medicines for human and animal internal and exterior usage used for the treatment, diagnosis, and prevention of any illness or ailment. It is a chemical used in illness diagnosis, cure, mitigation, therapy, or prevention. Cosmetics are substances applied to the body to improve

⁵² The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016, No. 11, Acts of Parliament, 2016 (India)

⁵³ Vikrant Rana, Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS)– Overview And Importance, mondaq(12 May,2022, 4.10 Pm, <https://www.mondaq.com/india/product-liability-safety/888040/bureau-of-indian-standards-bis-overview-and-importance>

its look or scent. Many cosmetics are intended for use on the face, body, and hair. These are often combinations of chemical substances generated from natural and artificial sources.

Adulteration of Drugs and Cosmetics:

Adulterated drugs:

- (a) if it consists in whole or in part, of any filthy, putrid or decomposed substance; or
- (b) if it has been prepared, packed or stored under insanitary conditions whereby it may have been contaminated with filth or whereby it may have been rendered injurious to health; or
- (c) if its container is composed, in whole or in part, of any poisonous or deleterious substance which may render the contents injurious to health; or
- (d) if it bears or contains, for the purposes of colouring only, a colour other than one which is prescribed; or
- (e) if it contains any harmful or toxic substance which may render it injurious to health; or
- (f) if any substance has been mixed therewith so as to reduce its quality or strength⁵⁴.

Adulterated cosmetics:

- (a) if it consists in whole or in part, of any filthy, putrid or decomposed substance; or
- (b) if it has been prepared, packed or stored under insanitary conditions whereby it may have been contaminated with filth or whereby it may have been rendered injurious to health; or
- (c) if its container is composed, in whole or in part, of any poisonous or deleterious substance which may render the contents injurious to health; or
- (d) if it bears or contains, for purposes of colouring only, a colour other than one which is prescribed; or
- (e) if it contains any harmful or toxic substance which may render it injurious to health; or
- (f) if any substance has been mixed therewith so as to reduce its quality or strength.⁵⁵

⁵⁴ The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, § 17A. No 26, Acts of parliament, Amendment 2008 (India)

⁵⁵ Id. at s 17E

Penalty for importing adulterated Drugs and Cosmetics: If any person by himself or on behalf of any other person imports any drug which is deemed to be adulterated or spurious or any cosmetic which is deemed to be adulterated shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and a fine which may extend to five thousand rupees⁵⁶.

Penalty for Manufacturing Drugs and cosmetics:

Any drug which is deemed to be adulterated the defaulter shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which shall not be less than three years but which may extend to five years and with fine which shall not be less than one lakh rupees or three times the value of the drugs confiscated, whichever is more. The Court may, for any adequate and special reasons to be recorded in the judgment, impose a sentence of imprisonment for a term of less than three years and of fine of less than one lakh Any cosmetic deemed to be spurious or adulterated the defaulter shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and with fine which shall not be less than fifty thousand rupees or three times to value of the cosmetics confiscated, whichever is more⁵⁷.

3.2.8: The Sale of Goods Act, 1930 (India):

The spirit of the concept of consumer protection is contained in several provisions in the Sale of Goods Act, which include the contract of sale, conditions and warranties in the sale, transfer of property between seller and buyer, duties of seller and buyer, right of unpaid sellers against the goods, and suits for breach of contract. This Act was not only consistent across British India, but it was also, outside of the high court's original jurisdiction, very ambiguous in its application. Section 14 to 17 of the Act have been designed to protect the interests of the buyers in terms of granting them the remedy of avoiding the transaction, besides the claim for damages⁵⁸.

3.2.9: The Agricultural Produce Act, 1937:

Agricultural Produce (Grading and Marking) Act, 1937 was enacted to provide for

a) grading and standardisation of agricultural commodities

⁵⁶ Clap, <https://clap.nls.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/ConsumerGuide/7DRUGSANDCOSMETICS.pdf>, 12 May, 2022

⁵⁷ Clap, <https://clap.nls.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/ConsumerGuide/7DRUGSANDCOSMETICS.pdf>, 12 May, 2022

⁵⁸ Egyankosh, <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/13502/1/Unit-17.pdf>, 11 may, 2022

- b) regulation of marks and marking practices,
- c) market research and surveys, and
- d) training of personnel in agricultural marking⁵⁹.

The Act establishes grading criteria for agricultural and livestock goods. The Act specifies the parameters that regulate the application of standards and the method for grading, marking, and packing agricultural goods. AGMARK, an abbreviation for Agricultural Marketing, is the quality mark established under the Act. The Central AGMARK Laboratory in Nagpur and sixteen regional AGMARK Laboratories in Calcutta, Bombay, Madras, and Kanpur offer laboratory facilities for setting grade standards for new goods and current grade standards as needed. Cochin, Bangalore, Patna, Rajkot, Guntur, and more cities are included. Different grading units and centers in different states grade agricultural produce at the farmer's level and 'kapas' at the producer's level.

3.3.10: The Indian Penal Code, 1860:

The Indian Penal Code, 1860 provides a catena of provisions dealing with offences against consumers. It has provisions for offences related to the use of false weights and measures⁶⁰, the sale of adulterated food or drinks, the sale of noxious food or drink, and the sale of adulterated drugs⁶¹.

3.3: Consumer Rights Protection-related law in Bangladesh:

Bangladesh first enacted an act in 2009 to protect consumer rights. There are various laws in Bangladesh to protect the rights of consumers, but these laws are not appropriate. I discussed various laws regarding Bangladesh consumers.

3.3.1: The Consumer Rights Protection Act (CRPA), 2009:

The consumer rights protection Act, 2009 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of adulteration and fake goods. According to this Act the term

⁵⁹ Egyankosh, <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/13502/1/Unit-17.pdf>, 11 may, 2022

⁶⁰ The Penal code Act, 1860, §264-267 ,No 46, India ,1860

⁶¹ Id. at s 272-276

“complainant” means any consumer, one or more consumers having same interest, any consumer association registered under any Act or the National Consumers’ Right Protection Council or any officer authorized to file any complaint on its behalf; the Government, or any Government officer authorized by the Government in this behalf; the concerned wholesaler and retailer⁶². The Act clarifies the term “Fake”. Here “Fake” means production or manufacturing of alike/similar things without authorization imitating the goods authorized for advertising whether the properties, ingredients, elements or quality of the goods authorized exist or not in such fake goods⁶³. The Act explains “anti-consumer right practice. It means to sell or offer to sell any goods, medicine or service at a higher price than the fixed price under any Act or rules; to sell or offer to sell adulterated goods or medicine knowingly; to sell or offer to sell any goods containing any ingredient which is extremely injurious to human health and the mixing of which with any food item is prohibited under any Act or rules; to deceive consumers by untrue or false advertisement for the purpose of selling any goods or service; not to sell or deliver properly any goods or services promised to sell or deliver in consideration of money; to sell or deliver less quantity of goods than the weight offered to the consumers while delivering or selling any goods; to show more than the actual weight by the weight stone or any other weight measuring instrument used for measuring weight in selling or delivering goods in a commercial enterprise; to sell or deliver less quantity of goods than the promised amount while delivering or selling any goods; to show more than the actual length by the length measuring gauge or anything else used for measuring length in selling or delivering goods in a commercial enterprise; to make or manufacture any fake goods or medicine; to sell or offer to sell goods or medicine the date of which has expired; or to do an act which may endanger life or security of the consumer and which is prohibited by any Act or rules⁶⁴.

Consumer:

Consumer means any person, who, without resale or commercial purpose buys any goods for a consideration which has been paid or promised to be paid, buys any goods for a consideration which has been partly paid and partly promised; or buys any goods for a consideration under any

⁶² The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 2(3) , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

⁶³ Id. at s 2(9)

⁶⁴ Id. at s 2(20)

system of deferred payment or installment basis; Who uses any goods bought under clause (a) with the consent of the buyer; Who buys any goods and uses it commercially for the purpose of earning his livelihood by means of self-employment; Who hires or in any other means avails of any service for a consideration which has been paid or promised to be paid; or hires or in any other means avails of any service for a consideration which has been partly paid and partly promised; or hires or in any other means avails of any service for a consideration under any system of deferred payment or installment basis; or who enjoys any service under clause (d), with the consent of the person who hires or avails it⁶⁵.

Establishment of Council:

Under the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009, there are Councils at two levels:

1. National level: For carrying out the purposes of this Act, there shall be a Council to be called the National Consumers' Right Protection Council. The Minister in charge of the Ministry of Commerce, who shall also be its Chairman.⁶⁶ The retired the Secretary of the Ministry of Commerce, Director General of the National Security Intelligence Department, Director General of the Bangladesh Standard and Testing Institution or not below the rank of the Joint Secretary will be the Secretary of the National Level Council. The meetings of the Council shall be held at such time and place as may be determined by the Chairman⁶⁷. The Council formulated policy on the protection of the rights of the consumers for this Act and gave directions to the Director-General and the District Committee to implement the policy; to consider and give an opinion on any matter referred by the Government regarding the protection of the rights of the consumers; to advise and cooperate with the Government in making necessary laws and administrative directions to protect and promote the rights of the consumers; to take steps required to create public awareness regarding the usefulness of protecting the rights of the consumers and the harmful impact of anti-consumer rights practices⁶⁸.

⁶⁵ Id. at s 2(19)

⁶⁶ Id. at s 5

⁶⁷ Id. at s 7

⁶⁸ Id. at s 8

2. District level: For carrying out the purposes of this Act, in every district, there shall be a District Committee called the District Consumers' Right Protection Committee⁶⁹. Duties of the District Committees to arrange necessary promotional activities, meetings, seminars and workshops for creating public awareness regarding the protection of the rights of the consumers to supervise and monitor the functions of the organizations, including the wholesale and retail business organizations, which manufacture and sell various goods for consumers⁷⁰.

Establishment of Directorate on Consumer Rights:

A Directorate of Consumer Rights is formed in Dhaka under the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009. In reality, this Directorate bears the primary duty for putting the Act into effect. The Directorate is led by a Director General (DG), who will be assisted by as many staff members as are required. The Director-General takes all necessary actions as he deems expedient and necessary for the protection of the rights of the consumers, prevention of anti-consumer right practice, and disposal of the complaint against violation of the rights of the consumers. If any officer, while conducting any inquiry or investigation under this Act, has reason to believe that there are goods contrary to this Act in any open place or any vehicle, he may, recording reasons thereof in writing, seize such goods after search and arrest the accused related to such goods⁷¹. If it appears that any goods of anti-consumer right are being sold or manufactured or stored in any shop, commercial enterprise, factory, workshop or godown, the Director General or any officer of the Directorate empowered in this behalf may pass an order for temporary closure of such shop, commercial enterprise, factory, workshop or godown⁷². The Director General or any officer empowered by him may request assistance of any law enforcing agency or any other public or statutory authority for exercising powers or performing of functions under this Act, and upon such request such agency or authority shall render such assistance⁷³. Any goods are proved to be

⁶⁹ Id. at s 10

⁷⁰ Id. at s 11

⁷¹ Id. at s 25

⁷² Id. at s 27

⁷³ Id. at s 28

particularly harmful to human health, the Government, on recommendation of the Director General, may, by notification in the official Gazette, issue direction for stopping the production, import, marketing, sale, display for sale, distribution, transportation for commercial purpose or commercial use of those goods completely all over the country or in any specific area, or for regulating or conducting those activities on such terms and conditions as may be specified in the notification⁷⁴. If in any inquiry, investigation or judicial proceeding, any goods prima facie appears to be adulterated and unfit for human consumption or injurious to human health and such allegation is admitted or not denied by the contesting party, such goods may, after seizure, directly be used, transferred, destroyed or disposed of in the prescribed manner⁷⁵.

Filing of Complaint:

No person can submit a complaint immediately at the Magistrate's court under this Act. Within 30 days after the alleged cause of action, a person may make a complaint with the Director General of the National Consumer Rights Protection Directorate or any other person authorized by him. The charge must then be filed in Magistrate court with the Director General's consent within 90 days after receiving the complaint.

Punishment for violating this Act:

Punishment for not using cover of goods⁷⁶, not showing price⁷⁷, not preserving and displaying price-list of services⁷⁸, selling goods, medicine or service at higher price than fixed one⁷⁹, not selling or delivering properly any goods or service promised⁸⁰, deceiving in weight⁸¹, deceiving in weight stone or weight measuring instrument⁸², deceiving in measurement⁸³, deceiving in measuring gauge or anything used for measuring length⁸⁴ and selling any date expired goods or

⁷⁴ Id. at s 29

⁷⁵ Id. at s 36

⁷⁶ Id. at s 37

⁷⁷ Id. at s 38

⁷⁸ Id. at s 39

⁷⁹ Id. at s 40

⁸⁰ Id. at s 45

⁸¹ Id. at s 46

⁸² Id. at s 47

⁸³ Id. at s 48

⁸⁴ Id. at s 59

medicine⁸⁵, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 1 (one) year, or with fine not exceeding Taka 50 (fifty) thousands, or with both. Punishment for manufacturing or processing goods in illegal process⁸⁶ and deceiving buyers by false advertisement⁸⁷ he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 2 (two) years, or with fine or with both. Punishment for making or manufacturing fake goods⁸⁸, selling adulterated goods or medicine⁸⁹, mixing prohibited materials in foodstuff⁹⁰, doing any act detrimental to life or security of service receiver⁹¹, damaging money, health or life etc. of service receiver by negligence⁹² and filing false or vexatious cases⁹³ he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 3 (three) years, or with fine or with both.

3.3.2: Consumer Protection through The Constitution of Bangladesh:

The Constitution of Bangladesh is almost dormant about consumer rights. However, it Recognizes certain rights related to consumer protection under its 'fundamental principles of state policy'⁹⁴.The Constitution of Bangladesh said about some basic rights. Article 15 of the Constitution said about some basic necessities like food, clothing, shelter, education and medical care etc⁹⁵.

3.3.3: Digital Commerce Operational Guideline 2021:

On 4 July, 2021 the Ministry of Commerce issued the Digital Commerce Operation Guidelines, 2021 pursuant to the National Digital Commerce Policy, 2018 (as amended in 2020) with the aim of ensuring transparency and accountability in the digital commerce sector, creating employment opportunities, ensuring the rights of the consumers and increasing the reliance on digital commerce by bringing about a regulatory framework, and creating a competitive market that

⁸⁵ Id. at s 51

⁸⁶ Id. at s 43

⁸⁷ Id. at s 44

⁸⁸ Id. at s 50

⁸⁹ Id. at s 41

⁹⁰ Id. at s 42

⁹¹ Id. at s 52

⁹² Id. at s 53

⁹³ Id. at s 54

⁹⁴ The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, § 18-25, Bangladesh, 1972

⁹⁵ The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, § 15, Bangladesh, 1972

provides opportunities for entrepreneurs⁹⁶. The guidelines reaffirm certain restrictions that no addictive or prohibited substances may be sold on digital commerce platforms; No provision can be made for online gambling or online betting, and no digital commerce platform can sell drugs or healthcare products without a proper license from the Director-General of Drug Administration. The guidelines also address some of the critical concerns regarding digital transactions. According to the guidelines, no digital wallet, gift card, cash voucher, or other payment option can be applied without the permission of Bangladesh Bank or in violation of the guidelines of Bangladesh Bank. The delivery timeline is also described as per guidelines goods delivered within the same city should be delivered within five days of payment and within ten days if delivered to another city. For regular use or perishable products, delivery will be prompt, and the buyer must be aware. An important addition to the guidelines is the Complaints and Remedies section. Marketplaces need to include the required phone numbers, emails or other means of communication through which customers can lodge complaints. Such complaints must be recorded and a solution provided to the consumer within 72 hours. Digital commerce platforms are also instructed to ensure proper rating and review systems so that buyers can view them and make a conscious choice and cannot be removed by such review platforms.

3.3.4: Sale of Goods Act 1930 (Bangladesh):

The sales of goods act are very old, but it is enforced and implemented in Bangladesh to protect consumers. According to this code, A contract of sale is made by an offer to buy or sell goods for a price and the acceptance of such offer. The contract may provide for the immediate delivery of the goods or immediate payment of the price or both, or for the delivery or payment by instalments, or that the delivery or payment or both shall be postponed. Subject to the provisions of any law for the time being in force, a contract of sale may be made in writing or by word of mouth, or partly in writing and partly by word of mouth or may be implied from the conduct of the parties⁹⁷. This also explains the terms and conditions of the warranty, a condition in a contract of sale with reference to goods which are the subject thereof, which is essential to the main

⁹⁶ Law desk, An overview of the Digital Commerce Operation Guidelines 2021, The daily star, 10 may, 2022, 8.14 pm, <https://www.thedailystar.net/law-our-rights/news/overview-the-digital-commerce-operation-guidelines-2021-2128871>

⁹⁷ Sales of goods, 1930, § 5, No III, Bangladesh, 1930

purpose of the contract, the breach of which gives rise to right to treat the contract as repudiated⁹⁸. Section 17 says about details of sale by sample. Section 37 describes the consequences of delivery of wrong quantity. The buyer's right to wrong quantity is to accept or reject the goods. The Act gives a right to the buyers, It says, where goods are delivered to the buyer which he has not previously examined, he is not deemed to have accepted them unless and until he has had a reasonable opportunity of examining them for the purpose of ascertaining whether they are in conformity with the contract. The Act also says, unless otherwise agreed, when the seller tenders delivery of goods to the buyer, he is bound, on request, to afford the buyer a reasonable opportunity of examining the goods for the purpose of ascertaining whether they are in conformity with the contract⁹⁹.

3.3.5: The Bangladesh Penal Code 1860:

Weight and measures are discussed in Section 264-267 of the India and Bangladesh Penal Code, 1860. That section provides for fraudulent use of false instruments, fraudulent use of false weights and Measurements, false weights, or anyone possessing measurements respectively, 'shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine, or with both¹⁰⁰. Section 172 says that: Whoever adulterates any article of food or drink, so as to make such article noxious as food or drink, intending to sell such article as food or drink, or knowing it to be likely that the same will be sold as food or drink, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to six months, or with fine which may extend to one thousand taka, or with both¹⁰¹. Selling noxious food or drink, adulterating drugs, selling drugs, and selling Drugs as different drugs or preparation are also punishable offenses. Using a false trademark is also a punishable offense under this code.

⁹⁸ Sales of goods,1930,§ 13, No III, Bangladesh, 1930

⁹⁹ Nazia Wahab, Online Shopping and Consumer Rights Protection within Bangladesh: A Review of Current Laws and Regulations, researchgate, (10 may, 2022, 12.41 pm, https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nazia-Wahab/publication/344247931_Online_Shopping_and_Consumer_Rights_Protection_within_Bangladesh_A_Review_of_Current_Laws_and_Regulations/links/5f6065ba299bf1d43c04f288/Online-Shopping-and-Consumer-Rights-Protection-within-Bangladesh-A-Review-of-Current-Laws-and-Regulations.pdf?origin=publication_detail)

¹⁰⁰ The Penal code Act, 1860, §264 , No 45, Regulation V of 1799, Bangladesh,1860

¹⁰¹ The Penal code Act, 1860, §272 , No 45, Regulation V of 1799, Bangladesh,1860

3.3.6: The Dangerous Drug Act 1940:

This Act is enforced in Bangladesh mainly to protect consumers. In which the quality of standard, sale, and production of drugs is under the control of the government. The government will form a Drugs Technical Advisory Board through the official gazette and appoint board members, including a board chairman. The advisory board will advise the government on various medicines. On the advice of this advisory board, the government will set up drug research to test the drugs of different companies. Under this Act, no banned drugs can be imported. No shopkeeper may sell unlicensed drugs on public roads, highways, and sidewalks.

3.3.7: The Special Powers Act 1974:

The Special Powers Act 1974 is a special law. Although the purpose of this Act is only to enforce the goods standing and order in the society, still, some of its provisions may be utilized for providing protection of life to consumers. In this respect, the term „protection of life“ is used to mean and include injury to health and death. The laws relating to protection of life may not be found in one umbrella legislation. It is dealt with by various laws including the laws relating to consumer goods. It has also been observed that the aspect of protection of life and the aspect of goods (supply of essential commodity) is dealt with by the same law. In some cases, it assumes the character of special law, e.g. the Special Powers Act 1974.¹⁰² The purpose of the Special Powers Act 1974 was to provide special measures to prevent certain superstitious activities, ensure speedy justice, and ensure effective punishment for these crimes. The Act carries a penalty of death or life imprisonment or 14 years rigorous imprisonment for any adulteration of food, drink, medicines, and cosmetics. This Act also provides trial cases by a special tribunal consisting of a Sessions Judge, an Additional Sessions Judge, or an Assistant Sessions Judge and the metropolitan magistrate for the metropolitan area may pass upon any person convicted by it any sentence authorized by law for the punishment of the offense of which such person is convicted¹⁰³.

3.3.8: Control of Essential Commodities Act, 1956: The Act states the powers to control the production, treatment, keeping, storage, movement, transport, supply, distribution, disposal,

¹⁰² Zahangir Alam Khan, Consumer Justice in Bangladesh: A Critical Study of Laws & Rules, 64 (17 January 2016)

¹⁰³ The Special Powers Act, 1974, §28, No 25, Acts of Parliament, 1974 (Bangladesh)

acquisition, use or consumption of, and trade and commerce in, certain commodities. According to this Act, the Government has the power to control production, supply, distribution, etc, of essential commodities¹⁰⁴. This Act has an important role in protecting the rights of consumers. It has been compelled to abide by guidelines and rules on various issues ranging from product production to consumer.

3.3.9: Trademark Act 2009:

This Act of 1940 was replaced by the Trademarks Act of 2009, which was enacted to amend and consolidate the law relating to trademarks and unfair competition, as well as to provide for the registration and better protection of trademarks, and to prevent the use of fraudulent marks, among other things. The trademark Act has been trending recently to promote competition in the global market by conferring exclusive rights on the proprietors conveniently ignoring the rights of the consumers. The essence of trademark law is the protection of consumers from deceit and confusion.

3.4: The result of the comparative legal framework study:

The India government first enacted an act in 1986 to protect consumer rights, and amended the Act in 2019 to make it timely, and Also, The Bangladesh government first enacted an act in 2009 to protect consumer rights. There are various laws in India and Bangladesh to protect the rights of consumers, but these laws are not appropriate. The Indian Consumer protection Act, 2019 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of e-commerce, in the age of digitization, sales, teleshopping, and many other levels of marketing. But The Bangladeshi consumer rights protection Act, 2009 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of adulteration and fake goods. The Indian consumer protection Act, 2019 provides six consumer rights; on the other hand, the Bangladeshi consumer protection Act, 2009 doesn't have specific rights for consumers. Under the Act 2019, a Central

¹⁰⁴ Nazia Wahab, Online Shopping and Consumer Rights Protection within Bangladesh: A Review of Current Laws and Regulations, researchgate, (09 may, 2022, 9.03 pm, https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nazia-Wahab/publication/344247931_Online_Shopping_and_Consumer_Rights_Protection_within_Bangladesh_A_Review_of_Current_Laws_and_Regulations/links/5f6065ba299bf1d43c04f288/Online-Shopping-and-Consumer-Rights-Protection-within-Bangladesh-A-Review-of-Current-Laws-and-Regulations.pdf?origin=publication_detail)

Consumer Protection Authority was established to regulate matters relating to consumer rights violations, misleading advertisements, unfair trade practices, and the exercise of consumer rights. The central Consumer protection authority inquiring for violations of consumer rights, investigating, and prosecuting at the appropriate forum, passing orders to recall products or withdrawal of hazardous services, refund the price paid, and cessation of unfair trade practices, and instructing the concerned merchant, manufacturer, supporter, advertiser, or publisher to stop false or misleading advertising. A Directorate of Consumer Rights is formed in Dhaka under the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009. In reality, this Directorate bears the primary duty for putting the Act into effect. The Directorate is led by a Director General (DG), who will be assisted by as many staff members as are required. The Director-General takes all necessary actions as he deems expedient and necessary for the protection of the rights of the consumers, prevention of anti-consumer right practice, and disposal of the complaint against violation of the rights of the consumers. The Act, 2019 calls for the formation of Consumer Disputes Redressal Commissions at the national, state, and district levels to hear consumer complaints. The State Commissions shall provide the Central Government with information on vacancies, disposition, the status of cases, and other topics on a quarterly basis. Under the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009, there are Councils at two levels, one is national level and another is district level. The Indian consumer protection Act, 2019 provides Alternative Dispute Resolution but The Bangladeshi consumer protection Act, 2009 does not provide alternative dispute resolution. The Act, 2019 provides consumers to register complaints with the jurisdictional consumer forum closest to their place of residence or employment. Previously, the consumer had to make a complaint at the point of purchase or where the merchant had its registered office location. The Act also includes provisions that allow consumers to file complaints online and to hear and/or examine parties through video-conferencing. In addition, consumers will not be required to engage a lawyer to represent their causes. Under the Act, 2009, No person can submit a complaint immediately at the Magistrate's court under this Act. Within 30 days after the alleged cause of action, a person may make a complaint with the Director General of the National Consumer Rights Protection Directorate or any other person authorized by him. The charge must then be filed in Magistrate court with the Director General's consent within 90 days after receiving the complaint. Penalties for Misleading Advertisement under the Act, 2019, up to Rs

10 lakh and imprisonment for up to two years for a false or misleading advertisement and under the Act, 2009 he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 2 (two) years, or with fine or with both. The Indian Central Government had notified the Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020, with effect from July 23, 2020, under the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 ("Act"), to prevent unfair trade practices in e-commerce. Also, The Bangladesh Ministry of Commerce issued the Digital Commerce Operation Guidelines 2021 to ensure transparency and accountability in the digital commerce sector, creating employment opportunities and providing the rights of the consumers. The rights of the consumer flow from the rights enshrined in Articles 14 and 19 and 21 of the Constitution of India. Equality before the law under Article 14 is not only a Constitutional right but it is an essential ingredient for making a state into just and effective welfare state. The right to be informed about the quantity, quality, potency, standard, purity and price of product are crucial to the exercise of other consumer rights. On the other hand, The Constitution of Bangladesh is almost dormant about consumer rights. However, it Recognizes certain rights related to consumer protection under its 'fundamental principles of state policy'. The Constitution of Bangladesh said about some basic rights. Article 15 of the Constitution said about some basic necessities like food, clothing, shelter, education and medical care etc. The trademark Act has been trending recently to promote competition in the global market by conferring exclusive rights on the proprietors conveniently ignoring the rights of the consumers. The essence of trademark law is the protection of consumers from deceit and confusion. The spirit of the concept of consumer protection is contained in several provisions in the India and Bangladesh Sale of Goods Act, 1930 which include the contract of sale, conditions and warranties in the sale, transfer of property between seller and buyer, duties of seller and buyer, right of unpaid sellers against the goods, and suits for breach of contract. Drugs are medicines for human and animal internal and exterior usage used for the treatment, diagnosis, and prevention of any illness or ailment. It is a chemical used in illness diagnosis, cure, mitigation, therapy, or prevention. Cosmetics are substances applied to the body to improve its look or scent. Many cosmetics are intended for use on the face, body, and hair. These are often combinations of chemical substances generated from natural and artificial sources. The India and Bangladesh Penal Code, 1860 provides a catena of provisions dealing with offences against consumers. It has

provisions for offences related to the use of false weights and measures¹⁰⁵, the sale of adulterated food or drinks, the sale of noxious food or drink, and the sale of adulterated drugs¹⁰⁶. Food safety is critical for both consumers and food businesses. Consumers must have trust that the food they purchase and consume will be what they anticipate, that it will not hurt them, and that they will be safeguarded against adulteration/fraud. The value of this confidence for businesses cannot be overstated. Although food safety regulation impacts everyone in the country, it is especially important for anybody involved in the production, processing, storage, transport, and sale of food, regardless of size. The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016, provides for the establishment of a national standards body for the harmonious development of the activities of standardisation, conformity assessment, and quality assurance of goods, articles, processes, systems, and services and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto. The Bangladesh Special Powers Act 1974 is a special law. Although the purpose of this Act is only to enforce the goods standing and order in the society, still, some of its provisions may be utilized for providing protection of life to consumers. In this respect, the term “protection of life” is used to mean and include injury to health and death. The laws relating to protection of life may not be found in one umbrella legislation. It is dealt with by various laws including the laws relating to consumer goods.

3.5: Conclusions:

The precondition for protecting consumer rights is to have laws on consumer rights. India and Bangladesh currently have specific laws to protect consumer rights. Along with this law, the two countries have different laws related to consumer rights. Those laws may not play an influential role, but they do play a role in protecting consumers in many cases. The Indian consumer protection Act, 2019 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of e-commerce in the age of digitization, sales, and teleshopping. The Act provides six rights of consumers, and also this Act protects from adulterated, misleading advertisements, unfair trade, and faulty goods. Under the Act, a Central Consumer Protection Authority and Consumer Disputes Redressal Commissions were established to regulate matters relating to

¹⁰⁵ The Penal code Act, 1860, §264-267 ,No 46, India and Bangladesh ,1860

¹⁰⁶ Id. at s 272-276

consumer rights violations, misleading advertisements, unfair trade practices, and the exercise of consumer rights. The Act also includes provisions that allow consumers to file complaints online and to hear and/or examine parties through video-conferencing. The consumer rights protection Act 2009 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights and directly cover the field of adulteration and fake goods. This Act also protects consumers from adulterated, false advertisements and goods, manufacturing defects, and unfair trade practices. Under the Act, The Consumer Protection Council and Directorate of Consumer Rights were established for consumer rights against unfair trade, adulterated, misleading advertisements, and faulty goods. The India and Bangladesh Constitution ensures the right to be informed about the quantity, quality, potency, standard, purity, and product price. The “right to know” and the “right to receive and impart information” have been recognized as a part of the right to “freedom of speech. The India and Bangladesh Sale of Goods Act,1930 includes the contract of sale, conditions and warranties in the sale, transfer of property between seller and buyer, duties of seller and buyer, right of unpaid sellers against the goods, and suits for breach of contract. The Indian and Bangladeshi Penal Code, 1860 provides a catena of provisions dealing with offences against consumers. It has provisions for offences related to the use of false weights and measures, the sale of adulterated food or drinks, the sale of noxious food or drink, and the sale of adulterated drugs. Bangladesh Consumer Rights Protection Act needs to be adapted in time. At the same time, the two countries need to be more stringent in enforcing laws to protect consumer rights. Institutions that have been established through the Consumer Rights Protection Act to protect consumers must work independently and be sincere towards consumers.

Chapter: Four

Consumer Awareness and Practical Approach to protect Consumer Rights

4.1: Introduction:

The Department of Consumer Protection and various non-governmental organizations play a significant role in raising consumer awareness. There are so many consumers in India and Bangladesh that these organizations can't increase this amount of consumer awareness. Most of the consumers live in villages, and most lack education. Due to a lack of education, consumers don't know about rights or do not want to know on their own. For this reason, if the consumer is deprived of his rights, he cannot take any legal action. Similarly, various departments have been formed under the Consumer Rights Protection Act to protect consumer rights so that consumers can be protected from unscrupulous traders. These organizations constantly work for consumers, receive consumer complaints, arrange hearings, and redressal grievances. At the same time, the market system monitors so that misleading advertisements, false goods, and adulterated products cannot be marketed. In addition, Non-profit distribute social programs, promotions, and leaflets to increase consumer awareness. At the same time, various government departments run various programs to increase consumer awareness.

4.2: Consumer Awareness:

People buy commodities and services at a set price to satisfy their endless wants. But what if the items and services purchased are discovered to be of poor quality, overpriced, measured insufficiently, etc. In such cases, buyers frequently feel duped by the vendors who have sold the goods and services rather than satisfied. Consumer awareness is essential in this case. Consumer awareness is simply the process of ensuring that the buyer or consumers are aware of information on products, services, and consumer rights. Consumer awareness is essential so that purchasers may make the correct selection at the appropriate time.

4.2.1: The object of Consumer Awareness:

a) Consumers' understanding of the quality of the goods they have purchased. For example, the consumer should be aware of whether the goods are safe for their health and whether it causes any environmental risks.

- b) Education on the various types of hazards and problems associated with product marketing. For example, one method of selling a product is by advertising in newspapers, on television, and so on. Consumers should be properly educated about the negative impacts of advertising. They must also confirm the advertisement's substance.
- c) The idea of 'Consumer Rights'. The consumer must understand that he or she has the right to obtain the appropriate goods. If the product is proven to be defective in some way, the consumer should be aware of his or her legal right to reimbursement.
- d) The consumer's understanding of his or her own duties. This suggests that consumers should avoid unneeded and wasteful purchasing.

4.2.2: Need for Consumer Awareness:

The importance of educating consumers about product quality and pricing cannot be ignored. The growth of technology, the appearance of smart devices in the market, and aggressive marketing methods in the era of globalization not only provide consumers with a wide range of options, but also do not protect them from the variety of difficulties connected with such quick changes. Today's market is swamped with a vast quantity and variety of goods and services. The number of producers and final sellers of commodities has likewise multiplied several times over. As a result, determining who is a genuine manufacturer or vendor has become extremely difficult. It is nearly impossible for consumers to interact with a producer or merchant in person. Furthermore, in the age of improved information technology, the physical distance between consumer and manufacturer has expanded because consumers may get their goods delivered to their door by booking orders over the phone or the internet. Similarly, determining whether many items are authentic has become quite tricky. People believe that if a product appears in an advertisement, it must be good or that the producer whose name is known through advertising must be offering the right thing. However, this is not always the case. Much information is purposefully withheld in specific adverts to mislead customers. In the case of packaged food and medications, an expiry date indicates that the product must be eaten before that date and not at all after that date. This information is critical since it concerns the consumer's health. Sometimes such information is not given, or the merchant purposefully does not provide it since the buyer

did not ask for it or notice the inscription printed on the products. It also happens frequently that a consumer purchases products and services without taking the bill, or that the merchant fails to give the bill. This is done to avoid paying taxes to the government on the product. Consumers should be educated about their consumer rights. He should be well-educated enough to defend himself from any wrongdoing on the trader's side. There is a need to give credible and comprehensive information that they can obtain without much effort or money.

4.2.3: Consumer Awareness in India and Bangladesh:

Consumer awareness campaign- Jago Grahak Jago is the most important and successful campaign which has shielded consumers against marketing malpractices and has successfully redressed consumer complaints. The campaign Jago Grahak Jago was started in 2005 by the Department of Consumer Affairs under the Ministry of Consumer and Public Distributions by the Government of India. The Slogan “ Jago Grahak Jago” means wake up consumers has now become very popular in almost every household. The Government of India used several different channels to create awareness among consumers. Following is the list of the channels used by the Government to meet the objectives of the “Jago Grahak Jago” awareness program. Media Advertisements, Video Campaign, Posters Printing, Audio Campaigns.¹⁰⁷ The Indian government acknowledged the importance of consumer welfare and has been working on this problem in several dimensions such as consumer protection through legislative measures, education and awareness programs, and so on. The government is responsible for ensuring consumer welfare. Despite multiple attempts, consumer protection and consumerism in India are still in their infancy. Given the context of economic disparity, level of education, and ignorance, educating consumers remains a massive undertaking. Everyone must work together to make this happen. The government, as well as several voluntary organizations and activists, have taken steps to increase consumer education and awareness in the country. Most of the people in Bangladesh do not know about the existence of their rights as consumers. There is not much consumer awareness activity in Bangladesh; however, from time to time the Department of Consumer Affairs conducts various awareness campaigns to make the consumers aware. That is very few awareness activities for the consumers. But many non-governmental organizations are

¹⁰⁷ vedantu, <https://www.vedantu.com/commerce/consumer-awareness> (21.05.2022, 9.37 Pm)

working in all districts of Bangladesh for consumer awareness. Such as: (The Bangladesh Food Safety Network, comprised of five founding NGOs, advocacy activities have been organized in every division of Bangladesh and have involved among others opinion makers, community and religious leaders, politicians, civil servants and journalists. The BFSN has played a critical role in the delivery of consumer education to many districts of the country, where they work. Millions of women and school children have been reached with messages about food safety in a variety of ways. Thousands of copies of food safety communication materials ranging from leaflets, booklet, cartoons, posters, calendars, flip chart, festoon, banners, fact sheets and newsletters have been distributed through the Directorate General of Health Services and the Directorate General of Family Planning. Three public service messages on household food safety are being broadcast on the national channel, Bangladesh Television¹⁰⁸).

4.3: Practical approach to protect consumer rights in India:

Many government departments and Non-profit organizations in India work to protect consumer rights. These organizations are constantly working on consumer rights.

4.3.1: Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA):

The Central Consumer Protection Authority was established under Section 10(1) of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019¹⁰⁹ to address issues affecting consumer rights, such as improper trade practices or the display of inappropriate or incorrect advertisements involving the public interest, and to promote consumer trust by enforcing consumer rights through practical guidelines. The Consumer Protection Act of 2019 updated the old Consumer Protection Act of 1986 and established the Central Consumer Protection Authority. The new statute has been amended to address other consumer issues, such as deceptive marketing and providing false information about the quality or quantity of products or services. The members of the Central Consumer Protection Authority will be appointed by the Central Government.

¹⁰⁸ fao, <https://www.fao.org/in-action/food-safety-bangladesh/activities/consumer-awareness/zh/>, (21 May,2022 11:37 Pm)

¹⁰⁹ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019,§ 10(1), No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

Aim and object of Central Consumer Protection Authority:

The objective of the Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) is to promote, protect and enforce the rights of consumers as a class. It will be empowered to conduct investigations into violation of consumer rights and institute complaints / prosecution, order recall of unsafe goods and services, order discontinuation of unfair trade practices and misleading advertisements, impose penalties on manufacturers/endorsers/publishers of misleading advertisements.¹¹⁰ Make actions when needed to protect consumers from harm caused by unfair commercial practices. To file a class action lawsuit, including product recall, refund, and return, etc.

4.3.2: National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission:

National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, is a quasi-judicial body formed under the Consumer Protection Act of 1986¹¹¹. The NCDRC can hear consumer complaints worth more than Rs. 1 crore under Section 21 of the Consumer Protection Act 1986¹¹². The NCDRC will listen to complaints worth more than Rs. 10 crores under the 2019 Act, which superseded the 1986 Act. The commission also has appellate and provisional authority over orders issued by state consumer dispute resolution commissions and district forums, if applicable. The Act also states that anybody who is aggrieved by an NCDRC ruling has 30 days to file an appeal with the country's (Indian) Supreme Court. Cases worth between Rs. 1 crore and Rs. 10 crores will be heard by state commissioners. The District Fora will investigate matters worth up to one crore rupees¹¹³. Another modification introduced in the 2019 Act is that the complainant can file the complaint in the location where they work or live rather than in the site where the other party resides or conducts business, lowering the burden on customers. The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission strives to provide the remedy to aggrieved consumers as promptly as practicable while bearing in mind the provisions of the Act that provide a timetable for case resolution. If a customer is dissatisfied with a District Forum's decision, he may appeal to the State Commission.

¹¹⁰ pib, <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1642422>, (22 May, 2022 10.47 AM)

¹¹¹ CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 1986, § 9, No. 68, Acts of Parliament, 1986 (India).

¹¹² Id at, s 21

¹¹³ Id at, s 21

Object of the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission:

The National Commission has also been given administrative supervision over all State Commissions by requiring periodic reports on the institution, disposition, and pendency of cases.

- a) adoption of a standardized approach for hearing cases
- b) previous delivery of papers produced by one party on the opposing parties
- c) rapid grant of document copies
- d) broadly supervising the operation of the State Commissions and District Forums to ensure that the Act's aims and purposes are effectively achieved, while not interfering with their quasi-judicial independence

4.3.3: Central Consumer Protection Council (CCPC):

Under section 3 of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 the Central Government shall establish the Central Consumer Protection Council which is known as the Central Council. It is an advisory body and the Central Council must consist of the following members;

- 1. The Minister-in-charge of the Department of Consumer Affairs in the Central Government will be appointed as the chairperson of the council, and
- 2. Any number of official or non-official members representing necessary interests under the Act.¹¹⁴

The Central Council may meet as and when necessary, however, they must hold at least one meeting every year. The purpose of the Central Council is to protect and promote the interests of the consumers under the Act.¹¹⁵

Object of the Central Consumer Protection Council:

The objects of the Central Council shall be to promote and protect the rights of the consumers such as:

¹¹⁴ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019, § 3, No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

¹¹⁵ Id. at s 4

- a) The right to be protected from the marketing of products and services that endanger life and property.
- b) the right to be informed about the quality, amount, potency, purity, standard, and price of products or services, as applicable, in order to protect consumers from unfair commercial practices.
- c) The right to have access to a wide range of goods and services at reasonable costs whenever possible.
- d) The right to be heard and to be guaranteed that consumer interests will be taken into account in suitable venues.
- e) The right to seek redress for unfair trade practices, restrictive trade practices, or consumer exploitation.

4.3.4: Consumer Rights Organisation:

The Consumer Rights Organisation is a pan-India consumer rights group that was founded in April 2010 to promote consumer awareness, education, and protection. The CRO is present in 24 states in India. Vision is A new India in which every consumer is fully aware of his rights and how to exercise them correctly. Mission is to organize, educate, and inform customers about their rights and to do all possible to prohibit unfair commercial practices and resolve consumer complaints.¹¹⁶ Food safety is another area where consumer groups have worked. Because scientific, nutritional, or medical data is typically more complicated than in other sectors, such as the electric safety of white goods, the demands for advocacy in this field are more difficult to reconcile with traditional techniques. Historically, consumer organizations' advocacy has influenced present obligatory labeling rules in industrialized nations. Consumer associations may be formed to establish and enforce consumer rights. However, practical work has been done merely by threatening corporations with negative press to keep them focused on the consumers' perspective. Consumer rights organizations may try to serve consumers' interests through relatively direct actions such as creating and disseminating market information, prohibiting specific acts or practices, or promoting competitive forces in markets that directly or indirectly

¹¹⁶ Consumer rights organization, <https://www.thecro.in/about-us/>, (22 May, 2022 11.26 Pm)

affect consumers (such as transportation, electricity, communications, and so on). A consumer rights organization is a non-profit consumer group.

The objective of the Consumer Rights Organization:

- a) Organize & Aware Consumer
- b) All consumer rights are protected and made public.
- c) With the assistance of the government and administration, implement consumer education, rights, and duties programs.
- d) Actively assist in the execution of the Consumer Protection Act.
- e) Give and receive moral support for the consumer interest of other organizations while working under the rules of the organization.
- f) Implement legislative measures relating to civil rights in order to attain organizational goals.
- g) To safeguard the interests of consumers, as well as their fundamental needs and rights, such as health, education, water, energy, roads, entertainment, catering, and traffic, among others.
- h) With government assistance, establish consumer information centers in all Indian districts.
- i) Organizing and conducting consumer-related programs to get aid and grants from the central government, state
- j) Through the organization, the Central Government and State Governments implement and operate numerous consumer-related initiatives.
- k) Legally address consumer concerns and complaints to the Consumer Forum and the Commission through the organization.

4.3.5: Consumer Guidance Society of India:

Since independence, India has been striving to develop and strengthen its industrial base. However, in this pursuit of "self-sufficiency", exploitation of consumers by manufacturers and service providers became rampant in India. In the 1960s, only a few monopolistic business houses controlled industry. In one infamous case, forty persons suffered dropsy and glaucoma after consuming groundnut oil adulterated with toxic argemone oil . The victims did not get any justice

and the culprits escaped without punishment. This outrage energized nine women to organize a movement to fight for consumer rights and to form the CGSI in 1966.¹¹⁷

The Consumer Guidance Society of India is a non-profit consumer organization that was founded in 1966¹¹⁸ India to protect and educate Indian consumers about substandard goods and services, contaminated meals, erroneous and dangerous pharmaceuticals, high costs, recurring shortages leading to black markets and profiteering, unmet promises manufacturer guarantees, and a variety of other issues.

Fight for a Legal Framework:

CGSI was the first consumer organization to demand special Consumer Court for redressal of consumers' complaints. In 1975, CGSI led a delegation of five consumer organizations from different parts of India to the then Minister for Food and Civil Supplies, Mr. T. A. Pai and demand for a comprehensive Consumer Protection Act, Special Consumer Courts and a Directorate for implementation of the Act. CGSI's constant follow-up was instrumental in enacting the "Consumer Protection Act 1986" by the "Government of India".¹¹⁹

Aim and Object of Consumer Guidance Society of India:

Consumer Guidance Society of India's important aim and objects include:

- a) consumer education (How to file a Grievance with the appropriate Authority, Education Planning, Soaps and Detergents –Types, Grades, How to purchase, Cosmetics – Types, Grades, How to purchase and Flavors & Fragrances / Perfumes / Body sprays – Types, Grades, How to purchase, Dangers of using cheap products¹²⁰)

¹¹⁷ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Guidance_Society_of_India, (23 May, 2022 6.13 pm)

¹¹⁸ Consumer rights organization, <https://www.thecro.in/about-us/>, (22 May, 2022 11.22 Pm)

¹¹⁹ Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://cgsiindia.org/about-cgsi/cgsi-profile-in-brief/>, (23 May, 2022 6.18 pm)

¹²⁰ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Guidance_Society_of_India, (23 May, 2022 6.38 pm)

- b) holding talks and exhibitions to spread consumer rights awareness among urban poor and rural areas¹²¹.
- c) publication of *KEEMAT* a bi-monthly news magazine now published for over 20 years having articles of general consumer awareness, for CGSI members and general public¹²².
- d) testing of consumer products
- e) consumer complaints redressal.

Holding talks and exhibitions to spread consumer rights awareness among urban poor and rural areas:

The CGSI's primary focus is in rural areas where consumer rights awareness is extremely low. CGSI has organized consumer camps, exhibitions, and consumer education for school and college students with the help of its dedicated volunteers and their expertise in various fields. Today, CGSI programs reach out to more than 20,000 consumers in a year. Now with the help of more and more experts from various fields, CGSI imparts knowledge about prudent investment, Telecom Services, food adulteration detection, medical negligence, mediation, legal redressal of complaints, etc¹²³.

Complaint redressal:

CGSI handles consumer complaints and provides legal counsel to those who wish to file complaints in the Consumer Courts. In cases where a party has received a large number of complaints, bringing both parties together to resolve the issue. The Complaints Committee of the CGSI meets at least twice a week. CGSI has redressed thousands of consumer grievances over the years, with 70-80% success in favor of the consumers¹²⁴. Medical/surgical malpractice and negligence; insurance non-payment; substandard drugs and medicines; home remedies; defective household appliances; poor quality foods and drinks; misleading advertising claims; and

¹²¹ Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://cgsiindia.org/about-cgsi/cgsi-profile-in-brief/>, (23 May, 2022 6.36 pm)

¹²² Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Guidance_Society_of_India, (23 May, 2022 6.40 pm)

¹²³ Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://cgsiindia.org/about-cgsi/cgsi-profile-in-brief/>, (23 May, 2022 10.20 pm)

¹²⁴ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Guidance_Society_of_India, (23 May, 2022 10.21 pm)

grievances concerning investments, real estate, insurance, telephones, and electricity supply, among other things, are all covered by the complaints. CGSI counsels over 400 complaints during the year through personal counseling sessions, correctly guiding complainants, sometimes even clearly saying that they do not have a case to fight for without wrongfully leading them on¹²⁵.

4.3.6: Consumer Association of India:

Consumers Association of India (CAI) is a membership-based organisation with 8,000 registered members all over India¹²⁶. Consumers association of India (CAI) was established on the world Consumers Rights to be a powerful lobby for the consumer¹²⁷. Its primary goals are to raise consumer awareness, empower consumers, and teach them about their consumer obligations and rights. CAI often holds seminars, workshops, and training programs, as well as publishing consumer guides on a number of consumer-interesting issues. In collaboration with its sister organization, CAI has also established a tiny drug lab to screen for counterfeit medications. It has successfully and steadfastly undertaken the mission of raising consumer awareness, educating them about their responsibilities and rights, and ensuring that consumers' voices are heard. (CAI has successfully settled over 98% of the complaints it has received through arbitration. For the remaining 2% CAI has supported the consumer in pursuing the complaint through the Indian legal system¹²⁸). They represent them in international policy forums and the global economy to ensure that they are treated securely, fairly, and honestly. They are also fiercely independent, with no links to corporations or political groups. The Consumers Association of India collaborates and wields power with honesty, persistence, and enthusiasm to achieve concrete changes.

4.4: Practical approach to protect consumer rights in Bangladesh:

Many government departments and Non-profit organizations in Bangladesh work to protect consumer rights. These organizations are constantly working on consumer rights.

¹²⁵ Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://cgsiindia.org/about-cgsi/cgsi-profile-in-brief/>, (23 May, 2022 10.20 pm)

¹²⁶ Consumer Association of India, <https://www.consumersinternational.org/members/members/consumers-association-of-india-cai/>, (23 May, 2022 10.38 Pm)

¹²⁷ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 10 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹²⁸ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 11 (Asia Law House 2021)

4.4.1: Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection:

Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection is a quasi-judicial government department responsible for hearing and addressing consumer complaints over goods and services. It is headquartered in Dhaka with local offices in every divisional capitals of Bangladesh.¹²⁹ The Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection was founded in 2009 through the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009. The act also created the supplementary National Consumer Right Protection Council. The Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection is led by a Director General.¹³⁰ Consumers can lodge a complaint with the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection. If the directorate finds against the company after an investigation, it may levy fines. The directorate will give the complaint 25% of the fine. The aggrieved consumer cannot take legal action against the responsible company without the Directorate's explicit permission, which has prompted consumer advocacy groups to claim that the law is actually working against consumers' interests.

Object of the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection:

The Directorate shall give assistance to the Council in performing all its functions and shall be responsible for the execution of the decisions of the Council.¹³¹ In addition, he will work to protect consumers' rights, prevent anti-consumer rights practices, and take the necessary steps to prevent any apprehended act likely to violate consumers' rights, as well as take the necessary actions in response. (The Directorate shall take action after recording the reasons in writing. He can issue a warrant to arrest such a person or to search the place where such thing, document, paper, or other things related to the offense is kept¹³²). He can also order the temporary closure of any shop, commercial enterprise, etc. for any violation of consumer rights. It should be noted

¹²⁹ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directorate_of_National_Consumer_Rights_Protection, (23 May, 2022 11.55 Pm)

¹³⁰ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directorate_of_National_Consumer_Rights_Protection, (24 May, 2022 10.35 am)

¹³¹ Juralacuity, <https://juralacuity.com/analysis-of-the-consumer-rights-protection-act-2009/>, (24 May, 2022 10.58 am)

¹³² Juralacuity, <https://juralacuity.com/analysis-of-the-consumer-rights-protection-act-2009/>, (24 May, 2022 10.58 am)

that the Directorate shall make a final decision after conducting regular hearings, examinations, and investigations, as well as considering consumer rights, after determining whether any anti-consumer right practice was committed actually as a result of a violation of any provision of this Act.

4.4.2: National Consumer Rights Protection Council:

To preserve and protect consumer rights, the National Consumer Rights Protection Council may issue appropriate regulations, conduct research, raise awareness, and advise the government on consumer protection policy, as well as monitor the activities of the Directorate of Consumer Protection. The District Committees, on the other hand, are responsible for enforcing the National Council's rules and regulations.

4.4.3: Mobile Court:

The word “mobile” is an adjective which means Capable of moving or of being moved readily from place to place and “court” generally signifies an institution in which disputes and conflicts are heard, argued and decided on the basis of law. In other words, court is an official, public forum which a public power establishes by lawful authority to adjudicate disputes, and to dispense civil, labour, administrative and criminal justice under the law. In common law countries, the courts are the central means for dispute resolution, and it is generally understood that all persons have a right to bring their claims before a court. Similarly, those accused of a crime have the right to present their defenses before a court.¹³³ The mobile court has jurisdiction to try offenses involving violations of consumer rights. The mobile court is presided over by an executive Magistrate. Furthermore, the DG has the same authority as an Executive Magistrate to run the mobile court. He has jurisdiction over the entire country of Bangladesh. A Magistrate may immediately recognize an offence under the consumer protection Act, 2009 if it is committed in front of him and sentence him to imprisonment for a maximum of two years based on his confession. However, if the offense is serious enough, he will file a criminal case in a criminal court.

¹³³ Gazi Delwar Hosen and Syed Robayet Ferdous, The Role of Mobile Courts in the Enforcement of Laws in Bangladesh, Volume I (2010) The Northern University Journal of Law 82, 82 (2010)

At present food safety is a major concerning issue in Bangladesh for the sake of public health. As foodborne illness is the main outcome of food adulteration for this every year huge numbers of people are suffering from foodborne illnesses. Unsafe as well as adulterated food is the main foundation of many serious and chronic diseases like diarrhea diseases and various forms of cancer. On the other hand, the foodborne disease kills about two million people annually which include many children stated by the World Health also “Food contaminants contain such as harmful parasites, bacteria, viruses, prions, chemical or radioactive substances which cause more than 200 diseases such as ranging from infectious diseases to cancers. As we know in Bangladesh for controlling food adulteration the mobile court is implemented which is conducted under the Mobile Court Act, 2009. This paper will mainly discuss the conduct of mobile court and procedure along with any limitation of the mobile court if any.¹³⁴

Mobile court’s function under different laws:

Mobile courts are now carrying out their duties in accordance with various laws. With the continued success of the initially established mobile court for the purpose of anti-adulteration drive, the government has already expanded its area of operation and invested powers under various laws. The mobile courts are strategically placed throughout the city, and they examine the fitness of motor vehicles, driving licenses, and the standards of edible food items, as well as taking appropriate punitive measures on the spot. The following laws govern how mobile courts can carry out their functions:

- a) Penal Code, 1860
- b) The Pure Food Ordinance, 1956
- c) The Standard of Weights and Measures Ordinance, 1982
- d) The Special Powers Act, 1974
- e) The Bangladesh Control of Essential Commodities Act, 1956
- f) The Trademark Act, 1940

¹³⁴ Anika Mardiah Chowdhury, Mobile Court Act, 2009 and Limitations, juracuity (24 May, 2022 5.46 PM), <https://juracuity.com/mobile-court-act-2009-limitations/>

Horizontal successes of mobile court to enforce laws:

Offenders who had previously received little punishment for violations of various laws are now being tried and sentenced on a regular basis as a result of the mobile courts' active operations.

The offences under the Penal Code which mobile courts have put into practice are-

- a) Adulteration of food or drink intended for sale
- b) Sale of noxious food or drink
- c) Adulterations of drugs
- d) Sale of adulterated drugs
- e) Sale of drugs as a different drug or preparation

The offences under the Pure Food Ordinance (Amendment) Act which mobile courts have put into operation are-

- a) Manufacture and sale of adulterated food
- b) Sale and use of formalin, intoxicated food color etc.
- c) Manufacture or sale of food not of proper standard or purity
- d) Keeping adulterants in place where food is manufactured or sold.

4.4.4: Consumer Association of Bangladesh (CAB):

Consumers Association of Bangladesh (CAB), a non-government, non-political, non-profit and voluntary consumer organization was founded in February 1978 at the initiation of some dedicated residents in Dhaka who were imbued with the ideas of consumerism, a movement that already took shape in many advanced countries in Europe and America. Primarily started as a social group to protect consumers from commodity adulteration and artificial price-hike it has gradually widened its scope to establish and safeguard consumers' rights and interests in social, economic, health and environmental issues.¹³⁵ The major areas of CAB activities are consumer information & education, monitoring on market prices and quality of essential commodities and utility services, consumers complaints handlings, campaign for safe foods and commodities, ethical drug promotion and safe environment. They also conduct study and research on consumer issues and have previously been involved in lobbying with the government and policy makers for

¹³⁵ Consumer Association of Bangladesh, <https://consumerbd.org/about-cab/>, (24 May, 2022 9.10 Pm)

implementation of Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009.¹³⁶ CAB has been attempting to convey the essence of consumerism to poor and low-middle class consumers since its founding, as well as organizing activities for the promotion and defense of consumer rights and interests.

The Aims and Objectives consumer association of Bangladesh (CAB):

The major objectives of CAB are:

- a) To make consumers aware of their rights and responsibilities.
- b) To promote consumer education, aiming at raising awareness of consumers against exploitation, and providing them with technical knowledge and support for real protection¹³⁷.
- c) Encourage and assist the development of consumer associations and activist groups at the district and rural levels.
- d) Exchange information and knowledge of various actions about consumer protection with national and international organisations¹³⁸.
- e) Provide mediation and legal assistance to displeased customers.
- f) Undertake research studies on consumer issues and problems.
- g) Testing goods and services on a regular basis ensures that the market is safe and consumer-friendly.

CAB activities also include the organization of seminars, workshops, and group meetings, as well as street processions, the distribution of posters and leaflets, and the publication of features in newspapers about environmental pollution and degradation, as well as safe road and transportation systems. The formation and development of consumers for the expansion of consumer movement at the division, district, Upzila, and peripheral levels is a routine activity of CAB. These organizations maintain contact with the national level, deal with consumer education and motivation, and address local consumer problems and issues.

¹³⁶ Consumers International, <https://www.consumersinternational.org/members/members/consumers-association-of-bangladesh-cab/>, (24 May, 2022 9.22 PM)

¹³⁷ Banglapedia, https://en.banglapedia.org/index.php/Consumers_Association_of_Bangladesh, (24 May, 2022 9.41PM)

¹³⁸ Banglapedia, https://en.banglapedia.org/index.php/Consumers_Association_of_Bangladesh, (24 May, 2022 9.45PM)

How CAB Helps Consumers:

CAB has its own complaint department. A dissatisfied consumer whose right has been violated may file a complaint by post, email, or in person. CAB investigates the complaint and provides redress in the form of settlement through negotiation and mediation between the parties. Consumers who have been wronged may receive legal assistance. CAB regularly monitors market prices for essential goods and publishes the price list through media for consumer convenience and knowledge.

4.5: Comparison of practical approaches for protecting consumer rights in India and Bangladesh:

The Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) is to promote, protect and enforce the rights of consumers as a class. It will be empowered to conduct investigations into violation of consumer rights and institute complaints / prosecution, order recall of unsafe goods and services, order discontinuation of unfair trade practices and misleading advertisements, impose penalties on manufacturers/endorsers/publishers of misleading advertisements.¹³⁹ Make actions when needed to protect consumers from harm caused by unfair commercial practices. To file a class action lawsuit, including product recall, refund, and return, etc. And also the Central Council shall be to promote and protect the rights of the consumers. Under section 3 of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 the Central Government shall establish the India Central Consumer Protection Council which is known as the Central Council. It is an advisory body. On the other hand, To preserve and protect consumer rights, the Bangladesh National Consumer Rights Protection Council may issue appropriate regulations, conduct research, raise awareness, and advise the government on consumer protection policy, as well as monitor the activities of the Directorate of Consumer Protection. The District Committees, on the other hand, are responsible for enforcing the National Council's rules and regulations. The Indian National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission,

¹³⁹ pib, <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1642422> , (22 May, 2022 10.47 AM)

is a quasi-judicial body formed under the Consumer Protection Act of 1986¹⁴⁰. The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission strives to provide the remedy to aggrieved consumers as promptly as practicable while bearing in mind the provisions of the Act that provide a timetable for case resolution. If a customer is dissatisfied with a District Forum's decision, he may appeal to the State Commission. On the other hand, The Bangladeshi Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection is a quasi-judicial government department responsible for hearing and addressing consumer complaints over goods and services. The Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection is led by a Director General.¹⁴¹ Consumers can lodge a complaint with the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection. If the directorate finds against the company after an investigation, it may levy fines. The directorate will give the complaint 25% of the fine. The aggrieved consumer cannot take legal action against the responsible company without the Directorate's explicit permission, which has prompted consumer advocacy groups to claim that the law is actually working against consumers' interests. And, The mobile court has jurisdiction to try offenses involving violations of consumer rights. The mobile court is presided over by an executive Magistrate. Furthermore, the DG has the same authority as an Executive Magistrate to run the mobile court. He has jurisdiction over the entire country of Bangladesh. A Magistrate may immediately recognize an offence under the consumer protection Act, 2009 if it is committed in front of him and sentence him to imprisonment for a maximum of two years based on his confession. However, if the offense is serious enough, he will file a criminal case in a criminal court. The Consumer Guidance Society, Consumers Association and Consumer Rights Organisation of India is a non-profit consumer organization. Its main goals are to protect and educate Indian consumers about substandard goods and services, contaminated meals, erroneous and dangerous pharmaceuticals, high costs, recurring shortages leading to black markets and profiteering, unmet promises manufacturer guarantees, and a variety of other issues. And, Consumers Association of Bangladesh (CAB), a non-government, non-political, non-profit and voluntary consumer organization. The major areas of CAB activities are consumer information & education, monitoring on market prices and quality

¹⁴⁰ CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 1986, § 9, No. 68, Acts of Parliament, 1986 (India).

¹⁴¹ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directorate_of_National_Consumer_Rights_Protection, (24 May, 2022 10.35 am)

of essential commodities and utility services, consumers complaints handlings, campaign for safe foods and commodities, ethical drug promotion and safe environment. They also conduct study and research on consumer issues and have previously been involved in lobbying with the government and policy makers for implementation of Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009.

4.6: Conclusions:

A consumer should aware of how to buy a product, what to do if the product is defective and how to find a remedy if deceived by unscrupulous traders. The most important thing for consumer protection is to increase consumer education and awareness. India and Bangladesh have a lot of consumers. It is not possible for government and non-government organizations to raise awareness of so many consumers. These consumers need to be aware of themselves. Also need to know about products, brands, trademarks and product manufacturers. There are many governmental and non-governmental organizations in India and Bangladesh for consumer rights protection, consumer awareness, consumer education, and consumer remedies. In India, for example, the Central Consumer Protection Authority, the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, and the Central Consumer Protection Council have taken all necessary measures to protect consumers under the Consumer Protection Act, 2019. Similarly, in Bangladesh, the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection, National Consumer Rights Protection Council, and Mobile Court have taken all measures to protect consumers in accordance with the Consumer Protection Act, 2009. India and Bangladesh, non-governmental organizations, are working with government departments for consumer protection. For example, the Consumer Rights Organization, Consumer Guidance Society, and Consumer Association of India are involved in promoting consumer education, consumer awareness, and providing legal assistance to consumers. Similarly, Consumer Association of Bangladesh is one of the non-governmental organizations in Bangladesh. They make consumers aware of their rights and responsibilities, provide consumer education and provide legal assistance to consumers. Consumers play an essential role in a country's economy; there is no alternative to protecting these consumers.

Chapter: Five

Present status of Consumer Rights Protection

5.1: Introduction:

Most consumers are currently unable to purchase the right product because they are not aware of their rights and responsibilities. Many times they express dissatisfaction with the product after purchasing it due to not knowing about the product. Consumers lack awareness. If there is a complaint about the product, he is not getting any remedy because he does not know about their rights. Even those who know about their rights do not complain because they do not want to get involved in any trouble. Most of the consumers live in villages and lack education. They do not know about their rights or are not interested in learning. Unscrupulous traders are constantly supplying adulterated products in the market; these products are endangering the health of ordinary consumers. Moreover, many consumers are suffering from serious diseases. Local shopkeepers in India and Bangladesh charge consumers more than a specific price for a product. Consumers cannot say anything because they do not know their rights. The best place to market those who are adulterators is the village. The adulterators know that the people of the village are poorly educated and do not know about consumer rights. Many non-governmental organizations are working on consumer rights, but their activities are not reaching everyone due to a large number of consumers. At the same time, the government's consumer rights department is working to protect consumer rights. As government departments do not have adequate staff, consumer grievances are not being dealt with on time. For this reason, even if consumers are deceived, they are not interested in complaining. Nowadays, consumers are more interested in shopping in online shops because they can buy products at any time of their choice. At the same time, more are deceived by online shops. An offer to sell a product for less than a specific price, but the consumer may not be satisfied with that product when the product arrives. Because the product is adulterated or inferior. At the same time, they are being misled due to misleading advertisements. Consumers are attracted to these products by looking at these advertisements, and after purchasing the product, it is of low quality. Unscrupulous traders adulterated products, and misleading advertisements are increasing day by day. Although there are specific laws on consumer rights, they cannot enforce appropriate actions. Although some activities are seen in the city, no activities are seen in the villages. The situation in Bangladesh is worse than in India.

Commodity prices for intermediaries are rising, and artificial commodities are creating crisis and selling goods at higher prices. Government departments need to play a more significant role in protecting consumers from these rogue traders.

5.2: Problems of Consumers:

A consumer is someone who buys goods or uses services to satisfy his wants in exchange for money. Many unfair and unethical tactics are used by producers and sellers in free markets, and the consumer is frequently cheated in terms of the quality, quantity, and price of goods and services. The consumers face many problems –They are:

5.2.1: Adulteration:

Most of the time, even when paying a high price, consumers do not receive pure or quality goods. For profit maximization, the organization typically supplies adulterated goods. Shopkeepers remove some things or add in a product which further lowers the quality of that product. The innocent consumer is the victim, who has no means to identify the genuine from the adulterated goods¹⁴².

5.2.2: Wrong Weights and Measures:

Sellers attempt to defraud by supplying goods weighing with faulty balances and underweight measures. The consumers go home with less quantity of goods for which they pay the price to a particular measurement¹⁴³. Even in the organized markets such as shopping malls, customers are cheated with wrong weights pasted on the packets¹⁴⁴.

5.2.3: High Price:

Sellers release fewer goods into the market that are in high demand, and they collect higher prices by raising the prices. Inflation has now become commonplace, and the consumer has no choice but to accept it.

¹⁴² Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 31 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁴³ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 31 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁴⁴ Articles junction, <http://articles-junction.blogspot.com/2013/06/various-problems-faced-by-consumers-in.html>, (26 May 2022 10.58 AM)

5.2.4: Irregular Supply:

One of the common problems faced by consumers is an irregular supply of goods¹⁴⁵. Organizations create artificial scarcity of essential goods by stockpiling them, resulting in high prices. The short supply of goods leads to non-availability and the consumer has to stand in queues to the goods he wants¹⁴⁶.

5.2.5: Misleading Advertisements:

To shape the needs of consumers, numerous deceptive, disruptive, and misleading tendencies are followed primarily through advertisements. Most consumers are frequently taken advantage of by false advertisements promising free gifts, high returns on investments, large discounts, nationwide contests, and so on. There was no law to control such misrepresentations in advertisements for a long time. The consumer is vulnerable to capitalist-controlled media influences, is self-depreciated, and is unsure of his needs and desires.

5.2.6: Black markets:

The present day market is seller's market for consumer goods and not the buyer's market. Present day businessmen store their goods in godowns and create artificial shortage of goods and release the goods in black market with high prices.¹⁴⁷ The consumer has no choice but to buy on the black market. Everyone is aware of the cause, but no one can do anything to control it because the government is behind the black markets.

5.2.7: Lack of Information:

The main problems faced by consumers is lack of information. The customers even do not know the sources of getting information.¹⁴⁸ Very often consumers do not get proper and timely information. The information may be about the arrival of new product or service, availability of

¹⁴⁵ India study channel, <https://www.indiastudychannel.com/resources/127857-What-are-problems-faced-by-consumers.aspx>, (26 May 2022, 11.15 AM)

¹⁴⁶ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 31 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁴⁷ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 31-32 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁴⁸ India study channel, <https://www.indiastudychannel.com/resources/127857-What-are-problems-faced-by-consumers.aspx>, (26 May 2022, 11.53 AM)

product; Changes in the existing product, etc. In the absence of information consumers may not be able to make proper decisions of purchasing product or services.¹⁴⁹

5.2.8: False Goods:

Customers face a significant problem with false goods. Customers are cheated when unethical producers imitate popular brand names. Even pharmaceuticals are copied by illegal producers.

5.2.9: Fraudulent Practices:

Another problem of the consumer is the fraudulent practices of the producers, manufacturers, traders, etc. Fraudulent practice means any practice adopted by the traders with an intent to deceive the consumer to purchase the goods by making false suggestions, which are not true or by concealing facts having knowledge or belief or by making false promises without having any intention of performing it.¹⁵⁰ Consumer claims have not been supported by business practices in India and Bangladesh. Most business practices simply deceive consumers and attempt to gain their loyalty without fully protecting their long-term interests.

5.2.10: No proper Return for Money:

Many consumers believe that they do not receive adequate returns for the money they paid to purchase the products. This could be due to poor quality, decreased durability, adulteration, inadequate packaging, and so on.

5.2.11: Health & Safety Hazards:

The consumer want safe, good quality and convenient food products which has to be met by proper policy framework.¹⁵¹ Many a time customers face problems of health hazards when they buy goods in the shops. For instance, shopkeepers sell products even after the expiry date; fruit vendors use chemicals to ripen the fruits faster; manufacturers use inferior quality of materials to keep the prices low; and so on.¹⁵²

¹⁴⁹ Articles junction, <http://articles-junction.blogspot.com/2013/06/various-problems-faced-by-consumers-in.html>, (26 May 2022 11.56 AM)

¹⁵⁰ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 32 (Asia Law House 2021)

¹⁵¹ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 32 (Asia Law House 2021)

5.2.12: Lack of awareness:

In the era of consumerism and market economy the problems of rural consumer have not been adequately addressed. The rural consumer remains disadvantaged as their right to information, choice, redress, education and the rights to heard are not sufficiently fulfilled.¹⁵³ They are exploited in a variety of ways due to a lack of knowledge about their rights. The rural consumer, who relies heavily on weekly markets, particularly in remote areas, to purchase necessities, is frequently duped in terms of price, weight, and measurement.

5.3: The current situation of a consumer:

A consumer is the end-user of a product. Consumers play an essential role in economic development. A consumer buys the necessary goods for himself or his family. Making a product for consumers to use or eat. The last stage of this cycle is the consumer. Consumers end up using or consuming products. Despite being so important to consumers, not all measures can play an effective role in protecting consumers. Currently, the situation of consumers is terrible for dishonest traders. Constantly adulterating goods are marketed in beautiful wrappers, and those products are sold to consumers using chemicals. The worst situation is in the village consumers. They lack education, are not aware of themselves, and even if they take measures to make them aware, they do not accept them. Consumers cannot buy goods at the right price from local shops. Shopkeepers sell goods at higher prices to consumers due to increased prices due to intermediaries. At present, a consumer is more likely to be deceived by buying in an online shop, where goods can be easily purchased; in this opportunity, vendors are deceiving and attracting consumers and forcing them to buy the product. When this product reaches the consumers, they are not satisfied with this product.

At the same time, consumers are more dissatisfied with the delivery. Online companies cannot deliver on time even though they are supposed to deliver on time. Although consumer awareness

¹⁵² Articles junction, <http://articles-junction.blogspot.com/2013/06/various-problems-faced-by-consumers-in.html>, (26 May 2022 12.24 pm)

¹⁵³ Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law 33 (Asia Law House 2021)

is supposed to be increased according to specific laws to protect consumers, this awareness program does not reach the consumers. If the consumer is aggrieved about something, he must wait long to get the remedy. If the consumer of Bangladesh wants, he cannot file a case in the conventional court without the permission of the consumer department. Counterfeit products are scattered in the market; the consumers buy these products due to unconsciousness. Adulterated products endanger the health of the consumers. Many consumers in the city are aware but do not take legal action due to their busy schedules. A consumer is constantly being deceived due to a lack of awareness. A product package should have detailed instructions for that product, but not an identical product. Poor people in rural and urban areas buy adulterated and low-quality products due to low income. They are at higher health risk. A consumer needs to know his rights and responsibilities and share his rights with friends, family, relatives, and people in society.

5.4: Presently, What are the problems consumers are facing in e-commerce?

In recent years, the e-commerce industry in India and Bangladesh has expanded and changed the way consumers shop. People are increasingly relying on online discount sales and schemes, with major companies exclusively launching their products on online shopping websites such as Amazon, Flipkart, Shopclues, Daraz Bangladesh, pickaboo, ajkerdeal, and others. However, as the number of e-commerce websites has increased and more consumers are purchasing from these portals, the problems that consumers face when purchasing their favorite shoes, or the latest phone and laptop, have also increased. Some problems faced by consumers while shopping online, such as:

Problems related to product quality:

The most common issue that customers face when shopping online is that there is no guarantee of a product's quality. Because most e-commerce websites act as aggregators for sellers to sell their products, more fraudulent sellers are registering on these websites and selling low-quality or counterfeit goods under the guise of genuine and branded goods. These sellers sell pretty poor products in order to deceive customers and increase their sales, thereby exacerbating the problems associated with online shopping. Quality-checks are seldom performed on these products as the magnitude of online sales has increased, especially during online sale days.

Sellers sometimes refuse to replace the faulty product or refund the consumer's money, leaving the latter with a low-quality product and money down the drain¹⁵⁴.

Problems related to delivery:

Another issue that arises in online shopping is delivery and logistics. Products are frequently lost or damaged in transit, and order tracking systems are unable to locate the product accurately. People prefer same-day delivery. One-day or two-day delivery, paying an additional fee to have their product delivered.

Payment issues:

There are lot of online shopping problems faced nowadays. Many consumers become victims to online payment issues. Even though there are several payment methods like Net Banking, Credit or Debit Card payments and even Cash-on-delivery, there are payment failures due to website's server error, payment gateway error or issues with One Time Password (OTP). Technical glitches often deduct the payment from buyer's account or card, but the website does not receive the payment.¹⁵⁵ Consumers must file a complaint with the website's customer service in order to receive a refund, but they must wait 10-15 days for any action to be taken.

Hidden costs:

Problems with online shopping are becoming increasingly common. After the consumer completes the purchase, e-commerce marketplaces frequently charge hidden fees. Taxes, additional shipping and handling charges are hidden from customers until their purchases are completed. Websites also include the option for customers to buy products worth a certain amount in order to avoid shipping charges; however, sellers charge additional fees even for purchases worth more than the set amount.

Website Policies:

Many shopping websites have no website policies at all or have unclear and confusing user, return and refund policy. Vague stipulations leave consumers confused about refund and return

¹⁵⁴ Prachi Darji, Most Common Problems faced by Consumers while Shopping Online, <https://www.myadvo.in/blog/5-most-common-problems-faced-by-consumers-while-shopping-online>, (26 May 2022 2.23 PM

¹⁵⁵ Prachi Darji, Most Common Problems faced by Consumers while Shopping Online, <https://www.myadvo.in/blog/5-most-common-problems-faced-by-consumers-while-shopping-online>, (26 May 2022 2.23 PM

of products and product description problems in e-commerce. With no policies defined, sellers often reject a consumer's claim to return the product or refund the money.¹⁵⁶ Some websites are also unclear about product warranties and guarantees, and buyers frequently end up purchasing faulty products with no warranty or replacement option.

Online shopping has become the most convenient way for consumers to buy great products at low prices from the comfort of their own homes. However, while participating in sale festivals or online discount days, a consumer may encounter any of the aforementioned issues.

5.5: The present situation of Retail stores for consumers:

Retail stores are goods buying centers. Most of the consumers here buy goods from retailers for money. Consumers buy goods directly for consumption or the family. Retail retailers buy goods directly from manufacturers or importers themselves or wholesale through wholesalers and sell them to marginal users. Numerous consumers in India and Bangladesh are associated with retail stores. These consumers collect daily necessities directly from retail stores. Some rogue retailers sometimes sell low-quality products to consumers for a higher profit. This low-quality product is endangering the health of consumers. Moreover, artificial commodities for mediators create a crisis by selling fixed-priced products at higher prices. The products that are in high demand by the consumers make a product crisis on their own and are supplied to the market at a higher price than the fixed price; as a result, the consumers are forced to buy the goods from the retailers at higher prices. Consumers have nothing to do here. India and Bangladesh retailers sell goods at a higher price than the fixed price if any stranger or foreigner buys a product. Strangers or foreigners do not have to do this for a while and are forced to purchase higher-priced products because they need those products. Retailers lack skills. They cannot determine the exact price of the product. They sell the same product at different prices, which is entirely illegal. They do not know how to deal with consumers. Sometimes misbehaves with consumers. At the same time, if they want to know about any product, they cannot say about it. A consumer has the right to know about any product. Here the consumer does not get accurate information from the retail store.

¹⁵⁶ Prachi Darji, Most Common Problems faced by Consumers while Shopping Online, <https://www.myadvo.in/blog/5-most-common-problems-faced-by-consumers-while-shopping-online>, (26 May 2022 3.202 PM

Moreover, retail stores cannot create a healthy environment. It is often seen that the necessary food items are kept outside the store, and the food items are kept open. These products are for the consumer to buy and eat, which puts his health at risk. Moreover, there are numerous open markets in the two countries, where all the inferior products are sold. These low-quality products are collected by the retailers and sold to the low-income consumers in the villages at higher prices. The activities of the consumer department are not seen to take action against the retailers. Retail stores make food items on the side of the road in unhealthy environments and sell them to consumers. Consumers cannot take legal action against retailers because they do not know about consumer rights. And those who do know are not interested in suing retailers.

5.6: Current status of legal protection to consumers:

Consumers play an important role in the growth of businesses and the economy as a whole. Consumer protection laws are concerned with regulating the quality of products and services as well as protecting consumers' interests so that they can make informed decisions. In response to the rapid changes in industry and commerce around the world, the (Indian) Consumer Protection Act, 1986 was amended with a new broader law that took effect in 2020, as well as new rules and regulations. (In India, consumer rights protection is governed primarily by the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 (Consumer Protection Act), and the laws and regulations enacted under it. Some of the laws and regulations enacted under the Consumer Protection Act include the Consumer Protection Act (E-Commerce), 2020, Consumer Protection Rules (Mediation), 2020, Consumer Protection Laws (Consumer Dispute Resolution Commissions), 2020 and Consumer Protection (General) Acts, 2020. Apart from the Consumer Protection Act, there are various other laws and regulations enacted regarding the protection of consumer interests that cover specific issues such as food, drugs and cosmetics¹⁵⁷).

The consumer movement arose as a result of consumer dissatisfaction as retailers engaged in increasingly egregious practices. The new Act completely restructures the administration and resolution of consumer disputes in India. It imposes severe penalties, including jail time, for adulteration and false advertising. More importantly, it now establishes guidelines for the sale of goods via e-commerce. (Here are some of the highlights:An aggrieved consumer can file

¹⁵⁷ Aviral srivastava, Consumer protection law: India, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/consumer-laws/consumer-protection-law-india-41083/>, (26 May, 2022 10.17 PM)

complaints about a defect in goods or deficiency in services from where she lives, instead of the place of business or residence of the seller or service provider. The new law provides for e-filing of consumer complaint as well. A concept of product liability has been introduced by the new law, thereby allowing aggrieved consumers to claim significant compensation as a relief due to the negligence of the manufacturer or service provider. Misleading advertisements may be punished with imprisonment. Celebrities endorsing a product may not be punished but can be barred from endorsing if the advertisement is misleading. E-commerce is now tightly regulated, and e-commerce companies are now expected to disclose all relevant product information, including country of origin, and respond to the grievance of consumers within prescribed timelines. Settlement of consumer disputes through mediation i.e. with the help of a neutral intermediary outside the consumer court is encouraged under the new law, thus saving time and resources of disputing parties which would otherwise have been spent on dispute resolution through a formal mechanism¹⁵⁸). There was no official program in place to protect consumers from market exploitation. For a long time, when a consumer was dissatisfied with a particular product or store, he avoided purchasing that product or stopped purchasing from that store. Consumers were thought to be responsible for exercising caution when purchasing goods or services. It has taken organizations in India and around the world many years to raise awareness. On the other hand, Bangladesh's current legal protection system for consumers is inadequate and out of date. Furthermore, whatever few laws exist are not strictly enforced to protect the rights of ordinary consumers. As a result, consumers in Bangladesh are denied their rights in every aspect of their lives. The Bangladesh Constitution recognizes consumer rights to a limited extent in its section on "fundamental principles of state policy." Consumer protection provisions can be found in Articles 15 and 18 of the Constitution. However, these provisions are more concerned with the critical issues of "health" and "food" than with other consumer rights. Furthermore, the aforementioned provisions are mentioned in the section of the Constitution titled "fundamental principles of state policy," rather than "fundamental rights." As a result, they are mostly unenforceable in court.

¹⁵⁸ Anay Shukla and Anil Upadhyay, New Consumer Protection law in India: A Simple Overview (Seller Beware!) , <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=4c180f5c-b6d6-417a-ab22-6275d0d5c0f9>, (26 May 2022 10.37 PM)

Further, there are certain legislations, part of which has got direct bearings on consumer protection. For example, sections 264-267, 272-276, 478-483 of the Bangladesh Penal Code 1860, the Poison Act 1919, the Dangerous Drug Act 1930, the Trade Mark Act 1940, the Animals Slaughter (Restriction) and Meat Act 1957, the Special Powers Act 1974, the Standards of Weights and Measures Ordinance 1982, the Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute Ordinance 1985, the Narcotics (Control) Act 1990, and the Safe Blood Transfusion Act 2002, etc.¹⁵⁹ (The current laws are faulty and do not meet the present needs. Under the existing legal regime, the aggrieved consumers themselves cannot go to the court to sue against the violators. It is only the designated government officials empowered under these laws, who can initiate and sue against the violators. The provisions of penalty or punishment under the current laws are so negligible that nobody cares to abide by such laws; and the laws are not effectively enforced¹⁶⁰).

5.7: Currently, the role of the Consumer rights protection authorities:

In India, Consumer Protection Division is mandated to implement the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 and Rules/Regulations made under the this Act. It is entrusted with the framing of policy related to the protection of the interests of the consumers particularly those grievances arising in post sale of goods and services. It provides for establishment of three-tier quasi-judicial consumer disputes redressal machinery at the District, State and National levels commonly known as “Consumer Commissions” to render simple, inexpensive and speedy justice to consumers. These redressal agencies have the jurisdiction to adjudicate the complaints received from consumers against any defect in the goods purchased or deficiencies in the services availed or any unfair/restrictive trade practices, etc. adopted by any trader or person. Apart from the quasi judicial mechanism, National Consumer Helpline and Zonal Consumer Helplines also addresses consumer grievances under the supervision of this Division. The Department looks after the establishment and functioning of Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) and National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC), the apex consumer court. Also

¹⁵⁹ Assignment point, Protection of the Consumer Rights in Bangladesh , <https://assignmentpoint.com/protection-consumer-rights-bangladesh/>, (26 May 2022 10.57)

¹⁶⁰ bdjls, <https://bdjls.org/consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-a-critical-study#one>, (26 May 2022 11.02 PM)

constitution of Central Consumer Protection Council is done by Consumer Protection Division.¹⁶¹

The Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) has imposed a penalty of Rs 10 lakh on eyewear maker Sure Vision India Sur for a misleading advertisement, which claimed its products improve eyesight naturally and eliminate eye strain, and directed it to discontinue the commercial. The CCPA, which initiated action after it received a complaint against the firm, passed the order on February 25, 2022, directing Director General (Investigation) to investigate the claims made by the company in the advertisement, the Consumer Affairs Ministry said in a statement.¹⁶² Cab aggregators, including Ola and Uber, have been warned of strict action unless they improve their systems and redress rising consumer complaints, a senior government official said on Tuesday. The government held a meeting on Tuesday with the ride-hailing platforms amid a rise in consumer complaints of alleged unfair trade practices by them, including ride cancellation policy, as drivers force customers to cancel trips after accepting bookings, which results in customers paying cancellation penalties.

Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) Chief Commissioner Nidhi Khare said the cab aggregators should immediately come out with solutions. "The authority is likely to issue an advisory to ensure that unfair trade practices by cab aggregators are not carried on in violation of consumers' rights.¹⁶³ The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission has awarded a whopping Rs 2 crore compensation to a woman who reportedly lost her modelling assignments due to a bad haircut given by the staff at ITC Maurya Salon in the capital. A five-star hotel in Delhi had to pay a heavy price for a haircut gone wrong! The mental trauma a woman, a communication professional and a model, underwent due to the negligence of a hair professional at the five-star hotel's salon, led the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission

¹⁶¹ consumer affairs of India, <https://consumeraffairs.nic.in/organisation-and-units/division/consumer-protection-unit>, (27 May 2022 11.09 AM)

¹⁶² PTI, CCPA imposes Rs 10 lakh penalty on Sure Vision for misleading ads, The Economic Times (28 May 2022 5.52 PM, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/services/advertising/ccpa-imposes-rs-10-lakh-penalty-on-sure-vision-for-misleading-ads/articleshow/90497580.cms>)

¹⁶³ PTI, Centre warns cab aggregators of strict action for unfair trade practices, The Economic Times (10 May 2022 3.20 PM, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/technology/centre-warns-cab-aggregators-of-strict-action-for-unfair-trade-practices/articleshow/91465856.cms>)

(NCDRC) to take a major action against ITC Maurya - it has been asked to pay a whopping Rs 2 crore compensation to the woman.¹⁶⁴ Similarly, According to experts, the rights of the consumer are hardly respected in the country and the observance of the day cannot ensure consumer rights as effective monitoring of prices and quality of goods is little in Bangladesh. The government, however, says that a number of entities, including the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection, the Bangladesh Food Safety Authority and the Bangladesh Competition Commission, are working to ensure quality products and services within the purchasing capacity of the consumer.¹⁶⁵ The National Consumer Rights Protection Department has fined a trader Tk 50,000 for selling soybean oil at exorbitant prices. According to the district office of the National Consumer Rights Protection Department, a five-liter bottle of soybean oil has a price tag of Rs 695, but the shopkeeper charges Rs 1,000 to one buyer. Asaduzzaman, assistant director of the consumer department, was present. During the interrogation, both the buyer and the seller admitted selling oil at a higher price. The businessman was then fined TK 50,000. His shop was also sealed for illegally storing soybean oil at home.¹⁶⁶

The National Consumer Rights Protection Department has conducted a raid on flour and flour wholesale shops in Savar, Dhaka. Dhaka District Office Assistant Director led the campaign. Abdul Jabbar Mandal. Muhammad Hasanuzzaman, Assistant Director at the Head Office of the National Consumer Rights Protection Department, and members of the law enforcement agencies, were present on occasion. Officials at the National Consumer Rights Protection Department said a raid was carried out at an Ekta Enterprise shop in Namabazar, Savar. The company was fined Tk 50,000 for not having the desired price increase, purchase receipt, and price list. Later, Shilpi Enterprise was fined Rs 5,000 for not having a price list, and M / s Alam

¹⁶⁴ Ipsita Bhattacharya, Haircut gone wrong! ITC Maurya in Delhi ordered to pay Rs 2 crore compensation to woman for bad haircut, Zee News (24 September 2021 10.11 AM),<https://zeenews.india.com/india/haircut-gone-wrong-itc-maurya-in-delhi-ordered-to-pay-rs-2-crore-compensation-to-woman-for-bad-haircut-2396624.html>

¹⁶⁵ Moinul Haque, Consumer rights hardly respected, Newage (15 March 2022 00:00), <https://www.newagebd.net/article/165440/consumer-rights-hardly-respected>

¹⁶⁶ Prothom Alo district reporter, The trader was fined Tk 50,000 for selling soybean oil at a higher price, Prothom Alo (23 May 2022 19:01), <https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/district/%E0%A6%AC%E0%A7%87>

Enterprise was fined Rs 1 lakh for being underweight, arbitrary price increase, and discrepancy in selling price with the list.¹⁶⁷

5.8: The Role of the Government for the consumer:

The government has enacted specific laws to protect consumer rights in India and Bangladesh. If there is the Act, it will not work; the government needs supervision. At present, the government has made it timely to protect consumer rights in India. Under current law, fraudulent transactions involving unscrupulous traders, misleading advertisements, and e-commerce are punishable by imprisonment and fines, and the government is making to give remedy through mediation.

However, this activity is slow to complete. Consumer awareness activities are not seen as adequate by India's central and state governments. It remains the responsibility of the government to raise awareness about consumer rights. According to the law, the officials and employees of the government's consumer department have the obligation to make the consumers aware of their rights and provide redressal to the consumers' grievances. The government should monitor the activities of the consumer department so that the rights of consumers are protected. Except for World Consumer Day, the central and state governments do not comment on consumer programs. Moreover, the situation of the government party is the same. Consumer protection is not discussed in government party programs. Only the government can play an essential role in protecting consumer rights. This government will have to take a more influential part in party politics and central and state government officials so that the rights of consumers are protected. If consumers are protected, then society and people will be able to live healthy lives. The situation in Bangladesh is worse than in India. The current consumer rights protection law in Bangladesh is not up to date. Various consumer rights protection non-governmental organizations demand that consumer rights protection laws be made timely. Officials and employees of the government consumer department have different responsibilities for consumer protection as per the law, but they are

¹⁶⁷ Prothom Alo district reporter, Raid on flour shop in Savar, fine of Rs 1.5 lakh, Prothom Alo (17 May 2022 17:04),<https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/district/%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%AD%E0%A6%BE%E0>

not fulfilling them properly. Under the current law, consumers are being made aware of their rights, but they are not being implemented. At the same time, no action has been taken to resolve consumers' grievances. Occasionally, under the direction of the government, the officials of the consumer department start various activities. However, after a few days, their actions cannot go further due to negligence. According to the law, even though the consumer department's regular activities, they do not implement them earnestly. Bangladesh always talks about market monitoring but occasionally visits the market.

However, when there is a shortage of goods in the market, a sudden rise in prices, and the effect of fraud increases, the officials at the behest of the government rise and fall for the market system. The government needs to play a more effective role in protecting consumer rights, and the current law needs to be adapted.

5.9: Conclusion:

King of the consumer market. The consumer economy plays a vital role in growth. Many non-governmental organizations, including the government, are working to protect the rights of consumers. There is no fundamental institution for the conscious evolution of consumers in India and Bangladesh. The government has enacted specific laws to protect consumers, but unscrupulous traders supply adulterated products to the market. Consumers are buying these products and later expressing dissatisfaction. Consumer protection requires raising awareness from lower to higher strata of society. Consumers are being deceived through adulterated, fake goods and misleading advertisements while purchasing products.

Moreover, the current e-commerce is being promoted as an effective means of deception. Consumers suffer from adulterated products, dishonest products, and delivery and payment issues. In the open market, adulterated goods reach village retailers through intermediaries, and retailers sell directly to consumers. Consumers in rural areas lack awareness; they do not know how to buy products or determine the right product. Unscrupulous traders are constantly deceiving consumers. This rate is equal in both countries. The two countries' governments are launching various departments to enforce consumer rights laws, but their activities are slow and complete. Unscrupulous traders get the opportunity to cheat due to a lack of skilled workers and

a lack of regular market monitoring. Sometimes the consumers of the traders are fined by the department's officials for cheating. Strict enforcement of the law is required to prevent such traders from conducting operations a second time. Consumers are not aware that they have been deceived but do not complain, for which the Consumer Department cannot take any action. Unscrupulous traders are being encouraged to cheat by not complaining. Retailers lack skills. They don't know how to deal with consumers; they sometimes misbehave with consumers. And those who are aware, if they complain, do not get the remedy in time and dismiss the allegations for various reasons. If the complaint is not settled within 30 days of filing, there is an opportunity to file a case in a specific court. Still, no case can be filed in any court without the permission of the Bangladesh Consumer Department. While the Consumer Rights Act in India is timely, the Consumer Rights Act in Bangladesh is not convenient. The Bangladesh Consumer Rights Act urgently needs to be amended.

Chapter: Six

The judiciary's perspective on the protection of consumer rights

6.1: Introduction:

The judicial systems in India and Bangladesh are both independent and impartial. Rather, this is the only pillar of Indian and Bangladeshi democracy in which all Indian and Bangladeshis have complete trust. This faith is amply demonstrated by the fact that numerous new cases are filed in courts across the country on a daily basis. As a result, the Indian and Bangladeshi judiciaries are among the most powerful pillars of Indian democracy. An impartial judiciary is required for a political system to function properly. It is the government's third organ, and it is responsible for delivering justice to the aggrieved party. In today's society, there is no substitute for the judiciary. Globalization of science and technology has resulted in rapid urbanization and modernization, resulting in intense market competition. The traditional view of purchasing goods and specific services changed, and many products, services, and professions were brought under the expanded scope of consumer law. As consumers, we are concerned about money, choice, health, and the safety of our lives. The seller's attitude toward the consumer as the weaker section has always dominated the market. In recent years, the market has been influenced by false, misleading advertisements or representations, bargaining, offering gifts, prizes, contests, and hoardings attracting the public for products or services.

(Since the enactment of the Consumer Protection Act in 1986, which set up these courts, they have functioned to uphold consumer rights and bolster the strength of the individual citizen to challenge the wrongdoings of businesses in markets. While High Courts protect the fundamental rights of citizens under writ jurisdiction, these consumer courts protect the rights of citizens as consumers buying goods and services from corporations in the marketplace. The Consumer Protection Act 1986 amended 2019 provided a three-tier, quasi-judicial structure for a speedy resolution of consumer disputes. The provisions of this Act covered goods as well as services. The goods are manufactured, produced, or sold to consumers through wholesalers and retailer

All services like transport, telephone, electricity, housing, banking, insurance, Misleading advertisements, e-commerce, etc., were covered¹⁶⁸).

However, In Bangladesh, a significant drawback of the Act is that it is mostly an administrative one and does not have a rights-based, bottom-up approach like other new consumer protection legislation around the world. To start with, despite the name of the act, “consumer rights” are not defined or listed, although a list of practices are termed as “anti-consumer rights practices”. The Act mostly concerns itself with the composition of the National Consumer Rights Protection Council and the National Consumer Rights Protection Directorate. Although it fulfils one function of a consumer law, which is to establish an institution tasked with consumer protection, it can barely be called a “citizen’s guide” as it does not define their rights as consumers and does not empower them to participate in the enforcement of those rights. Another important criticism forwarded is that the CPRA, 2009 does not provide standard international precepts of strict liability and to prevent liability shifting through contractual means to protect the rights of the consumers. There is no provision in the CPRA, 2009 on unfair conduct or unfair contract terms to better ensure the safety of Bangladesh consumers in relation to services liability.¹⁶⁹

6.2: Judicial framework for providing justice to consumers:

There is a judicial framework for providing judicial remedies. How to file a complaint, investigate, and start a trial are all within a framework. Similarly, their grievances are settled according to specific laws to compensate the consumers. The judicial structure of India and Bangladesh is almost the same.

6.2.1: Consumer Justice System in Bangladesh:

6.2.1.1: Judicial:

The judiciary plays the most important role in enforcing a law. Similarly, the Judicial Department has a role to play in implementing consumer rights protection laws. The last resort for consumers is the court. If the consumer does not get redress through the department, he can

¹⁶⁸ Clap , <https://clap.nls.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/EVOLUTION-OF-CONSUMER-COURTS-IN-INDIA-THE-CONSUMER-PROTECTION-ACT-2019-AND-EMERGING-THEMES-OF-CONSUMER-JURISPRUDENCE-ANKUR-SAHA-AND-SRI-RAM-KHANNA.pdf>, (29 May 2022 1.18 AM)

¹⁶⁹ HG Legal Resources, <https://www.hg.org/legal-articles/protecting-consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-39014>, (29 May 2022 1.28 AM)

get redress through the court. The place of consumer dependence is the court. The court ordered an investigation based on the consumer's allegations and subsequently provided redressal if the allegations were found to be true.

6.2.1.1.1: Procedural aspect of criminal remedies:

a) The court that functions as the court of original jurisdiction is Metropolitan Magistrate for metropolitan areas and the Court of Judicial magistrate 1st class for areas other than metropolitan areas.¹⁷⁰

b) For the purpose of dispensing justice, Consumer Protection Act , 2009 confers the cognizance taking power as well as conducting trial upon Courts of Judicial magistrate 1st class for areas other than metropolitan areas and Metropolitan Magistrate for metropolitan areas.¹⁷¹

c) The consumer or complainant must file his or her complaint with the authorized officer of the directorate or any executive magistrate appointed by the district magistrate. The deadline for filing a complaint is 30 days from the date the cause of action arises¹⁷².

d) Following receipt of the complaint, the authorized officer shall initiate an investigation to determine the validity of the complaint. Following the investigation, the investigating officer must submit the report to the court for consideration. The report must be submitted within 90 days of the date of the complaint¹⁷³.

e) The court may proceed with the case trial after taking cognizance.

f) The Consumer Protection Act, 2009 also provides for summary trial in order to expedite the trial of cases.¹⁷⁴

Time limit for complaint: No complaint shall be accepted if such complaint is not made by any person to the Director General or any officer of the Directorate empowered in this behalf within-

¹⁷⁰ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 57 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

¹⁷¹ Id. at S 57(2)

¹⁷² Id. at s 60

¹⁷³ Id. at s 61

¹⁷⁴ Id . at S 58

30 (thirty) days of arising the cause of action of any anti-consumer right practice under this Act.¹⁷⁵ It also does not allow for the forgiveness of delays. As a result, no matter how genuine the complaint, it will be dismissed because it was filed after the deadline. In fact, this provision violates the consumer's inherent right to justice. As a result, the victim is denied the right to justice under natural justice, and the system mentioned above has impliedly struck at Bangladesh's traditional criminal justice system.

Summary trial:

The Consumer Protection Act allows for summary procedure trials in accordance with Section 260 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, without impairing the provisions of Section 57 of the CRP Act 2009.¹⁷⁶

A critical analysis of the provision for summary trial reveals that it is not conducive for justice to consumers of Bangladesh. The term „trial by summary procedure“ does not imply trial by mobile courts; still, it is taken to imply „trial by mobile courts“ which is incorrect from legal point of view. Due to this misconception, the whole system of consumer justice has become dependent upon trial by mobile courts. Moreover, The trial by mobile courts receives its sanction from the Mobile Courts Act, 2009, not from the CRP Act 2009. This system of resorting or depending on other law places the consumer justice system at stake.¹⁷⁷

Appellate jurisdiction (Criminal justice):

Any party aggrieved by any judgment or order passed by the Magistrate, may prefer an appeal to the Sessions Judge having local jurisdiction within 60 (sixty) days of the judgment or order.¹⁷⁸

6.2.1.1.2: Procedural aspect of civil remedies:

Any affected consumer from filing a civil suit in a competent Civil Court for claiming civil remedies against a person on the ground that any criminal proceeding has been initiated against

¹⁷⁵ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 60 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

¹⁷⁶ Id. at s 57

¹⁷⁷ Zahangir Alam Khan, Consumer Justice In Bangladesh: A Critical Study of Laws & Rules, Dhaka University Institutional Repository, 2016, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/Zahangir%20Alam%20Khan.pdf

¹⁷⁸ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 65 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

the person for any anti- consumer right practice or the person has been convicted of a criminal offence for such act.If any consumer is affected by a seller for his anti-consumer right practice, and if such damage is assessable in consideration of money, the consumer may file a civil suit in any competent Civil Court claiming compensation not exceeding five times of the amount assessed for the damage.The Court may, after considering the plaint, defence, evidences and all other circumstances, allow any amount of compensation within the limit not exceeding five times of the actual amount assessed for the damage which the Court may think fit for the end of justice.¹⁷⁹ The Civil Court may order the defendant to replace the defective goods with appropriate goods, the defendant to take back the defective goods and pay back the price to the buyer and the defendant to give the complainant appropriate compensation not exceeding five times of the amount assessed for the damage proved; and to pay cost of the suit.¹⁸⁰

Appellate jurisdiction (Civil justice):

The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 and the Civil Courts Act, 1887, an appeal may be preferred only to the High Court Division against the judgment and decree passed by a Court under section 67 within 90 (ninety) days of such judgment and decree.¹⁸¹

6.2.1.2: Administrative:

6.2.1.2.1: Directorate of Consumer Protection:

The CRP Act 2009 provides provisions for establishing the Directorate of Consumer Protection for consumer protection.¹⁸² This organization functions mainly through two processes – centrally by the officials of this organization, the office of District magistracy, and the committees and lastly, through committees or councils constituted under the CRP Act 2009.¹⁸³ The Director General or any officer empowered by the Directorate may, if he thinks expedient to prevent any anti-consumer right practice or to take any action against any offence of anti-consumer right under this Act, take administrative actions of imposing only fine or cancellation of trade license

¹⁷⁹ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 66 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

¹⁸⁰ Id. at s 67

¹⁸¹ Id. at s 67

¹⁸² Id. at s 18

¹⁸³ Id. at s 69

or suspending commercial functions, permanently or temporarily, without imposing any punishment and taking any action to file a criminal case against the convicted person.¹⁸⁴ According to the provision of this Act, the powers and functions of this Organization is administrative in nature and it may be undertaken without recourse to any judicial or quasi-judicial bodies. But, main weakness of this organization of is its failure to formulate the strategy of its functioning, identifying the partner organizations with whom it may junction jointly, and so on.¹⁸⁵ Another significant failure of this Organization is its failure to take the initiative for the constitution and the establishment of consumer courts.

6.2.1.2.2: District Magistrate:

Any District Magistrate within his jurisdiction has the same powers and functions as the Director General under The consumer protection Act,2009 and such District Magistrate may exercise or discharge such power or functions without the Director General's prior approval.¹⁸⁶ Also the District magistrate has the power of conducting mobile courts under the Mobile Courts Act 2009.(A District Magistrate may, for performing his functions on his behalf, delegate his powers to any subordinate Executive Magistrate under such conditions as may be determined by him. The District Magistrate or, as the case may be, the Executive Magistrate shall immediately inform the Director General, in writing, about any action taken under this Act¹⁸⁷).

6.2.2: Consumer Justice System in India:

Consumer Dispute Resolution Agencies were established as consumer courts to deal with disputes, conflicts, and grievances. It is a forum where a consumer can file a case against a seller if he believes the seller has cheated or exploited him. The purpose of having a separate forum for consumer disputes is to ensure that such disputes are resolved quickly and cheaply. (When consumers file a case, the court primarily looks to see if they can prove the exploitation through evidence such as bills or purchase memos. In cases where no such evidence is presented, courts

¹⁸⁴ Id. s 70

¹⁸⁵ Zahangir Alam Khan, Consumer Justice In Bangladesh: A Critical Study of Laws & Rules, Dhaka University Institutional Repository, 2016, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/Zahangir%20Alam%20Khan.pdf

¹⁸⁶ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 69 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

¹⁸⁷ Id. at S 69

rarely rule in favor of the plaintiff. The Court mostly decides its verdict based on the violations of Consumer Rights.¹⁸⁸)

6.2.2.1: Types of Consumer Courts:

1) District Consumer Dispute Redressal Forum:

Establish a District Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, to be known as the District Commission, in each district of the State: Provided that the State Government may, if it deems fit, establish more than one District Commission in a district.¹⁸⁹ Every proceeding before the District Commission shall be conducted by the President of that Commission and at least one member thereof, sitting together: Provided that where a member, for any reason, is unable to conduct a proceeding till it is completed, the President and the other member shall continue the proceeding from the stage at which it was last heard by the previous member.¹⁹⁰ At the first hearing of the complaint after its admission, or at any later stage, if it appears to the District Commission that there exists elements of a settlement which may be acceptable to the parties, except in such cases as may be prescribed, it may direct the parties to give in writing, within five days, consent to have their dispute settled by mediation.¹⁹¹ If the District Commission is satisfied that the goods complained about have any of the defects specified in the complaint, or that any of the allegations in the complaint about the services or any unfair trade practices, or claims for compensation under product liability are proven, it shall issue an order directing to the opposing party.

2) State Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission:

Establish a State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, known as the State Commission, in the State.¹⁹² On the application of the complainant or of its own motion, the State Commission may, at any stage of the proceeding, transfer any complaint pending before a District Commission to another District Commission within the State if the interest of justice so

¹⁸⁸ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Court, 30 May 1.22 PM

¹⁸⁹ The Consumer Protection Act, 2019, § 28, No 54, Act of Parliament, 2019 (India)

¹⁹⁰ Id. at s 36

¹⁹¹ Id. at s 37

¹⁹² Id. at s 42

requires.¹⁹³ The complaint with such modifications as may be necessary, be applicable to the disposal of complaints by the State Commission. The State Commission may also declare any terms of contract, which is unfair to any consumer, to be null and void.¹⁹⁴ The State Commission shall have the power to review any of the order passed by it if there is an error apparent on the face of the record, either of its own motion or on an application made by any of the parties within thirty days of such order.¹⁹⁵

3) National Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission:

Establish a National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission known as the National Commission.¹⁹⁶ The provisions relating to complaints under sections 35, 36, 37, 38 and 39 shall, with such modifications as may be considered necessary, be applicable to the disposal of complaints by the National Commission. The National Commission may also declare any terms of contract, which is unfair to any consumer to be null and void.¹⁹⁷ The National Commission shall have the power to review any of the order passed by it if there is an error apparent on the face of the record, either of its own motion or on an application made by any of the parties within thirty days of such order.¹⁹⁸ Where the National Commission ex parte passes an order, the aggrieved party may make an application to the Commission for setting aside such order.¹⁹⁹ On the application of the complainant or of its own motion, the National Commission may, at any stage of the proceeding, in the interest of justice, transfer any complaint pending before the District Commission of one State to a District Commission of another State or before one State Commission to another State Commission.²⁰⁰

6.2.2.2: Jurisdiction:

Pecuniary Jurisdiction:

¹⁹³ Id. at s 48

¹⁹⁴ Id. at s 49

¹⁹⁵ Id. at s 50

¹⁹⁶ Id. at s 53

¹⁹⁷ Id. at s 59

¹⁹⁸ Id. at s 60

¹⁹⁹ Id. at s 61

²⁰⁰ Id. at s 62

- a) The District Consumer Dispute Redressal Forum has the pecuniary jurisdiction of up to an amount that does not exceed crore rupees.²⁰¹
- b) The State Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission has the pecuniary jurisdiction where the claim exceeds 20 lakhs but does not exceed ten crore rupees.²⁰²
- c) The Nation Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission has the pecuniary jurisdiction where the claim exceeds the amount of ten crore rupees.²⁰³

Territorial Jurisdiction:

After establishing pecuniary jurisdiction, territorial jurisdiction is to be considered. A complaint may be filed in the court located within those local limits:

- a) When the opposing party chooses to live or work within those areas.
- b) Where the cause of action arises from.

Appellate Jurisdiction:

- If a consumer is not satisfied with the decision made by the district forum, they may appeal to the state commission.²⁰⁴
- If the consumer is aggrieved by the decision made by the state commission, they may appeal to the national commission.²⁰⁵
- If a consumer is not satisfied with the decision made by the national commission, they may approach the Supreme Court for an appeal.²⁰⁶

6.3: Consumer Remedies and access to Justice:

6.3.1: Remedies available to consumer:

- a) Correction of defects in the goods as identified by the appropriate laboratory.
- b) Replacement of the goods with new, defect-free goods.
- c) A refund of the purchase price or, in some cases, the charges paid.

²⁰¹ Id. at s 34(1)

²⁰² Id. at s 47

²⁰³ Id. at s 58

²⁰⁴ Id. at s 41

²⁰⁵ Id. at s 51

²⁰⁶ Id. at s 67

- d) Compensation, with or without interest, for harassment and loss or injury caused by negligence.
- e) Correction of defects in the goods or deficiencies in the services in question.
- f) Cessation of unfair or restrictive trade practices or non-repetition of such practices.
- g) Make it illegal to sell hazardous goods.
- h) Avoiding the production of hazardous goods.
- i) Payment of a sum as determined by it, if it believes that a large number of consumers who are not easily identifiable have suffered loss or injury.
- j) Issuing corrective advertising to counteract the effect of misleading advertising at the expense of the opposing party responsible for the misleading advertisement.
- k) Removal of adulterated goods.

6.3.2: Remedies under the consumer protection Act:

Offences and Penalties under Indian Consumer protection Act:

- 1) Punishment for false or misleading advertisement:

Any manufacturer or service provider who causes a false or misleading advertisement to be made which is prejudicial to the interest of consumers shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to two years and with fine which may extend to ten lakh rupees; and for every subsequent offence, be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to five years and with fine which may extend to fifty lakh rupees.²⁰⁷

- 2) Punishment for manufacturing for sale or storing, selling or distributing or importing products containing adulterant.

Whoever, by himself or by any other person on his behalf, manufactures for sale or stores or sells or distributes or imports any product containing an adulterant shall be punished, with imprisonment for a term which may extend to six months to seven years and with fine which may extend to one lakh to ten lakh rupee.²⁰⁸

²⁰⁷ Id. at s 89

²⁰⁸ Id. at s 90

3) Punishment for manufacturing for sale or for storing or selling or distributing or importing spurious goods:

Whoever, by himself or by any other person on his behalf, manufactures for sale or stores or sells or distributes or imports any spurious goods shall be punished, with imprisonment for a term which may extend to one year to imprisonment for life and with fine which may extend to three lakh to ten lakh rupees.²⁰⁹

Offences and Penalties under Bangladeshi Consumer protection Act:

1) Punishment for not using cover of goods etc.

If any person violates any obligation, imposed by any Act or rules, of selling any goods within cover and inscribing weight, amount, ingredients, instructions for use, maximum, retail; price, date of manufacture, date of packaging and date of expiry of that goods on the label, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 1 (one) year, or with fine not exceeding Taka 50 (fifty) thousands, or with both.²¹⁰

2) Punishment for selling adulterated goods or medicine.

If any person knowingly sells or offers to sell any adulterated goods or medicine, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 3 (three) years, or with fine not exceeding Taka 2 (two) lacs, or with both.²¹¹

3) Punishment for manufacturing or processing goods in illegal process.

If any person manufactures or processes any goods in a process which is injurious to human life or health and prohibited under any Act or rules, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 2 (two) years, or with fine not exceeding Taka 1 (one) lac, or with both.²¹²

4) Punishment for deceiving buyers by false advertisement: If any person deceives any buyer by any false or untrue advertisement for the purpose of selling any goods or

²⁰⁹ Id. at 91

²¹⁰ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 37, No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

²¹¹ Id. at s 41

²¹² Id. at s 43

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service, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 1 (one) year, or with fine not exceeding Taka 2 (two) lacs, or with both.²¹³

6.3.3: Remedies under other Law:

India and Bangladesh have many laws to protect the rights of consumers. Other laws have criminal and civil remedies to protect the rights of consumers. I discussed others law remedies for the consumer in Chapter three.

6.3.4: Access to Justice:

The 2009 Act governs the procedure for filing a complaint in Bangladesh. According to section 76(1), any person who is a general consumer or is likely to be a consumer may file a written complaint with the Director General or any person authorized by the Director General against any anti-consumer right practice under the 2009 Act.

The complaint must be in writing and have the receipt of the products or services annexed to it. The complaint can be made in person, through fax, e-mail, website or other electronic means of communication or through any other way. The complainant must mention his full name, father and mother's names, address, contact details and profession. If a complaint is proved to be true after investigation or inquiry, the Director General or any officer empowered by him may impose fine upon the person.²¹⁴ As per the CPRA 2009, no complaint can be entertained by the Court without endorsement of the Director General of the Consumer Rights Protection Department.

Similarly, In the India, First of all, an aggrieved party has to send a notice to the goods or service provider. The notice must communicate the intention of the complainer regarding the defects of the goods or services or any unfair practice. The notice should be considered as an attempt to settle the complaint without approaching the Consumer Court.²¹⁵ If the seller refuses to address the consumer's complaint, the next step is to file a complaint under the Consumer Protection Act of 1986. A lawyer is not always required when filing a complaint. A person who has been

²¹³ Id. at s 44

²¹⁴ The Daily Star, Filing complaint by consumers, (14 March 2017 12:00 AM), <https://www.thedailystar.net/law-our-rights/filing-complaint-consumers-1375501>,

²¹⁵ Legitquest, <https://www.legitquest.com/legal-guide/consumer-court>, 30 May 8:52 Pm

wronged may file a complaint. He or she must include the following information in the complaint:

1. Name, description and the address of the complainant(s) and the Opposite Party or parties.
2. Cause of Action, the approximate date, time and venue.
3. Relevant facts relating to the cause of action.
4. The Relief or Remedy claimed by the complainant in accordance with the facts of the case.
5. Signature and Verification by the complainant or his authorized agent.

Copies of material evidence and relevant documents that support your case in Consumer Court are important. These documents include:

- a) A copy of the bill, receipt of delivery, packaging of a product, a record of online booking of the goods bought
- b) Warranty/Guarantee certificates
- c) A copy of the written complaint and notice sent to the manufacturer/seller²¹⁶

Choose the appropriate forum for filing the complaint based on the pecuniary jurisdiction, which is calculated based on the total value of goods and services purchased or obtained, as well as the amount of compensation sought. Depending on the forum, submit the prescribed fee along with the complaint. The court fee is determined by the value of the goods purchased and the amount of compensation sought.

6.4: Role of Judiciary in Consumer Protection: In Indian and Bangladesh judiciary plays a very vital role for consumer protection. In the latest judgment of Neena Aneja and Ors. v Jai Prakash Associates Ltd²¹⁷, (the division bench of the Supreme Court while discussing the matter of whether a complaint which was filed and registered under the Act of 1986, before the new Act of 2019 came into force, has to be entertained under the provisions of the erstwhile

²¹⁶ Prachi Darji, How to File a Case in Consumer Court?, (myadvo) (30 May 2022 9:01 Pm), <https://www.myadvo.in/blog/how-to-file-a-case-in-consumer-court>

²¹⁷ Neena Aneja and Ors. v Jai Prakash Associates Ltd, MANU/SC/0190/2021

legislation, passed references to what the intent behind the new legislation was. The change in pecuniary jurisdiction led to dispute in regard to transfer of cases between different forums. The Hon'ble bench analysed the Statement of Objects and Reasons of the new Act to establish background for the case and to reflect legislative intent. On the same, Court noted that "The Act of 2019, as indicated by its long title, is enacted to provide "for protection of the interests of consumers". The Statement of Objects and Reasons took note of the tardy disposal of cases under the erstwhile legislation. Thus, the necessity of inducing speed in disposal was to protect the rights and interests of consumers. The Act of 2019 has taken note of the evolution of consumer markets by the proliferation of products and services in light of global supply chains, e-commerce and international trade. New markets have provided a wider range of access to consumers. But at the same time, consumers are vulnerable to exploitation through unfair and unethical business practices. The Act has sought to address "the myriad and constantly emerging vulnerabilities of the consumers". The recurring theme in the new legislation is the protection of consumers which is sought to be strengthened by procedural interventions such as strengthening class actions and introducing mediation as an alternate forum of dispute resolution." The Court further went on to reflect how the legislative intent must have been to protect and support consumers and hence if the cases need to transfer between forums on enactment of it would defeat its own purpose²¹⁸).

In the case of *Srinath v. Union of India*²¹⁹, Madras High Court held that, in view of Sec. 3 of Consumer Protection Act, 1986. Consumer Redressal Forums have jurisdiction to deal with claims against advocates. Sec. 2 (U) of competition Act, 2002 defines the term 'Service' along the lines of consumer protection Act, 1986. Thus it may be concluded that legal services are becoming subject of trade related laws where consumerism and market forces should be given adequate space ²²⁰.

²¹⁸ Amazonaws, <https://s3.amazonaws.com/documents.lexology.com/15075f20-ddb6-49fd-b9187d9bf48a5a95.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAVYILUYJ754JTDY6T&Expires=1653739168&Signature=ZdB5YSjT9qrd%2FWteDDVNRU8q8Hc%3D>, (28 May 2022 6.40)

²¹⁹ *Srinath v. Union of India*, (AIR 1996 Mad 427)

²²⁰ Mr. Mohd Rafiq Dar, Role of judiciary in protection of consumers with special reference to telecom industry in India. Aligarh Muslim University (India), 2012, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/judiciary.pdf

The judiciary's perspective on the protection of consumer rights

The judgement of the Supreme Court in Lucknow Development Authority v. M.K.Gupta²²¹, may be cited as an illustration. In the instant case the Supreme Court while establishing the jurisdiction of the Consumer Disputes Redressal Agencies created under the Consumer Protection Act emphasised that the service provided by a private body or a statutory or public authority are within the jurisdiction of the Consumer Protection Act. In this context, the Supreme Court also laid down that any defect or deficiency in such service would be treated as unfair trade practice and would amount to denial of service²²². Bangladesh Supreme Court monitoring all the law including Consumer protection Act.

To protect consumers on legal grounds, the Court of Law, that is the Consumer Court, has established certain acts. This Legal Protection preserves the consumer's right, which, if exercised, will provide them with justice for any dissatisfaction caused by the seller/business/manufacturer. This legal Indian and Bangladesh framework by Consumer Court also includes a large number of regulations that are strictly enforced for consumer protection.

Consumer Courts are special courts set up by the Indian Judiciary to settle consumer grievances and entertain consumer problems. A special consumer court is set up to ensure that justice is done quickly and efficiently, without undue hardship to the complainant. Also to handle the sheer number of cases, the consumer courts help lessen the burden on the judiciary system. Another major advantage that the consumer court offers is that the whole process is fairly simple. One does not even need to hire a lawyer or any legal professional for the hearing if he thinks it is not required. Self-representation is possible in a consumer court. Right from submitting a complaint to the process of hearing all procedures are kept simple and uncomplicated.²²³ The main function of the consumer court is to offer redress to consumers and to maintain seller's orientation toward fairly treating the consumer. Approaching a consumer court is cheap as

²²¹ Development Authority v. M.K.Gupta, (1994) ISCC 243)

²²² Mr. Mohd Rafiq Dar, Role of judiciary in protection of consumers with special reference to telecom industry in India. Aligarh Muslim University (India), 2012, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/judiciary.pdf

²²³ Toppr, <https://www.toppr.com/guides/business-studies/consumer-protection/legal-protection-to-consumers/>, (28 May 2022 7.21)

plaintiffs can represent themselves without a lawyer and are only required to pay a nominal fee.²²⁴ However, in Bangladesh CRPA does not allow either the Council or the Directorate created under the law to receive complaints from consumers. This is an uncommon feature for a consumer protection law. Most consumer laws allow receipt of complaints directly from the consumers under some institutional mechanism or the other. The Bangladeshi Act provides only for redress in the usual criminal and civil courts. As per the CPRA 2009, no complaint can be entertained by the Court without endorsement of the Director General of the Consumer Rights Protection Department. Therefore, only competent government officers are entitled to institute a case against any violation of such laws.²²⁵ The court of original jurisdiction is the Metropolitan Magistrate in metropolitan areas and the Court of Judicial Magistrate 1st Class in non-metropolitan areas.²²⁶ Bangladesh has no specific court for consumer.

6.5: Supreme Court stands up for the rights of consumers:

In India, A judgement of the Supreme Court on 29 August, 2011, once for all settled the issue whether a consumer or an authorised Consumer Organisation Representative (ACOR) could represent consumers in the district consumerforum, state commission and national commission by clearly stating that an authorized representative has every right to represent, argue, appeal and perform all acts that are necessary. The Supreme Court hit the nail on the coffin of the efforts by traders and service providers, some district forum presidents, state commission presidents and most importantly the Bar Council of India to keep consumer representatives out and make this quasi-judicial tribunal a lawyers' forte.²²⁷ The significance of Consumer Protection Act has been described by Supreme Court in Lucknow Development Authority vs. M.K.Gupta (Attached herein below) in the following words, In fact the law meets long felt necessity of protecting the common man from such wrongs for which the remedy under ordinary law, for various reasons, has become illusory. Various legislations and regulations permitting the state to intervene and protect interest of consumers have become a haven for unscrupulous ones as the enforcement

²²⁴ Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer_Court, (28 May 2022 7.27)

²²⁵ HR Legal resources, <https://www.hg.org/legal-articles/protecting-consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-39014>, (28 May 2022 7.24)

²²⁶ The Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009, § 57 , No 26, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (Bangladesh)

²²⁷ Mr. Mohd Rafiq Dar, Role of judiciary in protection of consumers with special reference to telecom industry in India. Aligarh Muslim University (India), 2012, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/judiciary.pdf

machinery does not move or it moves ineffectively, inefficiently and for reasons, which are not necessary to be stated. The importance of the Act lies in promoting welfare of the society by enabling the consumer to participate directly in the market economy. It attempts to remove the helplessness of a consumer which he faces against powerful business, described as, 'a net work of rackets' or a society in which, 'producers have secured power' to 'rob the rest' and the might of the public bodies which are degenerating into store house of inaction where papers do not move from one desk to another as a matter of duty and responsibility, but for extraneous considerations leaving the common man helpless, bewildered and shocked. The malady is becoming so rampant, widespread and deep that the society instead of bothering, complaining and fighting for it, is accepting it as part of life. The enactment in these unbelievable yet harsh realities appears to be a silver lining, which may in course of time succeed in checking the rot." Preamble declares the object with which the enactment has been proposed and what it seeks to accomplish. Preamble assumes active role in case of any ambiguity in the interpretation of a provision in the statute. It is necessary to have a look at the Preamble as it unfolds the mind of the Parliament. "An Act to provide for better protection of the interests of consumers and for that purpose to make provision for the establishment of consumer councils and other authorities for the settlement of consumer's disputes and for matters connected therewith."²²⁸

In *S.B.Singh Gurjan v. Telecommunication Department Jodhpur*, complainant was a subscriber of telephone and though he had not applied for STD/ISD connection these facilities were provided and he received unwanted bills for STD and ISD calls. The complainant received a massive bill for March 1996 for STD calls. The complainant complained with the telephone department and a provisional bill was issued. Again in May 1996, the complainant received a bill for Rs.2, 15,186/- and a provisional bill was issued after complaining. The telephone department took no action to disconnect the STD facility. The District Forum and State Commission dismissed the complaint. In the appeal, National Commission held that so far as section 70 of the Contract Act is concerned, the complainant could not be held liable for calls made by strangers.²²⁹

²²⁸ Lucknow Development Authority vs. M.K.Gupta [III (1993) CPJ 7]

²²⁹ *S.B.Singh Gurjan v. Telecommunication Department Jodhpur*, (2005) II CPJ 6 NC

The judiciary's perspective on the protection of consumer rights

In *Secretary, Tirumurugan Co-operative Agrl. Credit Society vs. M.Lalitha* (Attached hereinbelow) through legal representatives & Ors, The Supreme Court held that “having due regard to the scheme of the Act and purpose sought to be achieved to protect the interests of the consumers, better the provisions are to be interpreted broadly, positively and purposefully. In the context of the present case to give meaning to additional/extended jurisdiction, particularly when Section 3 seeks to provide a remedy under the Act and other remedies provided under the Acts unless there is a clear bar”. From the above, it is clear that the Forums under the C.P. Act have jurisdiction to entertain a complaint. However, other Forums/courts also have jurisdiction to adjudicate the dispute. If there is any inconsistency between the terms of a rule framed under an Act and any of the provisions of the Act, the Rule is null and void to the extent of such repugnancy.²³⁰

Common Cause vs. Union of India, (Attached hereinbelow) In this case, the Supreme Court gave directions in 1989 to all States and Union Territories to constitute District Forums and State Commissions within six weeks. Again in 1992, in the same case, the Supreme Court observed as follows: to say the least, the emerging scenario is far too depressing, betraying a total lack of willingness on most of the States to earnestly implement one of the most benevolent legislation. Such indifference renders well-meaning legislation intended to protect a large body of consumers from exploitation ineffective.²³¹

In Bangladesh, in the writ Petition Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh vs states and others, As per Article 21 of the Constitution of Bangladesh, every public servant must perform public duties and observe the constitution and the laws. Under the present situation, the provision of Article 21 of The Constitution of Bangladesh has been violated. For that the, fresh food is essential for the life of the citizen living in Dhaka City. So at this stage, there is no alternative to stop the adulteration of food. For that disregard for laws and legal provisions and failure to ensure proper steps, the respondents have caused enough threat to the citizen's life, and the city dwellers are adversely affecting the right to life. Under these circumstances, the respondents are

²³⁰ *Tirumurugan Co-operative Agrl. Credit Society vs. M.Lalitha* (Attached hereinbelow) through legal representatives & Ors, (2004 CTJ 1 SC)

²³¹ *Common Cause vs. Union of India I* (1993) CPJ 1 (SC)

legally bound to take all necessary steps to stop food adulteration. After hearing the parties the Hon'ble Court issued Rule Nisi upon the respondents and granted ad-interim order.²³²

The High Court Division's directive for the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection to hold drives all over the country against violations of the rights of consumers is welcome as the marketing of substandard food products even in rural areas still continues, with none to check the serious crimes that affect public health. The court in response to a public interest litigation writ petition filed by the Conscious Consumers' Society on Sunday also directed the directorate to widen its drive against any violation of consumer rights, including illegal bus fare increase, sales of adulterated food and medicine and lawyers charging high fees from clients. The court sounded a warning that the institution and its officials would be sent to jail and not to the Anti-Corruption Commission on receipt of further irregularities. As the Bangladesh Food Safety Authority's chair apologised for a failure to withdraw and destroy 52 substandard food products of 43 companies, the court discharged him from the contempt of court charge on the condition that he would never flout court orders and continue holding drives against substandard food products and keep the court informed of the drives. The court on May 23 issued the contempt rule against the Food Safety Authority chair asking him to explain by June 16 why he would not be punished for contempt of the court for not complying with its May 12 order to remove and destroy the substandard food products and take action against the manufacturers.²³³

Supreme Court, High Court division, issues order on food adulteration. On April 29th, 2014, the High Court ordered the government to inform it within two weeks of what steps they had taken to halt the poisoning of food and against its perpetrators. The bench of Justice Mirza Hussain Haider and Justice Khurshid Alam Sarkar passed the order following a writ petition lodged by Supreme Court lawyer Kazi Mynul Hasan. The court also issued a rule seeking an explanation from the government as to why they should not be directed to ensure production and sale of safe

²³² Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh vs states and others, Writ Petition 2010

²³³ Staff Reporter, Welcome court directives on consumer rights, Newage, Jun 19,2019 00:05, <https://www.newagebd.net/article/75795/article/index.php>

food and to take proper legal action against the people who are responsible for adulteration of food and its selling.²³⁴

6.6: Case Law for consumer:

1) **Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr:** In this case, the appellant had purchased a second - hand truck under a Hire Purchase agreement. The vehicle was insured by the respondent insurance company. One day when he was driving the truck, a passenger asked him to stop the truck and give him a lift. When he stopped the truck, the passenger brutally assaulted the driver and fled with the vehicle. An FIR was lodged and the respondent finance company was intimated about the theft. However, the insurance company rejected the claim on the ground of breach of terms of the policy. The complainant approached District Consumer Disputes Forum, State Commission and National Commission to compensate him for the loss. All of them had rejected the case. So, finally he approached the Supreme Court.²³⁵

Judgment: The Supreme Court held that the appellant was not at all in fault. It can be considered as a breach of the policy, but not a fundamental breach to bring the insurance policy to an end and terminate the insurance policy. The two - judge bench of Supreme Court directed the respondent insurance company to pay 75% of the insured amount along with 9% interest p.a. from the date of filing the claim. The court also directed the insurance company to pay sum of Rs. 1, 00, 000 as compensation.²³⁶

2) Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited:

Ashok Iron Works, a private company which manufactures iron had applied for obtaining electricity from the state's power generation company - the Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (hereinafter KTPC) for commencing its iron production. In spite of paying charges and obtaining confirmation for the supply of 1500 KVA energy in February 1991, the actual supply did not begin until ten months later, in November 1991. This delay incurred a huge loss

²³⁴ Moniruzzaman Uzzal, Food adulteration reaches new height, Dhakatribune, April 29th, 2014 09:01 pm, <https://archive.dhakatribune.com/uncategorized/2014/04/29/food-adulteration-reaches-new-height>

²³⁵ Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr, Civil Appeal No(S). 21552 Of 2017 (India)

²³⁶ Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr, Civil Appeal No(S). 21552 Of 2017 (India)

for Ashok Iron Works. This company had filed a complaint to the Belgaum Consumer Dispute Forum and later Karnataka High Court. The legal argument by KPTC was that the complaint was not maintainable as the consumer Protection Act 1986 excludes commercial supply of goods. It also made an argument that the company in engaged in manufacturing iron and intended to use it for commercial consumption which is excluded under the Act. He also said that, the complainant is not a 'person' under Section 2(1)(m) of the Act, 1986.²³⁷

Judgment: In this case, Supreme Court gave his rulings. The Supreme Court mentioned the General Clause Act that includes a private company within the purview of the definition of a "Person." It was also held that the supply of electricity by the KPTC to a consumer would be covered under Section 2(1)(o) being 'service.' Also, if the electrical energy consumer is not provided to a consumer in time as is agreed upon, then under Section (2)(1)(g), then there can be a case for deficiency in service. Therefore, the clause stating "supply" of goods for commercial purpose would not be applied. The Supreme Court sent this case back to District Forum for retrial on these grounds.²³⁸

3) Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors:

This **consumer protect act** case arises out of a complaint of medical negligence where a 20-year-old engineering student was admitted to the Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences (NIMS) after he complaint about the acute chest pain. After several tests and x - rays, a tumor was revealed. Though, it could not be diagnosed whether the tumor was malignant or not, therefore, the patient was advised to undergo surgical removal of the same. After the surgery, the patient developed paralysis. There was a complete loss of control over the lower limbs and other related complications also raised leading to urinary tract infections, bedsores, etc. The family of the patient held NIMS and the State of Andhra Pradesh statutorily liable (being a government hospital) liable for this utmost negligence. Family also claimed that no pre-operative tests conducted, no neurosurgeon was present during operation. Consent was only taken for the tumor

²³⁷ Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited, Civil IVIL Appeal No 1879 Of 2003 (India)

²³⁸ Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited, Civil IVIL Appeal No 1879 Of 2003 (India)

excision, but the doctors also removed ribs, tumor mass and destroyed blood vessels leading to condition of paralysis.²³⁹

Judgment: Based on the evidence, Supreme Court held that a huge negligence was made out on the part of doctors and the hospital. Hence, the court awarded damages worth Rs. 1 crore to compensate present and prospective medical expenses and suffering of life.²⁴⁰

6.7: Conclusion:

The Consumer Protection Act has evolved over the last decade, and the judiciary is responsible for keeping consumer protection updated with changing times. The judiciary plays a vital role in implementing any law in a country. It also plays an essential role in implementing the consumer rights protection Act. The Supreme Court has given many judgments in one era in favor of consumers. These judgments will play an important role in protecting consumer rights. Consumer departments in India and Bangladesh are working to protect consumer rights. Accept consumer complaints and investigate complaints and seek redress. According to the jurisdiction, consumers in India first have to file a complaint in District Consumer Dispute Redressal Forum. If the Consumer is not satisfied with the District consumer Dispute Redressal forum's order, there is an opportunity to appeal to the State Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission. If the Consumer is not satisfied with the State Consumer Dispute Redressal Commission, they can appeal to the Supreme Court of India. Similarly, in Bangladesh, The consumer is the first to file a complaint with the consumer rights Department. After receiving the complaint, the consumer rights department investigates and arranges redressal. If the consumer is not satisfied with the remedy, then the consumer can file a case with the Judicial Magistrate subject to the permission of the department. There is an opportunity to appeal against the order of the Judicial Magistrate in the High Court. Moreover, the judiciary monitors whether the laws are being implemented properly. At present, consumers can easily take legal action if their rights are violated. So that consumers can get involved in the process of justice. So that consumers get the proper justice.

²³⁹ Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors, Civil Appeal No.4119 Of 1999 (India)

²⁴⁰ Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors, Civil Appeal No.4119 Of 1999 (India)

Chapter: Seven

Conclusion and Suggestions:

Consumer rights are neglected in both Bangladesh and India. It is essential to make consumers aware of their fundamental rights to protect them from unfair and aggressive business practices. Unscrupulous businesspeople cause consumer rights to be violated in India and Bangladesh due to some corrupt businessmen. Consumer rights have existed since ancient Indian times, but there was no law-making and law-enforcement system. Later, during the Mughal rule, written orders were issued for the protection of consumers. The Government of India enacted a comprehensive law in 1985 to protect consumers. However, with the increase in e-commerce, misleading advertisements, and fraud of traders, the Act is to be amended in 2019. And, In 2009 the government of Bangladesh made a law for the protection of consumers but this law could not play a role in implementation and enforcement. At present, to protect the rights of consumers, increase consumers' awareness and make more effective laws against rogue traders, black market, middlemen and provide punishment. Consumer rights are an essential aspect that every business should consider. Most companies provide low-quality products to consumers and do not provide detailed information about the products. Manufacturers create unhealthy environments in their products and make fraudulent advertisements. The economy can move towards an expanded state through social development. Traders of low-quality and duplicate products are creating artificial food crises for higher profits. Consumers need to be educated to protect themselves from such traders. The government needs to take effective action to increase consumer awareness, and the private sector needs to come forward to establish consumer rights. If consumers are protected, there will be social progress, and at the same time, the country will move towards prosperity, say experts. Consumer complaints about poor quality, harmful products and over-pricing are common in Bangladesh and India. They are caused by unskilled salespeople, lack of awareness and unscrupulous people who are greedy for profit. These problems are more common in rural areas due to lack of access and poor infrastructure. Many manufacturers make products in an unhealthy environment and market these harmful products, and consumers are encouraged to sell them. Consumers do not easily understand whether these products are genuine or fake. It is impossible to select quality products and choose the right one due to consumer awareness. India and Bangladesh have no political commitment or program to

protect consumers. Political parties may seek help from merchants and manufacturers, who create artificial crises in the market. The government machinery is fragile in terms of implementation as its machinery does not work correctly. So the non-government organization should come forward to help the consumers. Most people in India and Bangladesh are unaware of consumer rights protection and the law. Unethical traders provide unsafe products, adulterated products, or substandard products to the market for profit. Raising awareness to protect the rights of consumers is a major cause of concern. Consumer movements spread to protect consumers from exploitation by unscrupulous manufacturers, traders, and service providers. In India and Bangladesh, the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 and Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009 were enacted. Provision was made for the establishment of a consumer protection authority for the settlement of consumer disputes. The consumer is the last means of using the product. Consumers want their essential products to be available 24 hours a day and seven days a week. Retailers are trying to sell products for a more extended period to meet the needs of consumers. They can quickly check and choose which product to buy by visiting there and ordering at any time. It is impossible to enforce the law in many cases due to a lack of awareness. Many local and foreign non-profit organizations are working for consumers' awareness and rights. The United Nations has developed guidelines for implementing consumer rights worldwide. We should all be more vocal in protecting consumer rights. The right to safety is one of the most commonly recognized fundamental consumer rights. Consumers should be able to trust that the things they buy are reasonably safe when used as advised. This implies that the government will pay attention to their interests through well-crafted statutes and administrative rules. The Indian consumer protection Act, 2019 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights. The Act provides six rights of consumers, and also this Act protects from adulterated, misleading advertisements, unfair trade, and faulty goods. India and Bangladesh have different laws related to consumer rights which may not play an influential role. The consumer rights protection Act 2009 has been enacted to expand the scope of consumer rights. The Act also includes provisions that allow consumers to file complaints online and to hear and/or examine parties through video-conferencing. It covers the field of adulteration and fake goods. The India and Bangladesh Sale of Goods Act, 1930 includes the contract of sale, conditions and warranties in the sale. This Act also protects consumers from adulterated, false advertisements and goods. Institutions that have been established through the

Consumer Rights Protection Act must work sincerely towards consumers. The Department of Consumer Protection and various non-governmental organizations play a significant role in raising consumer awareness. Most of the consumers live in villages, and most lack education. Due to a lack of education, consumers don't know about rights or do not want to know on their own. Non-profit organizations work for consumers, receive complaints, arrange hearings, and redress grievances. Market system monitors so that misleading advertisements, false goods, and adulterated products cannot be marketed. Various government departments run programs to increase awareness of products and consumer safety.

The campaign Jago Grahak Jago was started in 2005 by the Department of Consumer Affairs of India. It has shielded consumers against marketing malpractices and has successfully redressed consumer complaints. The Government used several different channels to create awareness among consumers. Following is the list of the channels used by the Government to meet the objectives of the program. Despite multiple attempts, consumer protection and consumerism in India are still in their infancy. Given the context of economic disparity, level of education, and ignorance, educating consumers remains a massive undertaking. Most of the people in Bangladesh do not know about the existence of their rights as consumers. The Bangladesh Food Safety Network (BFSN) is comprised of five founding NGOs. The BFSN has played a critical role in the delivery of consumer education to many districts of the country. Millions of women and school children have been reached with messages about food safety. The most important thing for consumer protection is to increase consumer education and awareness. A consumer should know how to buy a product, what to do if it is defective and how to find a remedy if deceived. There are many governmental and non-governmental organizations in India and Bangladesh for consumer rights protection. In India and Bangladesh, non-governmental organizations are working with government departments for consumer protection. They promote consumer education, awareness and provide legal assistance to consumers. Consumers play an essential role in a country's economy; there is no alternative to protecting them from harm. Most consumers are unable to purchase the right product because they are not aware of their rights and responsibilities. Unscrupulous traders are constantly supplying adulterated products in the market. Even those who know about their rights do not complain because they do not want to get

involved in any trouble. Shopkeepers in India and Bangladesh charge consumers more than a specific price for a product. Consumers cannot say anything because they do not know their rights. Many non-governmental organizations are working on consumer rights, but their activities are not reaching everyone due to a large number of consumers. Unscrupulous traders adulterate products, and misleading advertisements are increasing day by day. Although there are specific laws on consumer rights, they cannot enforce appropriate actions. The situation in Bangladesh is worse than in India. Government departments need to play a more significant role in protecting consumers. Adulterating goods are marketed in beautiful wrappers, and those products are sold to consumers using chemicals. The worst situation is in the village consumers. They lack education, are not aware of themselves, and even if they take measures to make them aware, they do not accept them. Shopkeepers sell goods at higher prices to consumers due to increased prices due to intermediaries. Consumers are more likely to be deceived by buying in an online shop, where goods can be easily purchased. When this product reaches the consumers, they are not satisfied with this product. Some rogue retailers sell low-quality products to consumers for a higher profit. This is endangering the health of consumers. Retail stores are goods buying centers. Consumers buy goods directly from manufacturers or importers themselves or wholesale through wholesalers and sell them to marginal users. In India and Bangladesh retailers sell goods at a higher price than the fixed price if any stranger or foreigner buys a product. Products that are in high demand make a product crisis on their own and are supplied to the market at a much higher price. Consumers have nothing to do here. Consumers are being deceived through adulterated, fake goods and misleading advertisements. There is no fundamental institution for the conscious evolution of consumers in India and Bangladesh. The government has enacted specific laws to protect consumers, but unscrupulous traders supply products to the market. Adulterated goods reach village retailers through intermediaries and retailers sell directly to consumers. Consumers in rural areas lack awareness; they do not know how to buy products or determine the right product. The Bangladesh Consumer Rights Act urgently needs to be amended.

An impartial judiciary is required for a political system to function properly. The Indian and Bangladeshi judiciaries are among the most powerful pillars of Indian democracy. It is the third

organ of the government, responsible for delivering justice to the aggrieved party. They are the only pillar in which all Indians and Bangladeshis have complete trust. In recent years, the market has been influenced by false, misleading advertisements or representations, bargaining, offering gifts, prizes, contests, and hoardings attracting the public for products or services. As consumers, we are concerned about money, choice, health, and safety of our lives. The Consumer Protection Act has evolved over the last decade. The judiciary is responsible for keeping consumer protection updated with changing times. The Supreme Court has given many judgments in one era in favor of consumers. These judgments will play an important role in protecting consumer rights now and in the future.

Some recommendations may help develop protection rights for consumers. Such as:

- 1) The law on consumer rights that is drafted in the future must consider current societal needs and demands.
- 2) Specific consumer courts need to be established to protect consumer rights. The power and function of this court shall be under the judicial proceedings.
- 3) Consumer departments need to monitor the market regularly so that unscrupulous traders do not take advantage of the market.
- 4) To provide proper punishment to the criminals. So that he does not commit such a crime again.
- 5) To provide consumer awareness. So that they can buy the right and understandable product. Also, they can be aware of their rights.
- 6) To provision effective dispute resolution procedures for consumers.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

BOOKS:

- 1) Dr. S.R. Myneni, Consumer Protection Law (Asia Law House 2021), India
- 1) Ahamduzzaman and Syeda Shamsia Husain, Consumer Protection Law, Law Book Company, Dhaka, 2011

STATUTES:

- 1) The Consumer Protection Act, 2019 (India)
- 2) The Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules, 2020 (India)
- 3) The Constitution of India
- 4) Trade Marks Acts, 1999 (India)
- 5) Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (India)
- 6) The Bureau of Indian Standards Act, 2016
- 7) The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940(Amendment 2008) (India)
- 8) The Sale of Goods Act, 1930 (India)
- 9) The Agricultural Produce Act, 1937(India)
- 10) The Indian Penal Code, 1860
- 11) The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 1972
- 12) The Consumer Rights Protection Act (CRPA), 2009 (Bangladesh)
- 13) Digital Commerce Operational Guideline 2021(Bangladesh)
- 14) Sale of Goods Act 1930 (Bangladesh)
- 15) The Bangladesh Penal Code 1860
- 16) The Dangerous Drug Act 1940 (Bangladesh)
- 17) The Special Powers Act 1974(Bangladesh)
- 18) Control of Essential Commodities Act, 1956 (Bangladesh)
- 19) Trademark Act 2009 (Bangladesh)
- 20) The Mobile Court Act, 2009 (Bangladesh)

ARTICLES/JOURNALS:

- 1) Dr. Chatar Singh Negi and Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Consumer protection in India: Empowering consumer, 10, International Journal of Development Research. 02, 33873-33877 (2020)
- 2) Md. Emran Hossain, Consumer Protection in the Context of Existing Laws in Bangladesh, 5, JETIR, 671, 676-681 (2018)
- 3) Law Student, Consumer Rights in Bangladesh: A Critical Study, Bangladesh Journal of Legal Studies, (January 23, 2022, 12:19 AM), <https://bdjls.org/consumer-rights-in-bangladesh-a-critical-study#one>
- 4) Dr. A. Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, 132, Journal of Texas Consumer Law, 132-136, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/JCCL_India.pdf
- 5) R.P. Kangle, The Kautilya Arthashastra. Part III A Study 116 (2000)

- 6) Diya Berger, "A Tale of Two Movements: Consumer Protection in the U.S. from 1969 to 2010" 02 May 2013. CUREJ: College Undergraduate Research Electronic Journal, University of Pennsylvania, <https://repository.upenn.edu/curej/168>.
- 7) Peck, Linda, "Consuming Splendor: Society and Culture in Seventeenth-Century England", Cambridge Press, 2005
- 8) Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Consumer Organizations and the Right to Adequate Food, FAO, April 12, 2022, <https://www.fao.org/3/cb3685en/cb3685en.pdf>
- 9) WIPO, The Role of Industrial Property in the Protection of Consumers, WIPO Publication, April 13, 2022, file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/wipo_pub_648.pdf
- 10) Dr. Manoj Kumar Padhy, Consumer Protection Jurisprudence: A Constitutional Perspective, Rostrum's Law review (13 May, 2022 1.26 Pm), <https://journal.rostrumlegal.com/consumer-protection-jurisprudence-a-constitutional-perspective/>
- 11) Sheetal Sahoo & Aman Chatterjee, Consumer Protection - Problems and Prospects (13 May 2022 1.43 Pm, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1452526
- 12) Zahangir Alam Khan, Consumer Justice in Bangladesh: A Critical Study of Laws & Rules, 64 (17 January 2016)
- 13) Gazi Delwar Hosen and Syed Robayet Ferdous, The Role of Mobile Courts in the Enforcement of Laws in Bangladesh, Volume I (2010) The Northern University Journal of Law 82, 82 (2010)
- 14) Mr. Mohd Rafiq Dar, Role of judiciary in protection of consumers with special reference to telecom industry in India. Aligarh Muslim University (India), 2012, <file:///C:/Users/ABC/Desktop/judiciary.pdf>

CASES:

- 1) Neena Aneja and Ors. v Jai Prakash Associates Ltd, MANU/SC/0190/2021
- 2) Srinath v. Union of India, (AIR 1996 Mad 427)
- 3) Development Authority v. M.K.Gupta, (1994) ISCC 243)
- 4) Lucknow Development Authority vs. M.K.Gupta [III (1993) CPJ 7]
- 5) S.B.Singh Gurjan v. Telecommunication Department Jodhpur, (2005) II CPJ 6 NC
- 6) Tirumurugan Co-operative Agrl. Credit Society vs. M.Lalitha (Attached hereinbelow) through legal representatives & Ors, (2004 CTJ 1 SC)
- 7) Common Cause vs. Union of India I (1993) CPJ 1 (SC)
- 8) Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh vs states and others, Writ Petition 2010
- 9) Manjeet Singh Vs. National Insurance Company Ltd. & Anr, Civil Appeal No(S). 21552 Of 2017 (India)
- 10) Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation (KPTC) Vs. Ashok Iron Works Private Limited, Civil IVIL Appeal No 1879 Of 2003 (India)
- 11) Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences v Prasanth S. Dhananka & Ors, Civil Appeal No.4119 Of 1999 (India)

ONLINE SOURCES:

- 1) H2O, <https://h2o.law.harvard.edu>
- 2) Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org>

- 3) Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com>
- 4) Clap, <https://clap.nls.ac.in>
- 5) Vikrant Rana, <https://www.mondaq.com>
- 6) Egyankosh, <https://egyankosh.ac.in>
- 7) Researchgate, <https://www.researchgate.net>
- 8) Vedantu, <https://www.vedantu.com>
- 9) Fao, <https://www.fao.org>
- 10) Pib, <https://pib.gov.in>
- 11) Consumer rights organization, <https://www.thecro.in/about-us/>,
- 12) Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://cgsiindia.org>
- 13) Consumer Association of India, <https://www.consumersinternational.org>
- 14) Juralacuity, <https://juralacuity.com>
- 15) Consumer Association of Bangladesh, <https://consumerbd.org>
- 16) Banglapedia, <https://en.banglapedia.org>
- 17) Consumers International, <https://www.consumersinternational.org>
- 18) Articles junction, <http://articles-junction.blogspot.com>
- 19) India study channel, <https://www.indiastudychannel.com>
- 20) Myadvo, <https://www.myadvo.in>
- 21) Lexology, <https://www.lexology.com>
- 22) Assignment point, <https://assignmentpoint.com/>
- 23) onsumer affairs of India, <https://consumeraffairs.nic.in>
- 24) Legitquest, <https://www.legitquest.com>
- 25) Amazonaws, <https://s3.amazonaws.com>
- 26) Toppr, <https://www.toppr.com>
- 27) HG Legal Resources, <https://www.hg.org/>

NEWS PAPERS:

- 1) The Daily Star, <https://www.thedailystar.net>
- 2) The Economic Times, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com>
- 3) Zee News, <https://zeenews.india.com>
- 4) Newage, <https://www.newagebd.net/>
- 5) Prothom Alo, <https://www.prothomalo.com/>
- 6) Dhakatribune, <https://archive.dhakatribune.com>